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C O N T E N T S

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Editorial.....

It is heartening to note that our journal is able to sustain the enthusiasm and covering various facets of knowledge. It is our hope that IJMER would continue to live up to its fullest expectations savoring the thoughts of the intellectuals associated with its functioning .Our progress is steady and we are in a position now to receive evaluate and publish as many articles as we can. The response from the academicians and scholars is excellent and we are proud to acknowledge this stimulating aspect.

The writers with their rich research experience in the academic fields are contributing excellently and making IJMER march to progress as envisaged. The interdisciplinary topics bring in a spirit of immense participation enabling us to understand the relations in the growing competitive world. Our endeavour will be to keep IJMER as a perfect tool in making all its participants to work to unity with their thoughts and action.

The Editor thanks one and all for their input towards the growth of the **Knowledge Based Society**. All of us together are making continues efforts to make our predictions true in making IJMER, a Journal of Repute

Dr.K.Victor Babu
Editor-in-Chief

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REMEDIES TO HOMEBUYERS UNDER CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT (“CPA”), REAL ESTATE (REGULATION AND DEVELOPMENT) ACT (“RERA”) AND INSOLVENCY AND BANKRUPTCY CODE (“IBC”)

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Overview of Real Estate Sector

The Indian Real Estate Sector has witnessed high growth in the last two decades. People put in their hard earned money and life savings in this sector to unlock their dream homes. In India, the construction and real estate sector is the second largest employer after agriculture. However, in the recent 3-4 years there has been a slowdown in real estate sector. The reasons for slowdown of real estate sector are lack of buyer confidence in under-construction projects, unattractive/negative return on investment, economic slowdown, unfavorable loan to value ratio, high taxation on under construction homes, delayed constructions etc.

For years homebuyers were tormented and the only recourse available to them was to go to Civil Courts or Consumer Courts. However things changed with the enactment of Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act (“RERA”) and Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (“IBC”) in 2016. Now, the aggrieved Homebuyers have the option to approach Consumer Courts, Civil Courts, Real Estate Regulation Authority and NCLT. This article tried to explain the remedies available to homebuyers under Consumer Protection Act, 1986 (“CPA”), Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 (“RERA”) and Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 (“IBC”).

Consumer Protection Act (CPA)

The main objective of Consumer Protection Act 1986 is to provide speedy redressal mechanism to consumers. Consumer Protection Act applies in case consumer alleges Unfair Trade Practice or Deficiency with respect to Goods or Services. These terms are broadly defined under the act. The Homebuyers were also included within the purview of Act by interpreting the word “Services” under the Act to include construction, since construction is also a service. Three Consumer Disputes Redressal Agencies are established under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 namely District Forum, State Commission and National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission.

Jurisdiction of the District Forum: the District Forum entertains complaint where the value of the goods or services and the compensation, if any, claimed does not exceed rupees twenty lakhs.

Jurisdiction of the State Commission: the State Commission entertains complaint where the value of the goods or services and compensation, if any, claimed exceeds rupees twenty lakhs but does not exceed rupees one crore and appeals against the orders of any District Forum within the State.

Jurisdiction of the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission: the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission entertains complaint where the value of the goods or services and compensation, if any, claimed exceeds rupees one crore and appeals against the orders of any State Commission.

The Hon'ble Supreme Court in its landmark judgement in the matter of Amrapali Sapphire Developers Private Limited Vs. M/s Amrapali Sapphire Flat Buyers Welfare Association provided a major relief to the aggrieved homebuyers, it held that Homebuyers can jointly approach the National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (NCDRC) in case of dispute with the builder, where the aggregate value exceeds Rs. 1 Crore.

Relief to Homebuyers under CPA, 1986

If the allegations raised by the Homebuyer against the services of Developer or Builder are proved, the relevant Consumer Disputes Redressal Agency shall issue an order directing Developer or Builder to do one or more of the following things namely:

- a. To return the money paid to Developer or Builder
- b. To pay such amount as may be awarded by it as compensation for any loss or injury suffered by the homebuyer due to the negligence of the Developer or Builder

Section 27 of the Consumer Protection Act provides that if a Developer or Builder fails to comply with the order passed by District Forum, State Commission or National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, he shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which shall not be less than one month but which may extend to three years, or with fine which shall not be less than two thousand rupees but which may extend to ten thousand rupees, or with both.

Consumer Protection Act, 2019

The parliament passed Consumer Protection Bill, 2019 on 6th August, 2019 to replace the Consumer Protection Act, 1986. The President of India gave its assent to the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 on 9th August, 2019. However, the Consumer Protection Act, 2019 has not come into force till date. Under CPA, 2019 a new authority namely Central Consumer Protection Authority (CCPA) shall be created by the Central Government. Its main objects shall be to promote, protect and enforce the rights of consumers. It will regulate matters related to violation of consumer rights, unfair trade practices, and misleading

advertisements. Also, the pecuniary jurisdiction has been increased by CPA, 2019. The District Commission shall have jurisdiction to entertain complaints where the value of the goods or services paid as consideration does not exceed one crore rupees. The State Commission shall have jurisdiction to entertain complaints where the value of the goods or services paid as consideration, exceeds rupees one crore, but does not exceed rupees ten crore. The National Commission shall have jurisdiction to entertain complaints where the value of the goods or services paid as consideration exceeds rupees ten crore.

Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 (“RERA”)

RERA, 2016 provides for establishment of Real Estate Regulatory Authority for regulation and promotion of the real estate sector and to ensure sale of plot, apartment or building, as the case may be, or sale of real estate project, in an efficient and transparent manner and to protect the interest of consumers in the real estate sector and to establish an adjudicating mechanism for speedy dispute redressal and also to establish the Appellate Tribunal to hear appeals from the decisions, directions or orders of the Real Estate Regulatory Authority and the adjudicating officer .

Key highlights of RERA

- **Registration of Real Estate Projects:** Real estate projects are required to be registered with the Real Estate Regulatory Authority where the land proposed to be developed exceeds five hundred square meters or the number of apartments proposed to be developed exceeds eight inclusive of all phases.
- **Filing of Complaint:** the aggrieved allottees may file complaint with Real Estate Regulatory Authority or adjudicating officer.
- **Appeal:** the aggrieved allottees can make appeal against the decisions of Real Estate Regulatory Authority or adjudicating officer to the Appellate Authority, and thereafter to the High Court and the Supreme Court.
- **Deposit of amount in separate account:** Section 4 of the RERA provides that the promoters have to deposit 70% of the amount realized for the real estate project from the allottees in a separate account and the amount from the separate account shall be withdrawn by the promoter after it is certified by an engineer, an architect, and a chartered accountant in practice that the withdrawal is in proportion to the percentage of completion of the project.

Earlier, there have been certain cases wherein builder used funds raised by homebuyers for other projects or for other purposes. Section 4 prevents diversion of funds.

- **Remedy to Allottees:** As per Section 18 of the RERA, if the promoter fails to complete or is unable to give possession of an apartment, plot or building, he shall be liable on demand to the allottees, in case the allottee wishes to withdraw from the project, without prejudice to any other remedy available, to return the amount received by him in respect of that apartment, plot, building, as the case may be, with interest at such rate as may be prescribed in this behalf including compensation in the manner as provided under the Act. Provided that where an allottee does not intend to withdraw from the project, he shall be paid, by the promoter, interest for every month of delay, till the handing over of the possession, at such rate as may be prescribed.
- **Right to Information:** the allottee are entitled to all the information related to the project, be it plan layout, execution plan, stage wise completion status etc.

Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 (“IBC”)

The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, since its introduction in the year 2016 has faced lot of difficulties, especially while dealing with the real estate sector in India. We shall now discuss evolution of law with regard to real estate sector and its present position.

Homebuyers brought under the purview of financial creditors

Under IBC, Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process can be initiated against corporate debtor only by financial creditor, operational creditor or by the Corporate Debtor itself. After the introduction of IBC homebuyers were treated as orphan, they were neither considered as financial creditor nor operational creditors. Ultimately, in order to protect the interest of homebuyers the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code was amended on 6th June, 2018 and allottees of real estate projects were included in the definition of financial creditor. Several real estate companies were aggrieved with the amendment and approached Supreme Court. In its judgment dated 9th August, 2019 of Pioneer Urban Land and Infrastructure Limited and Anr. V. Union of India, the Supreme Court held that allottees/home buyers were included in the main provision, i.e. Section 5(8)(f) with effect from the inception of the Code, the explanation being added in 2018 merely to clarify doubts that had arisen. It held that the amendment is constitutional.

At present, homebuyers, just like any other financial creditor can file an insolvency case against real estate companies if the default amount involved is

Rs. One Crore or more. They have right to participate and vote in the meeting of Committee of Creditors

Application for initiating CIRP by not less than 100 allottees or not less than 10% of the total number of allottees whichever is less

Earlier even a single homebuyer could make an application to NCLT for initiation of Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process against Corporate Debtor. There have been instances where a single homebuyer has dragged a well performing real estate company into insolvency proceeding in order to claim his refund. Therefore in order to prevent a few potentially unscrupulous elements within the homebuyer community from abusing the spirit of the IBC, the Government vide Companies Amendment Act, 2019 introduced proviso under Section 7(1) of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 wherein it is mentioned that for financial creditors who are the allottees of real estate project, an application for initiation of CIRP shall be filed by not less than 100 of such allottees under the same real estate project or not less than 10 % of the total number of such allottees under the same real estate project, whichever is less.

Can a homebuyer approach cpa, rera and ibc concurrently?

In the matter of M/s M3M India Pvt. Ltd. vs. Dr Dinesh Sharma and Anr., various petitions were filed with Hon'ble High Court against the order passed by National Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission (NCDRC). The question for consideration was whether proceedings under CPA can be commenced by homebuyers against developers, after the commencement of RERA.

While passing the judgment, the Hon'ble High Court placed reliance on the Supreme Court judgment in Pioneer Urban Land and Infrastructure Ltd & Anr vs. Union of India & Ors, (2019) wherein it was held that that "RERA is to be read harmoniously with the IBC, as amended by the Amendment Act. It is only in the event of conflict that the IBC will prevail over the RERA. Remedies that are given to allottees of flats/apartments are therefore concurrent remedies, such allottees of flats/apartments being in a position to avail of remedies under the Consumer Protection Act, 1986, RERA as well as the triggering of the Code."

The Hon'ble High Court held that the remedies available to the respondents herein under CPA and RERA are concurrent and dismissed the appeal.

Conclusion

Recent trend shows that homebuyers prefer invoking an application under IBC, 2016 rather than approaching to Consumer Courts or Real Estate Regulatory Authority. The purpose of Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 is resolution of insolvency, or liquidation and not recovery. Recovery is only incidental under the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, 2016. Invoking IBC at the first

stage is like opting for operation when medicines can solve the issue. Therefore, the usage of Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code should be limited when it comes to real estate sector. It should only be used when the real estate company is unable to continue or complete the real estate project. Until then the remedies under Consumer Protection Act and Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, 2016 should be sought.

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RURAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INDIA: A STUDY OF ROLE AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract:

Rural entrepreneurship plays vital role in economy development at Global level. The economy of developing countries can be boosted with the help of rural development. India being a developing country with second largest population in the world is rich in manpower, natural resources and biodiversity. Out of total population of India 83 core population live in rural area. The development of rural area will lead to development of Indian economy. Rural entrepreneurship is the effective tool for rural enrichment. Rural entrepreneurship facilitates in optimum utilization of resources, employment generation, reduction in migration and reduction in poverty. Rural entrepreneur contribute to raise the national income through the export of rural industry produce. Rural development is real development. The present research paper main aim is to study the potential of rural entrepreneurship in rural area.

Key words: Rural Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneur, Rural Development, Challenges.

Introduction:

Indian government has focused on faster and sustains growth of economy. “Make in India” policy was announced by the Government of India with the intention to motivate and promote industrial development, innovation, entrepreneurship and skill development. Entrepreneur facilitates in capital formation, employment and socio-economic development. Mahatma Gandhi has rightly said that India lives in village. Rural economy is the backbone of Indian economy. Hence development of villages and rural areas will lead to development of the country. Entrepreneurship is an effective tool of rural development. Rural entrepreneurship is an activity of commencing and operating own business which can generate rural employment and income level. Out of the total Indian population 68.75% population live in rural areas. Agriculture is the prime occupation of rural population. The dilemmas faced by the Indian rural population are poverty, unemployment, low income, poor health facility and poor infrastructure. Establishment and development of rural

industries and rural entrepreneurship is the key for the rural problems. Government of India has continuously boosted and supported the promotion and growth of rural entrepreneurship.

A healthy and dynamic agriculture sector is a significant base of rural development and creating strong linkages to other economic sectors. Rural development consist the development of infrastructure, agriculture and allied activities, rural entrepreneurship and rural industry and social services.

Literature review:

This research is carried after the review of few literature studied previously. The literatures reviewed for present research paper are as follows:

1. Priyanka Kumari and Tarun Kumar (January, 2020), “Opportunities, Roles and Prospect Challenges of Rural Entrepreneurs in Economic Development in India”, publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338623155>. In their study explained the need and importance of rural entrepreneurship development and the opportunity of rural development through rural business. They emphasized that rural entrepreneurship can prove a best career opportunity for the rural youth.

2. Amrita Dhaliwal (2016) “Role of Entrepreneurship in Economic Development”, International Journal of scientific research and management (IJSRM) Volume 4 Issue 06 Pages 4262-4269. In this paper the role and significance of entrepreneurship is explained in the context of economy development.

3. Kushalakshi, Dr. A. Raghurama (2012), “Rural Entrepreneurship: A Catalyst for Rural Development”, International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) ISSN (Online): 2319-7064 Impact Factor (2012): 3.358. This paper studied the types, significance and problems of rural entrepreneurship of India. According to the authors of this research paper rural entrepreneurship is the key for the rural problems such as migration, poverty and unemployment.

Objectives of the Study:

- ❖ To study the role of rural entrepreneurship in rural development.
- ❖ To study the challenges faced by rural entrepreneurship.
- ❖ To study the initiatives taken by the government to encourage rural industry development.

Research Methodology:

The study of the paper is of descriptive nature. Secondary data is used for the study presented in this paper. Information related to the study is collected from

secondary source of data which comprises of books, research papers, government publications and previous studies by research scholars.

Entrepreneurship and Rural Entrepreneurship:

Entrepreneurship is an activity of setting up of own business and carrying out all the business operations by taking some financial risks to maximize the margin of profit. Rural entrepreneurship means the welfare and upbringing of the remote area. Rural Entrepreneurship defines the entrepreneurship whose origin lies in the rural areas whereas has a lot of potentials to undertake various business, industry, agriculture and play a significant role in the economic growth of the nation. The abundant availability of natural resources gives a wider scope for entrepreneurship in rural areas.

The above definition of rural entrepreneurship also defines the characteristics of an entrepreneur. A good entrepreneur must possess the qualities of self confidence, risk taking ability, decision making, market and financial knowledge and leadership.

Need of Rural Entrepreneurship:

The population explosion is the alarming issue faced by India. The ratio of the number of job opportunities to man power is declining day by day. The unemployment rate in India was recorded as 7.8 percent in February, 2020. In rural area the rate of unemployment is 7.4 percent. (Source: www.tradingeconomics.com). The need of new source of employment has enabled to evolve the concept of entrepreneurship in urban as well as in rural areas. Following indicators of rural entrepreneurship leads to rural development:-

- a) Reduction in the level of unemployment.
- b) Reduction in income disparities.
- c) Reduction in the number of migrants from rural to urban areas.
- d) Balanced regional development.
- e) Build up village republics.
- f) Optimum utilization of rural resources.
- g) Increase in share of agriculture sector.

Types of Rural Entrepreneurship:

The rural entrepreneurship can be classified in four categories as follows:

1) **Individual Entrepreneurship** – The enterprise with single ownership is known as Individual Entrepreneurship. Under this type the profit or risk is borne by a single person.

2) **Group Entrepreneurship** - It mainly covers partnership, private limited company and public limited company.

3) **Cluster Formation Entrepreneurship** - It covers NGOs, VOs, CBOs, SHGs and even networking of these groups. These also cover formal and non-formal association of a group of individuals on the basis of caste, occupation, income, etc.

4) **Cooperative Entrepreneurship** - It is an autonomous association of persons united voluntarily for a common objective.

Rural entrepreneurship has wide opportunity to evolve from rural industry. In other words rural industry is the mother of rural entrepreneurship. Agro based industry, forest based industry, and mineral based industry, textile industry and engineering services are some of the rural industries which give birth to the rural entrepreneurship.

Rural entrepreneurs can avail the opportunity created by the rural industries in the rural area. Rural entrepreneurship is the strategy of the Government to reduce poverty and unemployment which is promoted by financing the Micro, Small and Medium enterprise. Rural entrepreneurship not only benefits the entrepreneur but also the society as a whole in terms of employment generation, income generation, and social enrichment.

Role of Rural Entrepreneurship in Economic Development:

- Rural entrepreneurship as self-employment is the solution for rural poverty and unemployment.

- The migration of people for employment from rural to urban area is cut down due to employment availability in rural areas.
- It reduces the disequilibrium between the income levels of rural and developed areas.
- Profitable rural entrepreneurship attracts the investors which ultimately lead to capital formation.
- Rural entrepreneurship facilitates balanced development of the country. It helps to reduce regional disparities.
- It helps to improve the infrastructure facilities in the rural areas.
- Rural entrepreneurship aids to raise the standard of living of the rural entrepreneur.
- Rural entrepreneurship ensures optimum utilization of local resources such as raw material and man force. This helps in the reduction of cost and increase in productivity.

Challenges:

The business environment is classified as internal and external environment. The internal environment of a business comprises the strengths and weaknesses of the concern while the external environment comprises of the opportunities and challenges for the concern. Rural infrastructure, capital, investment opportunity, marketing knowledge and skill labour are the basic requirements of the rural entrepreneurship at initial stage. Following are some areas where the rural entrepreneurship faces the challenges:

1. Insufficient infrastructure facility: Underdevelopment of rural area has created the obstacle of insufficient infrastructure facilities of transportation, communication, power, health and market for rural entrepreneurship.

2. Lack of finance: Initial stage of every business demands huge capital requirement. Finance is the blood of a business. The source of finance for rural entrepreneur is very acute which consist of relatives, friends and unorganized lenders. Lack of knowledge about the government and other financial aid is a reason for lack of finance.

3. Lack of marketing skill: To cope up with the cut throat competition in the market one has to develop marketing and effective communication skills. Rural entrepreneurs

fail to promote and present their product in the competitive market due to insufficient marketing skills.

4. Shortage of skilled labours: The modern entrepreneurship requires highly skilled labours for operating the advanced knowhow. Proper training programme should be organized to train the labours which may be expensive

To overcome the above mentioned shortcoming of rural entrepreneurship Government takes initiative from time to time. The present research paper has studied the role of government to boost rural entrepreneurship in India. Eradication of poverty and unemployment are the motives of promoting rural entrepreneurship. Some government initiatives for promoting rural entrepreneurship in India are as follows:

- **Startup India Initiative:** To increase wealth and employability through increasing entrepreneurial spirit this initiative was launched by the Prime Minister in January, 2016.
- **ASPIRE:** ASPIRE was launched to promote the agro-business industry. It is a scheme for promoting innovation and rural entrepreneurship.
- **MUDRA:** Micro Units Development Refinance Agency (MUDRA) was established in 2015 to boost the growth of small enterprises in rural area.
- **Credit Guarantee Scheme for Startups (CGSS):** To provide business loan for small enterprises with zero collateral security, Government of India introduced this scheme.
- **Other Government schemes are:**
 - The Venture Capital Assistance Scheme
 - Rajiv Gandhi Udyami Mitra Yojana (RGUMY)
 - Performance and Credit Rating Scheme (Implemented through NSIC)
 - Product Development, Design Intervention and Packaging (PRODIP)
 - Khadi Karigar Janashree Bima Yojana for Khadi Artisan
 - Provision of Urban Amenities to Rural Areas (PURA)

Conclusion and suggestions:

Rural entrepreneurship is playing a significant role in rural development. Government needs focus on rural entrepreneurship development to improve rural economy. Motivating rural youth for own business is the need for rural development. Rural entrepreneurship can resolve various rural issues such as migration, unemployment and poverty. Present research paper studied the potential of rural entrepreneurship and its role in rural development. Following suggestions can help to create awareness about the significance of rural entrepreneurship among the rural population:

- Organisation of skilled based short term programmes to train the existing and new entrepreneurs.
- Process of obtaining financial aid for starting and operating the business should be easy and simple.
- Development of infrastructure facilities should be the priority in rural development and rural entrepreneurship development.

- Awareness programme regarding government schemes, market condition and knowledge, registration and advanced knowhow should be organized at grass-root level.

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EFFECT OF FAMILY CULTURE ON THE INTEGRATED DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY FOUNDATION

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Abstract

A family culture is created whether we intend to or not. Even if we don't make conscious decisions and openly discuss our values, norms and traditions within our household, we still create a family culture. Only by default, and on likely based on our own experiences as a child- rejecting what we perceived as negative and incorporating what we treasured or admired. As sensible being, we thrive when we know what our core values are. A clear vision inspires and motivates us. A sense of purpose and connection brings meaning, and helps guide decisions that will affect our children and our family's future. When it comes to family culture, often times we know what we don't want, but we're not clear on what we want or why. And if you are raising kids with a partner, you likely have different backgrounds, and have certainly been through different experiences. On the other hand, knowing your family culture can help you navigate the endless amount of (often contradicting) and follow your heart and intuition. By Aligning your decisions and actions with your values, you will find more joy and ease in your daily life. And much needed inspiration for trying times.

Keywords: Family Culture, Integrated Development, Pre School, Family Foundation, Inspiration.

Introduction

This brief introduction to family culture points at the many strands that weave together two systems, the family and the foundation. Influence doesn't move in one direction but rather is reciprocal. The family is changed by the experience of running the foundation, and the foundation, in turn, is influenced by the changes in the family. The younger generation comes on board, reflecting a new set of values and experiences and often different funding agendas. Norms are the spoken and unspoken rules of cultures. Reinforced over time, they operate as invisible constraints on family members' behavior. Norms set standards for how family members dress, talk and act. They also set limits on what is permissible or impermissible behavior under different circumstances and conditions. More than just rules of etiquette, norms provide family members

with a guide for living both within the home and without.

When Thomas and Alexandra went away to college in the 1970s, they encountered a different set of norms. There free expression was not only encouraged but considered healthy. Both of them spent several years in therapy, learning how to express their feelings, and both married spouses who grew up in family cultures in which arguing and shouting were commonplace. They didn't set limits on what is permissible or impermissible behavior under different circumstances and conditions. More than just rules of etiquette, norms provide family members with a guide for living both within the home and without.

"In our family, good manners count for everything", says Thomas. "As children, my sister and I learned not to raise our voices, never to ask personal questions, and to avoid dissension at all costs. If we violated those rules, my parents would only have to raise their eyebrows to let us know that our behavior was out of line".

To say that families have identifiable cultures, however, is not to suggest that they are static. Family is in a constant state of transition as each member moves through the cycles of life and the family itself moves from one stage to other stage of development. Marriages, birth, divorces and deaths change the family constellation and in profound ways, alter the family culture. Simultaneously larger political, economic and social forces also impinge on the family culture. Meaningful family traditions have always been a valuable tool for the parents and elders to carry out responsibility of raising children and inculcating into them social values and ethos. Family traditions ensure that the warmth and closeness of family bondage grow. In modern context, maintenance of developing family traditions continues to be as significant as they were as the earliest times.

Family Culture

Psychologists, Anthropologists and Sociologists trace different behavior

patterns of people to the different child rearing practices of their early childhood years. A number of studies have been conducted to show the importance of parental roles in the verbal communications Jacksaw(1958), adjustment as well as interpersonal interaction (Lederman 1959; Mitchell and Wilson 1967), cognitive development (Freeberg and Payne 1967) and in the academic performance (Radin and epstaein 1975, Jordan et al. 1981, Tizard et al. 1980, 1982, 1987). One fact has been recognized by several researchers of this field that only the presence of mother and father is no guarantee of adequate 'fathering' and 'mothering' but stress must be laid to the quality child relations with fathers and mothers.

Effective relationship of the child with parents is a crucial factor in the development of the personality of child. The parent-child bond is one of love, security and trust. Children imitate parents and teacher'salto at this age, therefore they should not display behaviors which they do not want their children to follow such as abusive language and telling lies. Parents actions leaves healthy impact if are inductive of positive behavior.

For boosting the integrated development of children and enhancement of their self esteem, following guidelines have been put forward:

- Try to involve your children in household activities. Give only those activities which she/he can perform according to her/his age. While celebrating festivals give children responsibilities for specific, activities as Children enjoy helping elders in various activities. Always encourage them to participate.
- Tell/read stories to your child related to festivals so that she/he knows why festivals are being celebrated.
- Always attend to child's queries, never discourage them. Concerned with the development of the Childs personality, the dimensionsof family culture have been identified as follows:
 - Control
 - Protectiveness
 - Punishment and Reward
 - Conformity
 - Socialization
 - Privileges
 - Nurturance
 - Rejection And Acceptance
 - Permissiveness
 - Values
 - Traditions And Customs

Importance of Family Level Education

The childhood experiences have a direct impact on child's future development. It has bearing on health, nutrition and social interaction in later life. The need for providing the young child with appropriate experiences through a family level learning programme, may not have seemed very necessary in the past, since children were generally brought up in a joint family system where they felt secure and loved. At the same time, the grandparents and other members of the extended family provided a stimulating environment by narrating stories and taking care of the physical, emotional and cognitive needs of the child during early years. Now the scenario has changed. Families are shifting from the traditional joint family system to more nuclear families and many more women have started working outside the home particularly in urban areas.

As a result, in the present context young children do not often get the benefit of stimulating, secure and protected environment at home. Parents are not able to give a sound foundation in pre school education at home even if they want to. A good preschool education programme can serve to effectively address these gaps and gives a fare start to all children for schooling.

The Objectives of Family Level Education Are-

- To develop good physique, adequate muscular coordination and baic motor skills
- To develop good health habits, and to build up basic skills necessary for personal adjustments such as dressing, toilet, eating, washing and cleaning.
- To encourage aesthetic appreciation.
- To develop emotional maturity by guiding the child to express, understand, accept and control his feelings and emotions.
- To encourage independence and creativity, by providing the child with sufficient opportunities for self-expression.
- To develop the child's ability to express his thoughts and feelings in fluent, correct and clear speech.

Review of Related Literature

There are prominent classes of definitions for "family" available in literature. The word "family" is derived from the Latin word "familia" which implies household and includes the master of the household, his descendants and servants. Murduck (1949) perceived the nuclear family as universal with four essential functional objectives which it always fulfilled completely. These three functions were: (1) Socialization, (2) Economic Cooperation and, (3) Reproduction. Structural definition of the family encompasses existence of at least one adult and a dependant. McDaniel et al. (2005) define family as any

group of people related either biologically, emotionally, or legally. That is, the group of people to which a person can look for his or her wellbeing. According to Srinivas & Beteilla (1964), in spite of the socio-economic and political changes, family life and family structure have remained an integral part of the Indian society with the 'spirit of family solidarity' as the sustaining power.

In western countries, family structure and related theories had seen many phases. In 1950s and 1960s, families were considered as a matter of pride. In late 1960s, many women and student movements had transformed the way we looked at family structure; families were exposed as a place for violence and suppression for women. With 21st century, it became very confusing what constitute a family. Three distinct family types have emerged: intact, blended (stepparent families) and single parent households. Single parent households will typically, Literature Review 16 Ph. D. Thesis but not exclusively, be headed by females. Blended or stepparent families are the fastest growing type of family in the U.K . In India family structure is quite different than in west.

Conclusion:

Most people do not think of their families as having a "**Culture**". They associate culture with countries and ethnic groups. But the family? For most of us, it's just a group of familiar people doing what they always do. Yet it is exactly this- a characteristic way of thinking, feeling, judging, and acting- that defines a culture. In direct and subtle ways, children are molded by the family culture into which they are born. Growing Up, their assumptions about what is right and wrong, good and bad, reflect the beliefs, values and traditions of the family culture.

"Whatever its biological inheritance from its parents and other ancestors, the child receives also from them a heritage of attitudes, sentiments, and ideals which may be termed the family traditions or the family culture". Transmission of any set of such families acquiring spiritual significance is largely an intuitive phenomenon and the flow of family traditions continue without any intentions and the same continue to move from one generation to the next generation.

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IMPACT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS ON THE TRADING DECISION OF INVESTORS IN EQUITY DERIVATIVE MARKET – A REGRESSION APPROACH

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of psychological factors on the trading decision of investors in the equity derivatives market among 350 samples from the twelve smart cities of Tamilnadu. To investigate the factors influencing trading decisions, exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis is employed. It is found that Market Factors, Herding, Prospect, Diversification and Overconfident are the factors influencing the trading decision. In addition, the study applied econometric approach to estimate whether the trading behavior of the investors is different from that of other groups concerning various psychological factors and found that female considers the market, herding and overconfident factors, whereas male considers prospect and diversification factors while trading in derivatives. Investors with high school education consider the herding factor and Graduate investors and students prefer market factors. Hedgers and speculators consider less about the market factors while trading in the derivative market but consider herding and diversification factors for their trading.

Keywords: Derivative, Psychological, Regression, CFA JEL Classification code: G130, G2, G41,

Introduction

Since 1990, the Indian financial system has turn more and more global in nature. It was exposed to the global financial market through channels of financial integration, development in information technology and telecommunication. This process of globalization has been accompanied by increasing volatility and uncertainty in prices of many commodities and in financial markets. As a result, some business risks like price risk, foreign exchange risk etc. has gained prominence. The risk factor is an important concern for financial agents and to reduce the risk, the concept of derivatives appears. The financial market venture has always been to maximize returns and minimize risk. Derivatives are among the forefront of the innovations in the financial markets and aim to increase returns and reduce risk (Himanshu Barot & Dr. Nilesh B. Gajjar, 2013) They provide an outlet for investors to protect

themselves from the vagaries of the financial securities markets. “Behavior of investor is a part of behavioral finance, which seeks to understand and predict systematic financial market implications of psychological decision processes. Behavior finance closely combines behavior and market phenomena and uses knowledge acquired from both the psychological field and financial theory.” The paper explores the psychological processes such as perception, attitudes, learning, and motivation that affect investor's trading decisions.

Problem Statement

As the equity markets are becoming more unpredictable, traders and investors are increasingly placing their bets in the derivatives segment, which has directed to a quick rise in the segment's turnover compared to the hard currency market. Currently, equity derivatives turnover is more than 14 times that of the cash market. In 2011, it was less than 10 times. This indicates that while investor activity has developed in the capital market, the majority of the growth has been in the derivatives marketplace. As an intact component of modern financial markets, derivatives can have an impingement on the trading behavior of the users of these marketplaces, therefore serving to channel the resources available therein into growth. Hence, the researcher tries to answer the following question

- What are the psychological factors affecting the investors trading decision in Equity derivatives instruments?

Review of Past Studies

Midhula Mohan K and A. V. Hemalatha (2016) examined the level of awareness of govt and aided employees on derivatives trading considering a sample of 100 investors in the Calicut district of Kerala. Even though the derivatives market was seen the highest, growth among all financial market segments, government and private employees make low investments in derivative trading in comparison to other investment avenues. Hence, the researcher suggests that the brokers should give more awareness to the govt employees and encourage them to invest in derivative instruments.

Tai Yuen Hon (2012) employed exploratory factor analysis to identify the factors that affect the behavior of investors in derivatives markets. The study considered a sample of 524 small investors in Hong Kong. It was found that five factors such as personal background, reference group, return performance, risk tolerance and cognitive style were identified. Among the five factors, the author concluded that returns performance, reference group and personal group are the main factors that influence the behavior of small investors in Hong Kong's derivatives market.

Nicolaus, D. (2010) analyzed the determinants that affect the derivative choices of retail investors and examined the performance of retail derivatives chosen by retail investors. The results establish that there is an increase in the

need for pinning down the characteristics of financial products and consequently an increase in retail investors' search costs contribute to the observed popularity of retail derivatives. Their analysis of the performance of the products chosen by retail investors further reveals that the trading behavior that is likely to underlie the observed derivative choices results in a performance loss compared to a more diversified portfolio. They concluded that retail derivative markets emphasize the importance of situational and investor-specific factors for retail investors' portfolio choices that might counteract the welfare improving potential of this instrument.

Data and Methodology

The aim of the paper is to determine the factors that the investors think are responsible for taking trading decision in Equity derivative market. Primary data is gathered from the 360 sample respondents from the 12 smart cities of Tamilnadu (provided by Govt. of Tamilnadu) through a well-structured interview schedule. The major cities are Chennai, Coimbatore, Madurai, Tiruchirapalli, Tirupur, Salem, Erode, Tirunelveli, Vellore, Thoothukudi, Dindugul, and Thanjavur. Exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and Econometric regression approach is employed in the study.

Result and Discussion

Reliability Test

Reliability is the ability of the questionnaire to consistently measure the topic under study at different times and across different populations. The reliability of a measure implies the extent of its stability and consistency (error-free) and hence ensures consistent measurement across time and the various items in the instrument. Cronbach's alpha is based on the number of items and the average inter-item correlation. A high correlation between the different items will indicate they are measuring the same construct and there will be only a small amount of error. A low correlation will indicate that there is a lot of error and the items are not reliably measuring the same construct. Table 1 displays the reliability scales for the factors influencing the trading behavior of Investors.

Table 1

Final reliability test for factors influencing trading behaviour of investors

	Mean	Variance	Std .deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
Psychological Factors	64.17	63.99	8.00	.819	17
Personal Decision Factors	37.46	49.057	7.004	.855	10
Motivational Factors	57.36	99.80	9.99	.904	15

Table 1 highlights the reliability test for assessing the accuracy of the operationally defined variables that were measured with a five-point Likert scale technique. It is inferred from the table that the Cronbach's alpha level to examine the internal consistency for the Psychological factors is 0.819 (81.9 percent) and this indicates that the reliability is good. The Cronbach's value for Personal factors is 0.855 and the motivational factor is 0.904, which reveals that reliability is excellent concerning motivational factors.

Psychological Factors Influencing Trading Behaviour of Investors

To explore the psychological processes such as perception, attitudes, learning, and motivation that affect investor's trading decisions. This part covers various factors affecting the trading behavior of investors.

KMO and Barlett's Test

The result of the KMO and Barlett's test is presented in table 2.

Table 2
kmo measure of sampling adequacy and bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.737
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2061.467
	df	136
	Sig.	.000

Source: Compiled and calculated from primary data

Table 2 presents the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of Sphericity to establish the reliability and scientific validity of the data and technique opted for further analysis. The table reveals that the KMO value is 0.737 that indicates that the factors selected are ideal for factor analysis and Bartlett's test of sphericity indicates that at 136 degrees of freedom (df) chi-square values for the factors derived are highly significant.

Rotated Component Matrix

The first five factors are the final factors solution and they all together represent 62.561 percent of the total variance in the scale items measuring the psychological factors affecting trading behavior.

It gives a clear picture of the number of factors. Rotation shows the different variables load on different factors. The researcher can look at the variables loading on each factor and choose suitable names for factors. The factors identified in the exploratory factor analysis are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3
Summary of exploratory factor analysis (n=360)

FACTORS	Rotated Component Matrix ^a	Component				
		1	2	3	4	5
Factor I Market Factors	I use the cash /spot price as a reference point in trading.	.771				
	I put the past trends of stocks under consideration for my investment.	.712				
	I set the value of futures/options contract based on the recent selling/buying price	.702				
	I use past performance as an indicator of future performance and rely on this to make investment decisions	.650				
	Market information is important for my stock investment	.618				
Factor II Herding	Other investors’ decisions about buying and selling stocks have an impact on my investment Decisions		.894			
	Other investors' decisions of the stock volume have an impact on my investment decisions		.856			
	I usually react quickly to the changes in other investors’ decisions and follow their reactions to the stock market.		.677			
Factor III Prospect	I consider carefully the price changes of stocks to invest in.			.773		
	I book profits on the stocks that have increased in value			.750		
	I tend to treat each element of the investment portfolio separately.			.636		
Factor IV Diversification	I become risk-averse when faced with sure gain				.670	
	I become a risk seeker when faced with sure loss				.646	
	I avoid selling contracts that have decreased in value and readily sell contracts that have increased in value.				.600	
Factor V Overconfident	I believe that my skills and knowledge of the stock market can help me to outperform the market.					.795
	I have high expectations on returns beyond market expectations					.768
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.						
a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.						

Source: Compiled and calculated from primary data

Table 3 shows the distribution of each variable in each component. The factor loading of the items indicates that all 17 items are categorized into five factors. These factors were named as Factor I “Market Factors”, Factor II “Herding”, Factor III “Prospect”, Factor IV “Diversification” and Factor V “Overconfident”. Five items were loaded in factor I, three items was loaded in II, III and IV factors and two items were loaded in factor V.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory Factor Analysis is the most common method of confirming the statistical procedure that is used to test how well the measured variables represent the constructs. The confirmatory model is also termed as the measurement model. There are many constructs in the survey questionnaires. Each construct has a set of observed variables. It is important to verify if the set of observed variables for a construct is relevant to that construct or not. The

researcher has verified the consistency of the observed variables in all the constructs.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the psychological factor and the trading behavior of investors.

Table 4
Model fit for psychological factors affecting trading behaviour

Parameters	CMIN/DF	GFI	AGFI	CFI	RMSEA
Study Value	3.110	.916	.875	.825	.077
Recommended Value	Acceptable fit [1-5]	Greater than 0.9	Greater than 0.9	Greater than 0.9	Less than 0.08

Table 4 depicts the model fitness indices for the psychological factors influencing trading behavior. The table indicates that normed chi-square (CMIN/DF) from the table is 3.10 (286/92), the value of Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is 0.916 which is more than 0.9 and indicates a very good fitness, Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) value is 0.875 and Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is 0.825 and these values are between 0.8 and 0.9, indicating adequate fit of the model. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value of 0.077 is indicative of a good fit of the model. It is concluded that the “Psychological factors influencing trading behavior” reveals that the CFA model is acceptable and fit. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. That means the constructs extracted using exploratory factor analysis are confirmed and there is a significant relationship between the observed values of psychological factors and the five constructs.

Table 5
Results of validity and reliability test value

Particulars	Construct Validity	AVE
MARKET FACTORS	0.82	0.58
HERDING	0.85	0.66
PROSPECT	0.76	0.52
DIVERSIFICATION	0.67	0.51
OVERCONFIDENT	0.76	0.61

Table 5 shows the result of construct reliability and convergent validity. Construct reliability evaluates the rigorousness with which the latent item is measured by the observable item (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). The authors have propagated that the AVE value should not be less than 0.5 to ensure the convergent validity of the model. The construct reliability should be above 0.6,

and table portrays that the construct reliability value in respect of all the items far exceeds the minimum requisite value. Hence, all the measurable items command the desirable construct reliability.

Impact of the Psychological Factors on the Trading Decision of the Investors

The psychological factors, namely Market Factor, Herding, Prospect, Diversification and Overconfident were identified using Exploratory Factor Analysis. An econometric approach is followed to determine the factors that the investors think are responsible for trading decisions.

Table 6
Regression analysis on the effect of psychological factors on the trading decision of investors

Variable	Market Factors	Herding	Prospect	Diversification	Overconfident
INTERCEPT	3.867	2.837	4.052	3.908	3.714
FEMALE	0.054	0.139	-0.138	-0.123	0.053
HIGH SCHOOL	-0.293	0.186	-0.308	-0.285	-0.144
DIPLOMA	-0.070	-0.064	0.094	-0.324	-0.478
GRADUATE	0.086	0.126	0.077	0.086	-0.012
STUDENT	0.849	-0.410	0.479	0.260	1.559
SELF_EMPLOYED	0.295	0.660	0.167	-0.422	-0.039
PRIVATE	0.202	0.299	-0.088	-0.263	-0.009
GOVT	0.184	0.255	-0.112	-0.315	-0.134
HEDGING	-0.015	0.071	-0.018	0.112	-0.121
SPECULATION	-0.006	0.070	-0.010	-0.104	0.074

Source: Compiled and calculated from Primary Data

Table 6 presents the effect of psychological factors, namely market factors, herding, prospect, diversification and the confidence level on the trading decision of the investors. The econometric approach estimates and helps to know whether the trading behavior of the investors is different from that of other groups concerning various psychological factors. The female coefficient of 0.054 suggests that holding other factors constant, when compared to male investors, the average number of female investors ($3.867+0.054=3.921$) consider market factors for their trading decision more by 3.92 units. The table also reveals that the coefficient of the female is positive in the case of Advocate factor (0.054), herding (.139) and overconfident (0.053) which indicate that the female considers these factors for trading decision more than the male considers, whereas the male considers prospect and diversification factors while trading in derivatives.

In the education of investors, Postgraduate is kept as the interactive dummy. The coefficient of High school is positive in the case of herding factor and signifies that compared to Postgraduate Investors, investors with high school education consider the herding factor while trading in derivatives.

The negative value of diploma reveals that diploma holders do not consider the market factors when compared with the Postgraduates, whereas the positive coefficient indicates that Graduate investors prefer market factors to the postgraduate investors.

The benchmark category concerning occupation is Retired employees. The coefficient of Student is 0.849 indicating that an average number of students considering the market factors is greater than the retired employees by 84.9 units. The coefficient value for self-employed is 0.295 which reveals that the average number of self-employed investors preferring market factors is more than the retired employees by 29.5 units. The positive coefficient values of private and govt employees disclose that when compared to the reference category, the number of investors included these two categories is more than the reference category.

For understanding, the impact of personal factors on trading behavior, investors trading for arbitrage purpose are kept as a benchmark category and it is revealed that hedgers and speculators consider less about the market factors while trading in the derivative market but consider herding and diversification factors for their trading.

Conclusion

The present study determined the psychological factors affecting the decision of investors while making trading in derivative instrument. Derivatives are introduced for the purpose of hedging or managing the risk of fluctuations in the prices of the stock. The study found that the psychological factors namely categorized as market factors, herding, prospect, diversification and the confidence level have effect on the trading decision of the investors and female considers the market, herding and overconfident factors, whereas male considers prospect and diversification factors while trading in derivatives. Investors with high school education consider the herding factor and Graduate investors and students prefer market factors. Hedgers and speculators consider less about the market factors while trading in the derivative market but consider herding and diversification factors for their trading.

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FAMILY IMPACTS OF ALCOHOL ADDICTION IN KERALA

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Abstract

Alcoholism negatively penetrates almost all spheres of human life. Addiction exerts considerable hardships to the drinker and all other members of the family as well. The present paper tries to delineate various issues of alcoholism within the family by comparing with non-alcoholic family. Thus, the paper is an eye-opener to family issues of **alcoholism**.

Key words: Alcoholism, Family, Addictions, Abuses, Breakups

1.1. Introduction

Alcohol consumption is regarded as a risk factor for many social, economic and health problems of society (Gururaj et al., 2006). Alcohol has been a known risk factor for increasing crime, absenteeism, loss of productivity, damage to property and physical and emotional abuse of women and children. Alcoholism often referred to as “family disease” as the drinking of the alcoholic affects the drinker and his/her family members as well. An addict tramples his entire family life and the related negative externality may have far-reaching consequences on each members of the family. There are large number of works on alcoholism that explains endless sufferings of children of addicts and spouses of alcoholics. Most often wife of the alcoholic has to undertake the duties of both the parents. As a result, addicted parent may be volatile and careless towards his family and children. Moreover, extravaganza for drinking purpose and expenditure for alcoholism treatment often clinch the family into iatrogenic poverty.

Alcohol abuse has notorious power for family destruction. Family of an addict is more prone to emotional inconsistency and insecurity. Such family always had a feeling of negative interactions. Majority of the partners of alcoholics and other family members became co-dependent or enabler of the addicts and sacrifice their life for the alcoholics by simply forget their own ends and aspirations. In short, alcoholism affects each member of the family – from the

unborn child to the alcoholic's spouse. Its far-reaching effects result in not only physical problems for the alcoholics but also may result in physical and psychological problems for other members of the family (Parsons.T, 2003). There is a considerable number of child abuse and domestic violence cases were reported to which alcohol was a risk factor (Laslet et al., 2010; Hung et al., 2009).

1.2. Objectives

1. To compare domestic verbal and physical abuses of alcohol addicts against non-addicts
2. To assess various family issues like sexual abuse, self-torture and family breakups of addicted family against non-addicted family
3. To analyze suicidal tendency and attempts of addicted family against non-addicted family

1.3. Methodology

The present paper employed only primary information from members of different Alcoholics Anonymous (hereafter A.A) groups all over Kerala for analyzing the issue. Hence 2600 members of A.A from 236 groups are considered as the population of the study. To find out the family impacts of addiction a multi-stage sampling technique has been employed in this paper. In the first stage, Kerala is selected for the study since per-capita alcohol consumption of the state is very high. In the second stage, the state is further divided into three geographical regions viz, south, central and north Kerala by geographic location and distinct living conditions. In the third stage, some A.A groups were identified from the respective regions through snowball sampling. In the final step, alcohol addicts, that is, the sampling units were identified through simple random sampling from each of these groups. This step has been done based on the number of distribution of each group in such a way that more addicts were selected from larger groups and vice versa. Total of 210 addicts was selected for the study with a criterion of a minimum of 70 addicted peoples from a particular region to ensure proper representation of each region.

To compare the impact of addiction, the same number of non-addicted samples was selected from the respective regions. This non-addicted control group is also selected based on many criteria. First of all, individuals were identified with the same socio-economic backgrounds of the addicted peoples. Then the identified persons were further screened to realize whether they are alcohol addicted persons or not. This stage has been done based on the CAGE questionnaire, which was used for the identification of problem drinkers (Ewing J. A., 1984). Two "yes" responses to CAGE questions were treated as the

respondent is a problem drinker. If a person got a score of 2 or more for the CAGE questions were treated as addicts and avoid from the control group. Then search for a new sample with the same background to substitute this one. In this way, 70 non-addicted persons were selected from each region and thus making a total of 210 non-addicts to form the control group of the study.

1.4. Analysis and Interpretation

1.4.1. Domestic Abuses

One of the most common problems associated with alcohol addiction is verbal and physical abuse by the addict on one or whole of the members of the family. Most often the family members concealed and deny these facts from others to keep up their family prestige. This section deals with the difference between addicts and non-addicts on the basis of emotional and physical abuses against spouse, parents and children. Chi-square test and logistic regression has been performed to analyze whether there was any significant association between addiction and verbal and physical abuses against spouse, parents and children in Kerala. Results of the tests have been given in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1

Abuses in the Family

Nature of Abuse		Chi-Square	df	Significance	Logist. Reg	Significance	Odds Ratio
Spouse	Verbal	277.71	4	p<.001	0.921	P<.001	2.512
	Physical	176.76	4	p<.001	1.116	P<.001	3.051
Parent	Verbal	103.93	4	p<.001	0.790	p<.001	2.203
	Physical	29.15	4	p<.001	2.226	P<.001	9.258
Children	Verbal	175.99	4	p<.001	-0.988	P<.001	0.372
	Physical	103.29	4	p<.001	-0.941	P<.001	0.390

Source: Primary Survey

Abuses against spouses and parents both in terms of verbal and physical attack were positively influenced and highly significant among addicts than that of non-addicts. At the same time, abuses against children were high among non-addicts than that of addicts. The reason was non-addicts are keener and highly careful about their children. The nature of abuse was severe among addicts and reasons were unnecessary while there were only mild punishment from the part of non-addicts and reasons were genuine.

1.4.2. Sexual Abuse, Self-torture and Family breakups

Sexual harassment against a spouse, Self-infliction and family collapse are some other serious family issues connected to addiction. Chi-square test and logistic regression has been performed to analyze whether there was any significant

association between addiction and sexual abuse, self-torture and family breakups in Kerala. Results of the tests have been given in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2

Sexual Abuse, Self-torture and Family breakups

Problems	Chi-Square	df	Significance	Logist. Reg.	Significance	Odds Ratio
Sexual Abuse	120.51	4	p<.001	3.656	p<.001	38.722
Self-torture	72.55	4	p<.001	3.842	p<.001	46.621
Family breakups	150.30	4	p<.001	3.309	p<.001	27.361

Source: Primary Survey

Sexual abuse, self-torture and family breakups were high among alcohol addicts than that of non-addicts. These variables were closely associated to addiction of an individual.

1.4.3. Suicidal Tendency and Suicidal Attempt

Suicidal tendency and attempts of both the addict and his spouse are a basic family problem to be analyzed in connection to alcohol addiction. Most of the addicted persons and their spouses were in utter despair. As a result, most often they show suicidal tendency or even attempt to suicide. Hence it is important to compare the suicidal tendency and attempt of the addicted category against non-addicted category. Chi-square test and logistic regression has been performed to examine whether there was any significant association between addiction and suicidal tendency of addicts in Kerala. The results indicate that there was a statistically significant association between the suicidal tendency of addicts and addiction in Kerala, $\chi^2(4) = 207.84$, $p < .001$. Logistic regression also confirmed the result, $B = 3.167$, $p < .001$, $OR(Odds\ Ratio) = 25.326$. Similar tests have been conducted to examine whether there was any significant association between addiction and suicidal tendency of spouses of addicts in Kerala. The results indicate that there was a statistically significant association between the suicidal tendency of spouses of addicts and addiction in Kerala, $\chi^2(4) = 160.89$, $p < .001$. Logistic regression also confirmed the result, $B = 3.232$, $p < .001$, $OR = 23.738$.

Mann-Whitney U-test and logistic regression are used to compare the Suicidal attempts of the addicts and spouses of addicts against non-addicts and their spouses. Test results indicate that there was a statistically significant difference in the suicidal attempts of addicts against non-addicts in Kerala, $U = 27905.50$, $P < .001$. Logistic regression also confirmed the result, $B = 2.497$, $p < .001$, $OR = 12.149$. Arithmetic mean of number of suicidal attempts among addicts was 0.52, while this was only 0.03 among non-addicts. Hence, it is inferred that the attempts for suicide among addicts was comparatively very high. Similarly,

test results also indicate that there was a statistically significant difference in the suicidal attempt of spouses of addicts against spouses of non-addicts in Kerala, $U = 29860.50$, $p < .001$. Logistic regression also confirmed the result, $B = 2.681$, $p < .001$, $OR = 14.596$. Arithmetic mean of number of suicidal attempts among spouses of addicts was 0.46, while this was only 0.04 among spouses of non-addicts. Hence, it is inferred that the attempts for suicide among spouses of addicts was comparatively quite high.

1.5. Policy Suggestions

- Long-term strategies should be framed to rehabilitate dependents of alcohol addicts. Special protection law should be maintained to protect female members and children from the torture of addicts.
- Construct comprehensive database regarding alcohol consumption, alcohol addiction, addiction related issues, etc.
- Provide early health checkups to identify physiological tendency of addiction among individuals. Proper maintenance of health checkups and counseling centers will help to detain people from alcohol.

1.6. Conclusion

The paper tries to analyze family problems associated to alcohol addiction. The problems are analyzed by comparing various issues in between addicts and non-addicts. Various issues happened within the family due to alcoholism include physical and verbal abuses among different members of the family, sexual abuse against spouse, self-infliction, family breakups and suicides in the family. Domestic abuses reveal that physical and verbal abuses against spouse and parents were comparatively very high in addicted families than that of non-addicted families. At the same time, the analysis shows that both the abuses against children were high among non-addicts than that of addicts. Abuses against children in non-addicted family are due to care giving and were mild in nature. But, the abuses in addicted family against children were for quite unnecessary reasons and were wild in nature. Similarly, issues like sexual abuse against spouse and self-infliction were quite high among addicts than non-addicts. Frequency as well as the number of family breakups also very high among addicts than non-addicts. Likewise, suicidal tendency and attempts for suicide also quite high among addicts and spouses of addicts than that of their counterparts. Thus, we can conclude that alcohol addiction generates considerable family disturbances and alcoholism disrupts ordinary family life.

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GENDER INCLUSIVE CULTURE AT MODERN WORKPLACES: PERCEPTIONS OF FEMALE EMPLOYEES OF KOLKATA

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Abstract: The paper is based on an empirical survey carried out by the authors to assess the state of gender equality prevailing in formal employment sectors of Kolkata. The study was based on responses obtained from female employees with the help of a questionnaire. The tabulated and analyzed results show that subtle forms of discrimination exist at the organizations and the very culture is not gender inclusive. The sample admits that they have the urge and capacity to climb up the corporate ladder but many feel that they are discriminated due to their gender. They also admit that the workplace schedule leaves little time for them to fulfill their domestic responsibilities. More than half of the sample admits that they have been discriminated during pay fixation and are looking for career advancements. The sample is also of the opinion that they are judged on many factors apart from their performances. Harassment in subtle forms is present and few have admitted it personally when confidentiality of information was assured. Discontentment is also observed from the fact that only a negligible few wish to continue in their present employment till retirement. The study, though subjective, tries to project the ground realities on the issue of exploitation and subordination of females at the workplace based on empirical evidences.

Keywords: Discrimination, Gender Inclusion, Inequality, Promotion, Subjugation, Workplace Culture.

1. Introduction

The Principle of Gender Equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution. Gender Equality is the state where there is availability of opportunities and resources for all irrespective of gender. It also includes participation, decision making ability, valuing behaviors, aspirations and needs equally. Men and women should have same rights, obligations, and opportunities in all aspects of life. Knowledge and experience of every men and women should be used to create improvements.

A practical review shows that there has been gender inequality since ages, as males and females are not treated at par. However, since the last century with advent of automation, greater emphasis is being laid down to treat all human beings equally. Companies around the world are transforming their approach. Today, men and women enter the organizations in equal proportions but still major gender discrimination is found. Discrimination is observed in pay fixation, compensation, granting promotions, majority of top positions being allotted to men etc. Women cannot get into the upper levels of any institution due to the so called Glass Ceiling, which is actually an invisible barrier, preventing someone to achieve success. The organizations may have a predefined notion about women. They are not made to realize their real potential. Gender discrimination decreases satisfaction, commitment and enthusiasm which directly or indirectly limit women from participating completely.

2. Literature Review

Ruohan Wu and Xueyu Cheng (2016) studied how gender equality in the workplace effects and promotes productivity of the manufacturers. The data for years 2001 to 2007 was collected from National Annual Industrial Survey conducted by the National Statistics Institute of Chile. Using semi-parametric method to estimate productivity, four types of employees (executive, specialized production workers, administrative staff and auxiliary production workers) were considered. It was concluded that gender equality does encourage productivity growth. In firms with more than 50 employees, only higher gender equality among low-skill employees improves productivity whereas in firms with less than 50 employees higher gender equality among high-skill employees can increase productivity.

Sumanjeet Singh (2016) discusses the extent, causes and consequences of Gender Inequality in India. In spite of measures taken by Government, there still exists gender gap. This is very well reflected in India's low ranking on the World Economic Forum's Gender Gap Index (GGI), 2014, with scores that were below average. UNDP's Human Development Index (HDI) 2015 showed that among the South Asian countries, only Afghanistan fares worse than India, if gender inequality is considered. The root cause of gender inequality is basically the Patriarchal system prevailing in India, where men hold authority over females. Lack of education is another serious problem. Without education, women lack confidence and knowledge required to make own choices in life. Solution to these is in providing women with equal opportunities and access to services, resources and infrastructure. Government authorities, private sector and the donor community should come closer to eliminate gender gap in India.

Neeraj Kaushik, Anita Sharma and Veerander Kumar Kaushik (2014) studied the gender issues like gender stereotype, gender discrimination and sexual harassment in Indian context, taking seven job-related factors (infrastructure, HR functions, organizational climate, legal pursuit, empowerment, training and development, ethical concerns) and two individual factors (interpersonal and mindset). Primary data was collected through questionnaire in 500 firms in India. The objective of the study was analyzed by calculating frequencies, factor analysis and one-way analysis of variance. The analysis showed that age and level of management has no significant effect on these factors but the male and female respondents differ significantly on these issues.

Sofia Elwer, Lisa Harryson, Malin Bolin and Anne Hammarstrom (2013) aimed to identify the different patterns of gender equality at workplace and also how these patterns are associated with the psychological distress. Primary data (n=715) was collected through questionnaire from the Northern Swedish Cohort. The method of cluster analysis was used to identify the gender equality patterns whereas Chi-square test was used to locate its association with psychological distress. In traditionally gender unequal workplaces, highest odds of psychological distress were found for women. In most gender equal workplaces, the lowest overall occurrence of psychological distress as well as same occurrence for men and women was found.

Gabriele Plickert and Joyce Sterling (2017) demonstrate the gender-based issues that women have to face in the legal workplace. Data was collected from a national representative U.S. panel study of lawyers. Logistic Regression model was used. It showed that gender, parental role have a significant effect on the work schedules. There are still major differences between mothers and fathers. Women lawyers report significantly lower probabilities of full-time employment than men. There is significantly less chance of experiencing workplace discrimination by men with children. Even if they do, it will have no change in their work schedule.

In 2006, a Swedish study revealed the problems faced in public and private sector by women. Women with small children face lot of problems in their career. Regardless of skills and abilities, even young and elderly women face problems. Women have had difficulties in getting right benefits and appropriate promotions.

Alexander Raj and K. Jasmin (2018) highlight the multi-dimensional areas of gender inequality in India. Primary data was collected from a sample of 100 randomly selected respondents through a questionnaire. Secondary information were collected from newspapers, journals etc. The research reveals 34.6% people feel that equal opportunities are not give to all genders. On matters of education, employments etc., a significant percentage of women are not allowed to put forward their opinion. A high level of exploitation is observed at

household level. Maximum of the respondents are unemployed, showing that they are affected by gender equality.

3. Objective of the Study

Based on the Literature review, it is found that few empirical studies has been carried out in and around the city of Kolkata, targeting specifically women, to analyze their position at workplace and the amount of discrimination they face due to their gender.

The primary objectives of the study are as follows-

- a) To survey the perception of females employees regarding their workplace culture, whether gender inclusive or not,
- b) To access, if females are discriminated in issuance of salary, getting top positions and promotions or other benefits at their workplace.

4. Data and Methodology

For the purpose of the study, 100 females were randomly selected who were working in various institutions in and around Kolkata (urban centre). The survey was conducted in March, 2020. The survey instrument was a close ended questionnaire, containing questions relevant to the issue of study. Personal interview was conducted with the respondents by researchers and the objective of the research was explained to them. Each respondent was given the questionnaire and asked to fill it to the best of their ability. They were assisted by the researchers whenever required. Confidentiality of the data was assured to the respondents. Finally, data for 100 samples were obtained. The collected data was tabulated in Excel sheet, processed and meaningful inferences were drawn.

5. Findings from the Survey

Demographic Profile and Details of the Sample (N=100)		
Age	Under 25 years	21
	25-29 years	33
	30-39 years	29
	40-49 years	15
	50 years and above	02
Marital Status	Married	43
	Unmarried	51
	Separated	05
	Widow	01
Education qualification	Not Graduate	03
	Graduate	30
	Post Graduate	43
	Professional degree	24
Approximate Income (monthly in Rs)	Below 15,000	19
	15,001-30,000	36
	30001-60000	27
	Above 60000	18

Type of Institution employed into	Academic Institutions	29
	Corporate Office	53
	Govt. Employee	05
	Others	13
Position/ Designation	Non-management	30
	Junior Level	16
	management	49
	Middle Level	05
Average weekly working hours	management	05
	Top Level management	
	Less than 30	09
	30-39	26
Tenure in the present organisation	40-49	52
	Above 50	13
	Less Than 1 Year	34
	1-5 Years	50
Intention to remain in current employment	6-10 Years	09
	Above 10 Years	07
	Less than 2 year	21
	2-5 years	23
	6-10 years	05
	Until retirement	15
	Uncertain	36

6. Major Observations:

Sl. No.		Yes	No
1.	My career choice was influenced by stereotypical female-oriented profession	20%	80%
2.	I observe a gender inclusive culture	40%	60%
3.	I have faced harassment or bullying in any occasion	14%	86%
4.	I feel that women get lower positions at workplaces	24%	76%
5.	I feel that women getsame opportunities as men	31%	69%
6.	I have sometimes been discouraged from participating in institutional activities because of gender	23%	77%
7.	I feel that women are judged in terms of dress that they wear to work	61%	39%
8.	I feel that my workplace gives me enough space to fulfill my domestic commitments	54%	46%

6.1 Observations on issue of Salary:

Abbreviations Used - [Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)]

- I believe that there are salary gaps among the same level in the organisation-

- I have been, at some point unfairly denied a salary increase in the organisation-

- I am not fully satisfied with current salary-

6.2 Observations on issue of Promotion:

Abbreviations Used - [Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)]

- I am looking forward for promotion/ career advancement in near future-

- My manager/supervisor does not encourage me to work up to my full potential-

- I have more potential and ability to work at a better position than to what currently working at.

6.3 Observations on issue of Gender Discrimination:

Abbreviations Used - [Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)]

- I have experienced some sort of gender discrimination in the workplace.

- My supervisor does consider gender while delegating job assignment.

- My colleagues treat me differently because of my gender.

7. Interpretation of Results

- Nearly 25% of the respondents feel that women get lower positions at work.
- 40% of the respondents feel that their workplace does not have gender inclusive culture.
- Among the total respondents, 69% feel that they do not get same opportunities as men.

- 14% of the respondents reported that harassment or bullying, due to gender is observed at workplaces, directly or indirectly.
- Only 15% of the respondents have an intention to stay in the current employment till their retirement, whereas 36% are uncertain.
- According to 23% of the respondents, they are sometimes discouraged from participating in different types of activities.
- A majority of 61% responded that women are judged in terms of dress that they wear to work.
- 46% of the respondents feel that their institution does not give them enough space to fulfil their domestic commitments.
- More than half of the respondents feel that there are salary gaps among the same level of employees in their institution.
- 30% respondents reveal that they have been unfairly denied a salary increase at their workplace.
- Only 4% of the total sample, strongly disagree being unsatisfied with their current salary.
- Approximately 90% of the respondents are looking forward for promotion and career advancement.
- 36% of the respondents do not receive any encouragement from their supervisor.
- Among the total respondents, 74% believe that they have a higher potential to work at a better place, than what they are currently working at.
- 17% of the respondents have experienced gender discrimination some point of time.
- More than half, i.e. 58% of the respondents agree that their supervisor considers 'gender' as a basis in delegating job assignments.
- 9% felt of receiving a different treatment by their colleagues.

8. Concluding Remarks

Discontentment at the workplace is clearly observed among the females. The women believe that their workplace culture is not gender inclusive and somewhere males get more opportunities than females. The workplace culture and superiors have a discriminating attitude and this often leads to assignment distribution on considering factors apart from talent of the employees. Salary disparity is perceived by many in the sample and it is also believed by them that they have the potential to work at better assignments which is denied due to gender.

In a nutshell, it can be said that gender inequality is vividly observed among the sample studied and the so called glass ceiling is still present in the modern

organizations which stops a female employee to express her full potential at her workplace.

Culture of gender inclusion should be present- be it at workplace or at home. Every girl child in India faces gender discrimination in society. Son often get quality studies than daughters. Daughters are expected to take part in household chores than sons. Superiority complex is developed among sons (males) during childhood. This discrimination at the initial stages, leads to lack of autonomy and authority thereby affecting a women's mental health and progress. For bringing parity among the genders, higher quality of education should be provided to females. Creation of inclusive gender-diverse workplaces, boosting women participation along with pay advancements should be worked on.

9. Limitations of the Study

- a) The study area was restricted in and around the city of Kolkata (urban centre) only. A large survey area might give a different picture,
- b) The sample selected was only 100 females which is small and negligible when compared to the total population,
- c) The survey was carried out in March, 2020, when the economy was facing financial crisis. A different period of survey might have showed different results,
- d) Many other issues targeting "Gender Inclusive Culture" were not reflected in the questionnaire used in the survey.

In spite of the above limitations, the study has made an honest attempt to portray "Gender Inclusive Culture at Modern Workplace: A Viewpoint of Female Employees of Kolkata."

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DIGITAL LENDING AN EMERGING AREA IN THE FIELD OF LENDING

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Abstract

Digital Lending is an advanced process of lending and borrowing in comparison to traditional lending. The lending and borrowing can be done within a short duration of time and it does not require any paperwork. Online technology and automation is used to provide and renew loans, right from the receipt of loan application to the disbursement of loans, so that individuals and businesses can get capital fast. The process of obtaining loan is transparent, simple and efficient. Digital lending could benefit the large unaddressed market segment by providing low-cost loans. A new class of a company known 'FinTech' companies are the one who are combining the financial services with the current technology to promote lending easier and has given a new path to the lending industry in India. FinTech companies are solving the lending requirements of different individuals and sectors by collaborating with the leading banks and financial institutions. They use modern digital tools and technologies like India Stack and open APIs of the borrowers. To apply for a loan one must have internet connection and a computer or smartphone, and some relevant government approved identification documents such as, PAN card, Aadhaar, voter ID, etc. Revolution happened in the lending function through Digital lending. It has emerged as an alternative to the traditional bank credit.

Key words: Digital Technology, Fintech Companies, Financial Inclusion, India Stack, Msmes

Introduction

In the field of lending and borrowing, Digital lending is a new and emerging concept. The lending and borrowing can be done within a short duration of time and it does not require any paperwork. **It involves managing and processing loans online through the web or mobile phones.** The process of applying for loan, management of document, electronic signatures, credit analysis, decision making, fund disbursement, all are handled using digital technology. The use of digital technology makes the process of digital lending simple, efficient, fast and transparent. Borrowers must have internet connection and a computer or

smartphone for applying a loan. They need to go to the portal, fill their details and upload some documents such as, PAN card, Aadhaar, voter ID, etc. Digital lending can fulfil the different borrowing needs by offering consumer loans, Small Medium Enterprises loans, working capital loans etc. Speaking at the 12th Mint Annual Banking Conclave, RBI Deputy Governor Mr. N.S. Vishwanathan said "The basic function of a digital lender is to bring lenders and borrowers into contact; in the process, it provides basic services like loan origination, information exchange and transaction matching, facilitating servicing of the loan, record maintenance, management of cash flows and aiding recoveries."

Objectives

- To study the importance of Digital Lending
- To study the process of Digital Lending
- To study its benefits and limitations
- To study the prospect of Digital Lending in India

Research Methodology

The study is descriptive in nature and based on secondary data. The secondary data have been collected from different secondary sources of information such as reports published by RBI, World Bank, News Paper reports, Reports from Boston Consulting Group etc. Information has also been collected from journals and periodicals, websites etc.

Need for Digital Lending

In India, the process of applying for a loan in banks or in non-banking financial institutions has been too lengthy and time consuming. It also creates lots of stress and tension for the borrowers. Because of all these, now it is important and also the need of the time to introduce a new kind of lending which can provide borrower to avail any kind of loan easily and fast. Digital Lending is the solution to all the above problems and can be a new age in the domain of lending. The traditional bankers and other formal financial institutions offer loan through offline. They process loan application manually which is time consuming and tiring process for the borrowers. The borrowers have to visit bank again and again, first to apply for the loan and then to trace the process which caused so much of stress and tension to the borrowers.

With the advancement in technology all kind of people across India use internet today. In such a scenario, with the Digital Lending platform the process of borrowing has become so simple that the customers need not to go to the bank even for a single time. Digital technology is used to handle every part of the loan process. According to a research work on consumer behaviour made by

Boston Consulting Group, 50% of borrowers with internet access avail their loans online.

Access to credit from formal channels of funding was becoming a major issue for different kinds of borrowers. Digital lending could be a solution to this problem and can benefit a host of people and sectors like self-employed, MSMEs and small borrowers. Digital lending could benefit the large unaddressed market segment by providing low-cost loans, which are simple to obtain and hence, digital lending can boost the process of financial inclusion.

Digital lending is rapidly growing sector in financial service industry all over the world and in India too. Digital lending offers the perfect platform for individuals and institutions to lend money to borrowers who are in need of a loan without much difficulties. Borrowers can get their funds fast without any hassle and lenders earn interest on the money lent.

Process of Lending

A new class of companies known as 'FinTech' companies have shown a new path to the lending industry by promoting paperless lending almost within 24 hours. To apply for a loan, borrowers need to go to online to the FinTech company portal and has to fill the details required. Then the required documents, such as, ID proof, address proof, salary proof etc to be uploaded by scanning them. By integrating tech innovations like cloud technologies, imaging and analytics etc. the lending process can be completed quickly. Using a mix of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning and automation, large quantities of data, the entire credit history & income history of an existing borrower can be analysed and interpreted online in a few seconds to complete the underwriting process of loans. Then the decision relating to the fresh loan or further credit extension can be relayed to the borrower immediately. The launch of India Stack by the Indian government, a set of open application programming interface (APIs) like e-KYC, e-sign etc. helped considerably to this alternative lending segment. e-KYC allows financial companies to perform the verification of Know Your Customer process digitally using biometrics or mobile OTP and e-Sign enables applicants to digitally sign and submit documents. Adopting these technologies, FinTech lenders seamlessly designing, launching, implementing and executing tailored and hyper-personalised products and services. Multiple types of collaboration are important for the process, collaboration with banks, collaboration with e-commerce companies and even collaboration with the other lending companies. The following exhibit shows how the end to end digital lending process is being followed.

Consumer Lending End to End Digital Example

Sources : FIBAC Productivity Survey 2017, RBI Data, BCG Analysis

Benefits

- Any kind of loan applications can now be submitted with a few swipes on a mobile phone
- Loans can be applied by the borrowers from anywhere and at any time. It is not required that the bank that lends to them is present in their locality or not.
- With paperless digital loans, borrowers do not need to visit the bank.
- The way of documentation has completely changed with the introduction of Digital Lending system.
- A digital loan reduces the steps and automates many processes such as the verification of borrowers' details as well as assessing their creditworthiness, not only much simpler and faster but also considerably more accurate than ever before into a very quick, painless process.
- FinTech companies have a transparent loan process. The applicants of loan can also keep a track of their loan application at every stage.

- It provides low-cost loans, which are simple to obtain for the large segment including consumer loans, Small Medium Enterprises loans, working capital loans etc.
- The SME industries and the start-ups can also flourish with the growth of Digital lending in India.
- The first-timers and even those on the lower end of the credit spectrum get funding through Digital lending easily.
- India's unbanked population can now opt to access the benefits of the formal financial system.
- For any financial emergencies like wedding requirements, medical, vacations, accidents and others, digital loans are the best options.
- The rate of interest charged to the customers is also reasonable in comparison to the traditional lending banks.
- As the processing of lending, from the applications to the disbursement of funds, is done with the help of technology, it helps in eliminating the chances of human error.
- FinTech lenders are focused on developing innovative products which can solve the different needs of the borrowers. They also focused on catering to low income, semi-urban and rural customers in unorganised sectors.

Limitations

Although digital lending makes remarkable impact in the space of lending in India, the world of digital lending is still a new frontier with unfamiliar and untamed landscapes. Hence, there are few obstacles also that arise in this exciting but unexplored territory.

- The most important concern at present time for digital lending is data protection. India has yet to introduce data protection laws and that has raised concerns over privacy of data and how data is being used by the tech companies.
- Digital lenders generally offer smaller loans than traditional lenders.
- Digital Lending does not require only the digitizing paper documents but requires efficiency in complete digitization of back-office process.
- Though it helps in eliminating the chances of human error, there will always be a possibility of machine error.
- The availability of human interaction can be an invaluable asset for finding solutions to different problems of the borrowers. But in digital Lending process no human interaction is possible.

- Since the process of approval of loan is easy, the borrowers may borrow beyond their capacity and ultimately may face difficulties in paying back due to over indebtedness.
- Many digital lenders may face problems as the availability of financing vehicles is limited.
- There is also limited scope for the availability of official data in FinTech credit. Hence, for assessment of market size, one has to rely on non-official sector surveys and financial disclosures.

Prospect in India

Digital lending is rapidly growing sector in financial service industry all over the world as well as in India. This is a digital era and digital lending presents a large opportunity in the Indian context too. Approximately 450 million people in India use smartphone which makes India the second-largest smartphone market in the world after China, and this number is bound to grow in the future. Due to the growth of e-commerce, government initiatives for having cashless economy through digitization, a good proportion of Indian population is now using online transactions. According to the report of Boston Consulting Group 2018, the percentage of urban people in India engaged in online purchases increased from 7% to 30% from the year 2014 to 2018. The growth of digital infrastructure in India and readiness of the Indian consumers will drive the growth of digital lending exponentially. The value of total retail digital loans is expected to reach a total of more than \$1 trillion by the year 2023 and the value will grow by more than 3 times by the year 2023 from the year 2019 according to the report of Boston Consulting Group.

Digital lending can be a financial tool to solve the problems of credit requirement by millions of Indian MSMEs. Since the credit requirement for MSMEs is small, they are the first-time borrowers, have no collateral or CIBIL score, they are unable to borrow from traditional lender such as banks and NBFCs. But with the growth of Digital lending, MSME industries can also flourish as FinTech companies provide loans easily to the MSMEs according to their eligibility and without any hassle. The increased application of digitization is helping credit flow to MSMEs. According to a joint study made by Omidyar Network and Boston Consulting Group (BCG), there is a chance of growth of digital lending to MSMEs in India up to 7 lakh crore by 2023.

Digitalisation policies of the Government since 2016, such as the launching of Unified Payments Interface (UPI) and the Goods and Services Tax (GST), forced significant numbers of MSMEs to formalize and digitize their businesses. It is now possible for end-to-end digital MSME lending with loan approval times as short as one day with the help of API based data availability. All these helped the growth of MSMEs in India and now they are contributing a big part of India's GDP. Small Medium Enterprise loans and personal loans are the leading digital loans of the customers followed by home loans.

From Start-ups to global technology giants, all are equally enthusiastic in this field and trying to grab their share of digital lending segment in India. Amazon launched an online sellers' lending network to link its sellers to third-party lenders. In 2018, Google made a partnership with four major Indian banks, namely, HDFC, Federal Bank, ICICI, and Kotak Mahindra Bank. Chinese smartphone company Xiaomi is the latest to enter in the segment. To connect smartphone users with lending companies for quick access to loan, Xiaomi started Mi Credit.

India is the second-largest unbanked population after China. According to the World Bank data, more than 190 million people in the country do not have access to a bank account. In such a scenario, Digital lending can boost financial inclusion in India by especially helping borrowers who do not get the benefit from formal finance.

Conclusion

Lending is an attractive business opportunity in India because of the low penetration of credit in the country. Borrowers can get their funds and lenders earn interest on the money lent and hence it is a win-win situation. It is clear that our future will doubtlessly be defined by technology – for better or for worse. Technology has changed the way people transact with money. We are going to witness significant changes in the Fin Tech sector and Digital Lending will play an increasingly important role in the delivery of lending services in the

future. The launch of India Stack by the Indian government as well as Jan DhanYojana have made end-to-end digital loaning in the country a reality. Digital lending could benefit millions of people and sectors, such as, the self-employed, micro, small and medium enterprises and small borrowers who previously had no credit access and thus, can boost financial inclusion in India. The Indian lending sector will need continuous support from the government as well as the regulators for further development and also to compete with the fast-changing global technological landscape. More transparency and collaboration with financial institutions and tech companies will be needed for future sustainability. Revolution happened in the lending function through Digital lending. It has emerged as an alternative to the traditional bank credit. It can also be viewed as the additional credit over and above the bank credit. Looking ahead, a Data Utility that brings the various data pools together and facilitates digital lending can be a game changer for the financial services industry provided the limitations of digital lending are properly taken care off.

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CONCEPTUAL REVIEW ON SNANAKARMA IN AYURVEDA

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Abstract:-

Ayurveda is a science of life. It is providing guidelines on ideal daily and seasonal routines, diet and behaviour. The goal of Ayurveda is to maintain the health and cure of the diseases. To achieve this goal Dinacharya plays very important role to maintain normal equilibrium of Dosha, Dhatu, Mala and Agni. Dinacharya includes procedures like wake up early in the morning (Bhramahurata) , brushing teeth (Datuna-karma), Nasya, Tambul, Abhyanga , Snana, etc. Regular habit according to Dinacharya in our daily routine is of prime importance to keep away from diseases, and maintain our body healthy. Snana is one among such Dinacharya and its play very important role to maintaining health.

Key words: Ayurveda, Dinacharya, Snana ,Health.

Introduction:-

Ayurveda reminds us that health is the balanced and dynamic integration between our environment, body, mind, and spirit. To Achieve this target Dinacharya play very important role, It is known as Daily routine, the ideal life style for a day explains various duties which systematically and scientifically highlights and explains various duties from one day to the next. It also regularizes a person's biological clock, aids digestion, absorption and assimilation and generates self esteem, discipline, peace, happiness and longevity.¹ It starts from early waking up in the morning (Bhramhamuhurtha), Ushapana, Mala-Mutra Visarjana, Achamana, Dantadavana, Anjana, Nasaya, Kavala, Gandusha...etc. Snana is one of the regimens of Dinacharya mentioned by Acharyas (Charaka, Susruta, Vagbhata etc.) of Ayurveda and other ancient literatures of India. The procedures, time, duration, types and benefits of Snana explained in our Texts, according to our classics one can surely say that Snana is important and unique concept explained among the regimens of Dinacharya. Acharya Charaka says that Snana is the best way to remove fatigue & Sweat (Shramaswedamalapaham)² and in Agraha-dravaya Snana is best "Sramahar"³. Snana should be done every day as said in Manu-Simrati (Snanam Samachareth Nithyam...)⁴ Cleanliness is one among the Dinacharya which has two kinds, external and internal. External

Purification is to keep the body clean by Snana hence the body free from all type of pathogens and dust particle etc. while internal purification is to keep the mind free from any types of stress and joyfull living,The cleanliness is necessary for health, growth and development of the body, Snana is the best form of cleaning.

Definition of Snana: Snana is the process which can be done daily and which removes Mala, Sweda from the body, and makes the person healthy. Snana is purifying, libidinal stimulant and gives longevity. Snana tarpanaparyantham kuryadekena vasasa⁵. Taking bath is auspicious, enhances virility, longevity, strength, compactness and Ojas⁶.

Matra of Snana :

Some classical reference gives us the reference that Snana should be performed like an elephant which means water used to take bath should be more in order to clean the whole body and keep the mind relax . According to modern science, approx 140-150 litres per person for daily life purpose and it include even bathing⁷.

Time of Snana :

Acharya's have said that one should take bath early in the morning⁸, among Dinacharya's, Snana is explained after Vyayama Karma, So it should be done after Vyayama-karma.

Types of Snana:

There are seven types of Snana's explained in Yagnavalkya-Smriti⁹ there are as follow's -

Mantra, Bhouma, Agneya, Vayavya, Divya, Varuna and Manasa in order.

Mantra Snana : Bathing by uttering Auponishadi Mantra is known as Mantra Snana.

Bhouma Snana : Bathing by smearing the whole body with mud is known as Bhouma Snana.

Agneya Snana : Application of Basma (Ash) i.e. burnt powder of cow dung is Basma, And other Basma can also be used. This Snana is known as Agneya Snana.

Vayavya Snana : Bathing with dust that arises while cow is walking is known as Vayavya Snana. This bath is done in the evening when the sun set's and the animals, like cows return to there home from forest. That dust itself is considered as most auspicious and this Snana is called VayavyaSnana.

Divya Snana : Bathing in sun rays or the glare of the sun combined with rain is known as Divya Snana.

Varuna Snana : Bathing in river water or in any other kind of water is known as Varuna Snana, It is considered as best snana among the types of Snana according to Mahabharata .

Manasa Snana : To think about oneself to cure it's soul is known as Manasa Snana.

Place's where Snana can be done :-

One should do Snana daily in river, scared places, ponds, Sarahasu, Garta, Prastravana as said in manusmruti¹⁰.

Benefits of Snana :

Acharyas have clearly mentioned about the qualities of Snana. It's purifies the body, libidinal stimulant, longevity and it removes fatigue, sweating and dirt from the body. It also brings strength in the body and it is best for increasing the Ojas (Snana Ojaskaramparma)¹¹. It also improves the appetite, removes itching, drowsiness, thirst, burning sensation, Destruction of sin¹². Snana is Hridayam (good for heart), Sarvendriya visodhanam (purifying all organs), Tandrapaposhamanam (lethargy and destruction of sin) Tushtidam (gives satisfaction), Pumsavatvardanam (enhances virility), Rakta Prasadnam (clears the blood) Deepanam (improves appetite)¹³. Yogaratnakara advised that Snana should be done in early morning as it is best owed with qualities like; Papa Nasaka (Destruction all sins), Dukha Swapna Vidhwamsana (destroys the Dosas of bad dreams), Pavithram (auspicious), Deha Mala Nasakam (removes all morbid matters of the body), Tejo Vardhanam (improves lustre), Rupadhyokaram (helps in beautification of body), Shareera Sukha Dayakama (brings pleasing or happiness to the body), Kayagnideepanam (increases the digestive fire), Streenam Manmatha Gahanam, Sramaharam (increases the work of women)¹⁴. Rubbing the entire body with cloth soon after bathing improves lustre, removes itching and disorders of skin^{15,16}.

Effects of Ushna and Sheeta Jala Snana:-

Ushna jala (Hot water) indication :- It increases strength and even relives Vata and Kapha Doshas¹⁷ and Adha Kaya (body below the clavicle level) increases strength where as to head decreases the strength of hairs and eyes. Hot water bath to head causes harmful effect to eyes in all the Kalas (always)¹⁸. When it put on the body does vasodilatation. The warm bath has stimulation action on the skin and reflex excites the heart and circulation. Warm water bath strengthens body and mitigates aggravations of Vata and Kapha.

Sheeta jala (cold water) indication :- Bathing with Sheeta Jala (cold water) relieves Rakta-Pitta (bleeding disease) and benefits for increase eye sight's and it tightened the pores of the face and has a contrasting effect of vasoconstriction. Bathing in cold water mitigates the aggravation of Rakta and Pitta.

Bathing is necessary not only for cleanliness of skin but also for their action on the internal organ as it helps in circulation. The sebaceous secretion of the skin and the sweat requires daily removal. Bathing is the last form of cleaning the body. Bathing in Luke warm water, drinking milk, copulation with young

women, eating food which are healthy and less in quantity are good for men always¹⁹.

Contraindications of Snana:-

Bathing is contraindicated for persons suffering from Arditha (facialpalsy), Atisara (diarrhoea), Aadmana (distension of abdomen), Pinasa (rhinitis), Ajeerna (indigestion), Bhuktavat (immediately after taking food), Jwara (fever), Karna-Shoola (earache), Anila (Vata), Arochak (anorexia) and also persons suffering from Netra (eye), Asaya (oral), Karna (ear) Rogas (diseases)^{20, 21}. Bathing in very cold water and in cold seasons aggravates Vata and Kapha. And bathing in very cold water and in hot season causes aggravation of Rakta and Pitta. A person should not bath when he had enough food, diseased, at mid night, with much cloth and near unknown ponds. One should not see his own image in water, looking down into the water standing on the lake, splash the body with either by hands, beat out the water from the hairs, cover the body with wet cloth or with the head dress, use the same dress, oil etc. warm earlier to bathing.

Snana-Sheela Manushya Gunas :-

Acharya manu has explained 10 Gunas of Snana-Sheela Manushya. Bala(strength), Roopa (enhances beauty), Swarashudhi(clear voice), Varnashudhi, Sparsha(touch), Gandha (pleasant odour), Parishudhatha (cleaniness), Shanty (peace), Saukumarya (delicacy), Uttam Strilabaare the Gunas (qualities) of Snana-Sheela person²².

Rules for taking bath:-

Bath should be taken in the morning and is prerequisite to the morning meal. Bathing should be done with Luke warm water, rubbing the entire body with cloth soon after bathing improves lustre, removes itching and disorders of skin. Dress should be changed after bath, sleep, while going out of the house and worshipping gods. The women after menstruation must have a purifying bath. The practise of an oil bath is a good Indian custom. Women folk in country side use a paste consisting of gram, mustard oil and turmeric powder and rub it on the body before bath. One who baths with Amlaka water in which Amlaka fruits are soaked, always will surely gets rid of wrinkled skin and grey hairs and lives hundreds years²³.

Conclusion & Result :-

Snana is one of the part of Dinacharya procedures which have promotive, protective and curative effect on the body health and should be practised as a prophylactic measure to attain its benefits. It maintain our body and mind health. As a results Person get all types of health Dimension such as Physical, Mental, Social, Spiritual and Emotional, So bathing should be done daily and on time.

Suggestions :-

1. In Various Parts of India there are many types of snana.
2. According to Age and Sex there are different types of Snana.
3. Holy bath taking place on various festivals happening in the country.
4. Various drug containing bath according to Hindu mythology .

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ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL AGENCIES IN ACHIEVING EDUCATION GOALS

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Abstract

In the present scenario, to ensure that every student receives high-quality education for productive participation in society, financial agencies are considering pillars of global education system. For promoting a holistic and inclusive vision of lifelong learning and to make quality education reality in future international financial agencies such as WTO, World Bank, UNICEF and UNESCO play a significant role for achieving this valuable mission. This paper focuses on the enhanced role of these international financial agencies in making global education policies and investigates the ideological basis through which these policies shaping developments in global education system. The paper concludes that these agencies help countries to develop inclusive, holistic and balanced education system worldwide from early childhood to the adult years. To generate sustainable, large scale improvements in education system and to ensure that education system respond to the real needs of societies some recommendations are also given in this paper. In a nutshell, for achieving education goals these agencies are backbones of our education system.

Keywords: Financial agencies, UNESCO, UNICEF, World Bank, WTO.

Introduction

In order to survive, flourish and blossom a nation, international cooperation is highly essential. To encourage international cooperation, education should play the most important role and it is one of the important catalysts in any nation for achieving all development goals. For progress and prosper of a nation its citizens should adequately educated. Through education, the social and economic life of the country is made better. The social and economic conditions of one nation create problems for a large number of other nations. Any problem of a nation cannot be solved by itself unless and until it gets some sympathetic understanding of other nations.

Huge investment in education leads to the creation of human capital and human capital play an important role into socioeconomic development of a nation. The accumulation of human capital implies moving to the successive levels of the educational pyramid. For climbing the educational pyramid, which

becomes an important and necessary condition for socioeconomic development, the international financial agencies came to play an increasingly important role. Currently, international financial agencies provide a favourable environment for implementing innovative approaches in education system. These agencies become relevant actors with their extensive knowledge in the education sector alongside government where the government sector is unable to achieve its education goals. For promoting respect for diversity and for protecting the right of education for all, these international agencies shaping the personal and collective identities of the individuals through principles of respect for life, human dignity and cultural diversity. Therefore we can say that international agencies play a significant role for achieving crucial socialization function which is the important aspect of education in the present scenario. Hence, it is true that world widely more people are benefiting from education than ever before.

Therefore, different international agencies have been formed in order to solve the problem of different countries of the world. These international agencies are also committed to bringing about decisive changes in their strategies and policy formulation in order to promote education. They are placing great importance on financing innovative programmes for improving the quantity and quality of education in general. The World Declaration on Education for All (1990) have been major landmarks and gave further boost to the various processes already set in motion in the country. However, it is from the 1990s onwards that the size, the role and scope of the international financial agencies have expanded dramatically for making education policies.

Objectives of the study

In the present scenario, every nation is keen on developing their education sector as a tradable service. This paper provides an overview of the enhanced role of the international agencies such as UNESCO, UNICEF, WTO and World Bank in the present education mission. The paper also reviews the global education policies which are made at present by these agencies for shaping current development in global education system and also provides some policy suggestions for future development of the education sector.

The Role of UNESCO in Education Mission

UNESCO is the specialized agency in the United Nations' system dedicated to education, culture, communications, information, social and human science, and natural and social sciences, established in 1945. UNESCO's mission has been to contribute to the building of peace, poverty eradication, lasting development and intercultural dialogue, with education as one of its principal activities to achieve this aim. Today, the organization is committed to an overall

and humanistic vision of quality education worldwide, the realization of everyone's right to education, and the belief that education plays an essential role in human, social and economic development. UNESCO has been utilizing its financial resources and professional expertise to develop, expand and create educational facilities all over the world. UNESCO's activities are funded through a combination of assessed contributions by member states to its regular budget, and voluntary contributions by member states and organizations.

UNESCO is the only United Nations agency with a mandate to cover all aspects of education which encompasses educational development from pre-school through primary, secondary and higher education, including technical and vocational education and training, non-formal education and literacy. The Organization focuses on increasing equity and access, improving quality, and ensuring that education develops knowledge and skills in areas such as sustainable development, HIV and AIDS, human rights and gender equality. UNESCO works with governments, National Commissions for UNESCO and a wide range of other partners to make education systems more effective through policy change. Therefore, UNESCO has been playing a significant role in various international programs in the field of education through its financial assistance.

The EFA movement is a global commitment led by UNESCO to provide quality basic education for all children, youth and adults. It began at the World Conference on Education for All (Jomtien, Thailand, 1990), which stressed education as a human right and outlined a holistic vision of lifelong learning. As lead agency of the EFA movement, UNESCO's educational incentives are; to provide global and regional leadership in education; to build effective education systems worldwide from early childhood to the adult years; to respond to contemporary global challenges through education. In 2000, UNESCO also adopted the eight Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) aim to halve poverty by 2015. Although MDGs 2 and 3 focus on achieving universal primary schooling, empowering women and eliminating gender disparities at the primary and secondary levels, education drives the achievement of all the MDGs. In September 2009, UNESCO took leadership in the field of early childhood development (ECD) by holding a World Conference on Early Childhood Care and Education in Moscow, Russia. Part of the follow-up of that conference is a major project to develop a Holistic Early Childhood Development Index (HECDI). U.S. education specialists will continue to participate actively in HECDI activities. This is because it equips people with the knowledge and skills to break the cycle of poverty and shape their future life chances.

There has been a history of close and ongoing cooperation between the Government of India and UNESCO in Education on all three focus areas –

access, quality, and content. India is part of UNESCO's efforts towards the Education for All (EFA) goals, the Post-2015 global education agenda, and the UN Secretary-General's Global Education First Initiative (GEFI), of which UNESCO is the lead implementing agency. The EFA goals are advanced by UNESCO in India through policy and programme support to the Government of India in Early Childhood Care and Education, Secondary Education, Technical and Vocational Education & Training, Higher Education etc. India currently holds the Chair of the EFA Task Force on Teachers. UNESCO is working to enhance research capabilities through its Chairs programme.

India's participation in UNESCO is an example of sharing with others the new problem and the unfolding vision of education to this world-wide movement of the renewal and transformation of education. India made notable contributions, and she also derived from the global cooperation of nations many advantages and ideas for her own national development. In a nutshell, UNESCO is an international laboratory of ideas, taking part in this process by mobilizing global knowledge and forward-looking research to identify, understand, and anticipate the challenges for the future of education in an increasingly complex world.

Main Functions of UNESCO in the field of Education are:

1. To raise educational standards throughout the world-specially for women and girls, who in turn will educate their children.
2. To make primary education compulsory for the removal of illiteracy.
3. Spread of knowledge by training teachers, educational planners, administrators, to encourage local building programmes and equipment of schools. To provide grants and fellowships to teachers and scholars, organize library systems and promote international understanding through education.
4. To guide and expand education to enable the developing countries to take their own development in hand more effectively.

Role of UNICEF in Education Mission

The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) was created by the United Nations in December, 1946 for providing financial aid to the suffering children of the post-World War II Europe. UNICEF became a permanent part of the United Nations in 1953 and expanded the scope of its activities in the 1960s to include advocating for and advancing children's rights to education, healthcare, nutrition and the struggle of women, especially mothers, in the developing world. In 1989, the UN General Assembly adopted the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which UNICEF uses as guidance for its programs. Most of the programmes funded by UNICEF are long-term operations closely related to the national development plans of many countries of the world.

According to its mission statement, 'UNICEF is mandated by the United Nations General Assembly to advocate for the protection of children's rights, to help meet their basic needs, and to expand their opportunities to reach their full potential.' Hence, UNICEF education objectives are: to support basic education and gender equality, including early childhood education, to enhancing the primary and secondary education quality, and to ensuring equitable access to education for both boys and girls. UNICEF bases its actions on up-to-date substantial research and experience on what works to help give children the best start in life, to survive and thrive -- especially in emergencies-- and to go to school. This work correlates closely with the Millennium Development Goals set by United Nations States in 2000 – and is central to meeting them. UNICEF's work can be grouped into different strategic areas and progresses in each area are interrelated.

These strategic areas are:

1. UNICEF works toward helping young children survive and advocates for and gives financial and technical support to national- and community-based education and intervention programmes on health care and nutrition.

2. Along with the World Health Organization (WHO), UNICEF supports local programmes that improve access to basic water and sanitation, which are in turn vital for health, development and education initiatives.

3. In support of MDG, UNICEF collaborates with countries, donor governments and other UN agencies to promote, fund, facilitate universal primary education and gender equality and works to reduce the gender gap and other disparities in access to, participation in and completion of basic schooling. This includes` supporting water, sanitation and hygiene improvement in schools to create a child-friendly environment for learning.

4. In emergencies as part of UNICEF Back-to-School programme it also delivers school supplies and tents, helping children return to a more normal, safe environment and protecting their right to basic education.

5. UNICEF promotes sustained national and global investments that leverage resources and results for children's well being, including in emergency situations. For fulfilling the children's rights to survive and flourish, UNICEF works with a wide range of partners including governments, regional bodies, and private and civil society groups. UNICEF provides input and participates in developing sector-wide approaches (SWAPs), Poverty Reduction Strategy Plans (PRSPs) and budgets.

Moreover, UNICEF also takes the lead in knowledge management: researching needs, monitoring results and keeping open records of lessons learned and is itself the lead agency for monitoring global and country data related to children. For example, The Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) method of UNICEF is an inexpensive and effective tool, which is a major

source of data for monitoring the fulfillment of human rights and progress towards the children related goals. Further, for advocating children's rights to freedom of thought and expression and to create a Web site for them to share ideas, UNICEF promotes the active participation of children and young people in decision-making on matters concerning their own well-being.

The Government of India in collaboration with UNICEF have sought to realize the national goals of providing basic education for all children and reducing disparities in education among different groups, areas and genders. In order to advance the empowerment of girls and women UNICEF supports gender equality in education system. In Many countries, where large gender gaps and as girls' vulnerability are increased, addressing gender barriers to enrolment and achievement in these contexts is an important focus for UNICEF. Typical strategies are targeted gender interventions at local levels and technical support in emergency interventions to support gender equality is integrated in policy and budgets. All of UNICEF's work in education is supported by a commitment to an inter-sectoral approach in education which is mutually beneficial and takes on extra significance in emergencies where schools provide an opportunity to bring together services for children in a safe and protective environment.

UNICEF has also provided financial as well as technical support to the implementation of projects of Minimum Levels of Learning (MLL) and Total Literacy Campaign (TLC) in co-operation with NCERT, NIEPA and other national bodies of education in the country. In a nutshell, it is an agency which is exclusively entrusted with the worldwide welfare of the children.

UNICEF education expenditure in 2018 was US\$1.2 billion, compared with approximately US\$500 million per year for the period 2006–2010. The increase during recent years has been driven principally by increased resources for emergencies. Fifty per cent of education spending in 2018 was in only eight countries, including 40 per cent in five countries affected by the Syrian crisis.

Role of World Bank in Education Mission

The World Bank was initially created to help with economic development, especially to provide long-term financing for economic development. It was originally formed shortly after World War II in an effort to rebuild the economies of war-torn countries, but its mission is now global in scope. Today the World Bank is trying to create a free global market in education and the biggest external loan provider for education programmes, which are implemented in about 85 countries. During the 1990s, the amounts lent by the World Bank for education programmes represented 27% of global external funding on education and 40% of the total aid provided for education by international organisations (Jallade, Radi, and Cuenin 2001).

The World Bank's central mandate for financial discipline and development of market economies is of course reflected in its educational programmes too. As a rule, investments in education supported by the 'Bank' have to be substantiated on the basis of human capital needs of the country under consideration. Thus, in the period 1962–80, as Heyneman (2003) demonstrates in his review of the World Bank policies in education, the 'Bank' prioritised the establishment of institutions of technical and vocational training while it inhibited the promotion of educational contents related with 'pure' science, arts or humanities, and even the construction of libraries, as these were considered merely unproductive academic activities. As a consequence, in the 1970s, when the Western countries were establishing comprehensive secondary schools, the World Bank would fund only binary secondary education systems and only if sufficient emphasis was to be on the teaching of technical skills. Similarly, in the 1980s, when the West started expanding higher education, the World Bank decided to stress through its lending programmes the provision of primary education and to promote tuition fees in developing countries' higher education systems. As a researcher demonstrates (Jones 1992), in the year 1990, 70% of the 'Bank's' education programmes requested increase of participation in primary education, 67% reduced funding to secondary and higher education, 56% promoted the introduction of tuition fees and 56% included the condition that private education should be expanded.

Without abandoning these priorities, from the 1990s onwards the World Bank has been promoting a reform agenda whose main elements are now common wherever neoliberal policies in education are well established: decentralization of school management, free choice of school, more involvement of the private sector, performance-related payments for teachers, monitoring and evaluation of educational results (see Alexander 2001).

The current focus of the World Bank's is on helping countries to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), established in 2000 at the Millennium Summit, that all 192 United Nations member states and twenty-three international organizations have agreed to achieve by the year 2015. They include reducing extreme poverty, reducing child mortality rates, fighting disease epidemics such as AIDS, and developing a global partnership for development.

Role of WTO in Education Mission

The General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) is one of the legally binding agreement aimed at deregulating trade in services adopted in 1994 as part of the then established World Trade Organization (WTO). At its heart, the GATS commits WTO members to a liberalization agenda, not just by eliminating barriers to trade and investment in services, but also by encouraging

countries that have privatized, contracted out their public services or deregulated them to cement in these liberalisations by making relevant education services commitments under the GATS. At present, the GATS agreement covers a total of 161 activities which can be clubbed under 12 major services categories and education is one of them. Prior to emergence of WTO there was no multilateral agreement on services because services invariably are place specific and were considered to be non-tradable. However, with education emerging as a trillion dollar industry, this sector is now at the center-stage of trade policy discussion.

More specifically, the GATS defines four modes of education by which trade in services can take place: (1) 'cross-border supplies'; (2) 'consumption abroad'; (3) 'commercial presence'; and (4) 'presence of natural persons'. The implementation of these four modes of education can be translated as, for example: (1) distance education, e-learning, trade of teaching aids and examination material; (2) studies abroad; (3) establishment of foreign institutions' annexes in another country (directly or through franchising), and private training companies; and (4) teachers and researchers working abroad. In the framework of these modes, several WTO members have made commitments for at least one education sector from the five defined by GATS (preschool and primary, secondary, vocational and higher, adult, and 'other' education).

Today developing countries like India face multiple challenges in the education sector like low levels of literacy, inequity and low quality basic and secondary education, declining public fund for education etc. despite the 'knowledge hub'. However, given India's abundant skilled labour force, English-speaking and technically trained manpower, there exists tremendous opportunities for India for liberalization of its education sector under the WTO.

Suggestions

There should be no doubt that today our education is in crisis and needs immediate solutions. These multiple challenges should be overcome by implement substantive organizational reforms in the education sector. A key obstacle is governments' differing perspectives regarding the role of the international financial agencies in the global multilateral framework. Such differences sometimes lead to fundamental disagreements on budgeting, programming, and, as most recently demonstrated, membership. Therefore, in emergencies and transition situations partnership is necessary between different international financial agencies. An effective and sustainable partnership requires effort and commitment on both sides at all levels of the education system. It is essential to make the expertise, competencies and comparative advantages of different partners available to support affected countries across the spectrum from emergency relief to development and growth. Work in this

area should be improved through sharing of experience, knowledge and initiating dialogue with key partners on the theory and practice of evidence-based work in education. For up-gradation of infra-structural facilities like building laboratories, computerized libraries, IT for universities / institutions promoting research and development co-operation between international agencies should also encourage. These international agencies also focus on Implement academic reforms like frequent revision of the curriculum, introduction of the course credit system, emphasis on internal assessment, quality research and improved governance of institutions. Of course, we cannot deny the fact that there is a great tendency for these international agencies to act too much and overpower the sovereignty of the countries in education system.

Conclusion

With the foregoing discussion, it can be concluded that world widely international financial agencies have great impacts on the education sector. It is vitally important that all of us who are concerned about the health of the world's children actively support and maintain constant, friendly pressure upon these international agencies. We must strongly support and defend these agencies when they take a stand on behalf of the disadvantaged, when they dare to call attention to and attack the structural injustice that underlies poverty, underdevelopment and poor health. And we must offer firm but constructive criticism when UNICEF and WHO retreat from their ideals under the browbeating of the powerful.

At the same time, we must be realistic. We cannot deny the fact that UNESCO, UNICEF, WTO, and other bodies of the United Nations have a valuable role to play as allies of grassroots movements in the struggle to achieve "education for all". In a nutshell, these international agencies are correct in asserting that momentum for progress toward a more democratic, equitable, world must come from the bottom up.

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DOES INTERNAL MARKETING IS ANTECEDENT OF COMMITMENT?

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Abstract

This research paper gives insight about the internal marketing and commitment and focussed to solve the issue of relation between internal marketing and commitment. This is a conceptual research paper. To conduct this research, qualitative data has been collected from various journals, research papers, and articles. Initially internal marketing identified as a concept to satisfy and motivate employees so that they are more committed towards the organization and leads to service improvement. On the other hand, organization is also committed to give benefits to the employees and future growth and development. It is also confirmed that committed employees creates market orientation. In this research paper a new model has been developed to clarified the relationship between internal marketing and commitment which consists of five building blocks which are job satisfaction, employee commitment, internal marketing, organizational commitment and market orientation. The three elements of internal marketing are motivation and satisfaction, internal customer orientation and internal service quality. It is found that employee commitment and organisational commitment both is required for the implementation of the internal marketing. This model also clarified that job satisfaction is the antecedent of the employee commitment and organisational commitment is antecedent of market orientation.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Employee Commitment, Internal Marketing, Organisational Commitment, Market Orientation.

1.1 Introduction

Internal marketing is the process of exchange between employer & internal customers in such a way that improves internal relationship and building long term relationship with each other to achieve objective of the organization. Internal marketing improves employees capabilities and competencies. In the internal market jobs are called as products. Employees are motivated to sell job products in the internal market. Employee satisfaction or internal customer satisfaction is important for the internal marketing implementation. The first step of internal marketing process is 'motivation and satisfaction'. According to

this step organization get success to sell job products. After this internal customer orientation and inter-functional coordination created in the organization. It develops good relation of employees within the organization that makes positive impact on their commitment towards organization. Employee's intention to work, emotional attachment can be built through internal communication, inter-functional coordination of the organization. For the long-term success organization has to treat employees as a capital assets. Mayer and Allen defined three components of organizational commitment which are, emotional commitment, normative commitment and continuous commitment. Emotional commitment is the attachment of the employee to the organisation which shows that organisation has strong bonding with the employees. When employees joined any reputed organisation or working in a good company they are happy with their personal growth that retains them in a particular organisation, this is normative commitment. And when employees think that will lose something after leaving the organisation this makes them needy for the job, this is continuous commitment. Third component of Meyer and Allens model is continuance commitment in which employees have to pay cost when they leave the organization. If cost is high then chance of leaving organization is less likely. Cost may be low salary in another organization, no job opportunity, do not have opportunity to get better work environment etc. Employees retain in the organization due to two reasons. First is when they would like to work at the present organization. Second reason, is that when employees want to leave organization but they have no opportunity of another good job. Even if government employees do not want to continue their job they are unable to quit due to no option except it. Internal marketing is a tool to build employee commitment in which employees are motivated for work. For selling organizational values, goals, mission, vision internal marketing is a best practice. By getting job products that they want and all the things to perform that job employees become committed towards organization. Internal marketing is the overall activities involved between employees and employer for the mutual benefit.

In this competitive era, it is difficult to retain competitive employees, to compete with the external market, to increase organisational values and to improve the performance of the employees. Thus, commitment is necessary to compete in the market. However, success of the organisation is depends on the employees and the employer both. Both works for the mutual benefits and it leads to achieve organisational goals. It is difficult to measure the employee performance but it is easy to see the impact of it on the market orientation. Job satisfaction and employee commitment are linked to each other. Satisfied employees are willing to work for long time in the particular organisation. Internal marketing is a tool, strategy or practice that creates internal customer

orientation and improves internal service quality that leads to organisational performance. The ultimate goal of the commitment and internal marketing is to create market orientation. Thus it is pivotal to understand the relation between commitment and internal marketing.

2.1 Objective of the Study

To find out the relation between the internal marketing and commitment.

3.1 Internal Marketing and Commitment

Commitment is called as multi-dimensional concept due to different viewpoints of it. According to Hunt and Morgan (1994), Committed employees benefited in the organizations in two ways which are, a strong intention of employees or internal customers to serve customers and employee retention. Commitment means to accept the values of the organization, attitude, and belief in accepting goals of the organization, strong liking of an organization that makes them willing to stay in the organization depicted by Mowday et al. Robbins Coulter (2003) et al explained it as committed employees keen to serve their organization in a worthy manner and have strong intention to retain at the organization. According to Akroyd et al. (2008), it is the affection of employees to stay in the organization.

IM is the practice of exchange between employer & internal customers in such a way that enhances internal relationships and maintaining long-term relationship with each other to achieve the objective of the organization.

According to Gilmore (2000), employee commitment is widely used to improve the effectiveness of services through internal marketing. This means internal marketing improves the quality of services providing by the organization. For this there is need of employee commitment. Employee commitment is on priority to get success in the internal marketing implementation. Shekary et al. (2012) revealed that internal marketing is an effective means of organizational commitment. Gilmore and Shekary agreed that for commitment, internal marketing plays a very important.

Internal marketing improves the employee's capabilities and competencies to improve service quality. For the implementation of internal marketing in the organization, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment is required. Various studies confirmed that internal marketing has a positive impact on organizational commitment.

Due to two views regarding internal marketing and organizational commitment it becomes difficult to find out that organisational commitment is antecedent or succeeding dimension of internal marketing. Olorunleke K took five dimensions to study the impact of internal marketing on the organizational

commitment, which are, motivation, job satisfaction, training, understanding and differentiation of employees, inter-functional coordination and integration and found all the dimensions are positively related with organizational commitment. Likewise, Moghaddam (2012) found that there is a positive impact of internal marketing on the organizational commitment and customer orientation. Nuthathai Thaotrakool empirically examined in the hotel industry that internal communication builds trust and commitment among employees. The researcher studied on IM practice (Empowerment, rewards, training and development, and communication) to see the impact of it on organizational commitment. Except for communication, they found all the dimensions are positively related with organizational commitment. Organizational commitment works as a mediator between internal marketing and service quality in the study of Tsai et. al. This means internal marketing is the creator of organizational commitment and that improves service quality.

Various studies gave different perspectives between internal marketing and organizational commitment. Due to multidimensional in nature, commitment is relating with internal marketing in a various ways. By analysing studies of internal marketing and commitment relation it can be explained in the following categories.

- **Indirect relation between internal marketing and organizational commitment**

Studies shows indirect relation between internal marketing and organizational commitment and market orientation works as a mediator between the two.

One of the internal marketing dimensions, inter-functional coordination studied on organizational commitment of Jaworski and Kohli (1993) shows the indirect relation of inter-functional coordination and organizational commitment. In the study they found that market orientation works as a mediator between the two. Likewise, the effect of internal marketing on organizational commitment in Iranian banks was studied by Farzad et al (2008). The most significant component of internal marketing that makes an impact on organizational commitment was inter-functional coordination. Many researchers (Caruana et al 1997, Jones et al 2003, Waris 2005,) viewed IM is to create market orientation and found a positive relation between IM and organizational commitment.

- **Studies shows indirect relation between internal marketing and commitment and job satisfaction works as a mediator between the two.**

Job is a product in the internal marketing. To accomplish the goal of the organization it is necessary to make employees satisfied. According to Scott (2002) job satisfaction is an individual assessment of a job. Employees get emotional experience through job satisfaction. There are two components of job satisfaction that has been given by Dawes are, cognitive and affective. Shimizu et al (2005) advised that the job itself results in job satisfaction. Employees do exchange with the organization in which organization sells the job and employees purchase it. Organisation gives monetary and non-monetary benefits to the employees and employees give their services to the organization. Researchers worked to search out the factors affecting organizational commitment in the banks of Vietnam city. Vietnam banks were facing trouble in managing loans, to overcome this problem researcher focused on how makingan employee commitment. In the study, researcher hypothesized that human resource practice (relationship with management, working environment, career development, teamwork spirit, compensation) positively affects job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Job satisfaction works as amediator and their result proved that first human resource practice makes an impact on Job satisfaction and after this on organizational commitment. Studies proved job satisfaction as a mediator between the internal marketing, and organizational commitment. Internal marketing is a growing concept, but underdeveloped concept.

3.2 Relation between internal marketing job satisfaction and organisational commitment

There are two views regarding job satisfaction and internal marketing. First is internal marketing is antecedent of job satisfaction and the other is job satisfaction is antecedent of internal marketing. Fig. no, 2.1 shows the relationship among Internal marketing, job satisfaction and organisational commitment.

- **Internal marketing is antecedent of job satisfaction**

Fig. No. 2.1

According to first perspective, internal marketing is antecedent of job satisfaction. Al-Hawary (2013), favored that Internal marketing has an impact on job satisfaction in the study of sports centers. It is also accepted that IM has a positive effect on job satisfaction and it makes an impact on organizational commitment in sports centers. Chiu found that Internal Marketing makes a positive impact on job satisfaction and job satisfaction leads to organizational commitment. Mohammad Khalaf Ahmad researched on IM variables (selection & appointment, training & development, org support, incentive, motivation, retention policy) on two dependent variables, one is job satisfaction and other is an organizational commitment in Saudi teaching hospitals.

Job satisfaction is antecedent of internal marketing

Fig. No. 2.2

Fig. No. 2.2 shows relationship among job satisfaction, internal marketing and organizational commitment. Some authors agreed that job satisfaction is antecedent of internal marketing. Some researcher's emphasized on the impact of job satisfaction on internal Marketing and effects of organizational commitment on internal marketing. They found positive effects of job satisfaction and organizational commitment in Melli Bank. In this job satisfaction and organizational commitment, both are antecedents of internal marketing.

3.3 Relationship among commitment, market orientation and organisational commitment

Fig. 2.3 shows relationship among internal marketing, market orientation and Organisational commitment. There are also two views of researchers to explain the relationship between commitment and market orientation. According to kohli and joworskis 1990 market orientation is antecedent to commitment and according to Sivaramakrishnan et al 2008, commitment is antecedent of market orientation.

- Market orientation is antecedent to commitment (Kohli and Jaworski's 1990).

Fig. No. 2.3

Mehdi Abzari found that internal marketing directly or indirectly influence market orientation and after this makes an impact on organizational commitment. This means that internal marketing influence organizational commitment after the market orientation. The researcher studied the impact of IM and commitment on market orientation in Mellat bank. They found that internal marketing has a positive impact on market orientation. They also found a positive relationship between commitment and market orientation. Whereas no relationship between internal marketing and commitment. It is suggested that there is a need to improve commitment and market orientation through internal marketing. According to Kohli and Jaworski's market orientation is antecedent to commitment. This means commitment develops through internal marketing. This shows that it is the output to internal marketing and input for external marketing.

- **Commitment is the antecedent of market orientation (Sivaramakrishnan et al 2008)**

Fig.2.4

According to Sivaramakrishnan et al (2008), committed employees eagerly take part in the implementation of market orientation culture. For creating a market orientation, culture, internal marketing is implemented thus, the commitment of employees is required for its success. According to this view, commitment acts as input for market orientation. Internal marketing creates market orientation, thus commitment is also an input for internal marketing. Fig. 2.4 shows relationship among employee commitment, market orientation, and internal marketing.

4.1 Research Proposed Model

To clarify the relation between internal marketing and commitment a research proposed model is developed that is given in fig no. 3.1. The five building blocks of the model are job satisfaction, employee commitment, internal marketing, organizational commitment and market orientation. The three elements of internal marketing are motivation and satisfaction, internal customer orientation and internal service quality.

Fig. 3.1 Research Proposed Model: Job satisfaction, employee commitment, Internal Marketing, ornaizational commitment and Market orientation.

Important features of this research proposed model are:-

1. To implement internal marketing, employee commitment is necessary.

In the research proposed model of internal marketing and commitment there are two commitment necessary for the implementation of internal marketing process in the organisation. Employee commitment makes employees happy to work while organisational commitment drives organisation to achieve goals. For the implementation of the internal marketing it is prerequisite to understand internal customers or employees in a well manner and make them satisfied.

2. Job satisfaction is antecedent of employee commitment

Employees are willing to work when they are satisfied. Organisation always provide benefits and services to their internal customers so that they will work effectively. To get work done it is necessary to make committed employees in the organization. Employees can not be forced to work in the organisation. Thus to make them productive they should be willing to work. They are interested to work only if they are happy and satisfied.

3. Organisational commitment is also required with the employee commitment for the implementation of the internal marketing

Organisational commitment is required for creating internal customer orientation in the organisation. It also enhances internal service quality of the organisation. Employee commitment makes employees willing to work while organisational commitment make ready organisation for improving internal process for the effective implementation of the internal marketing. Organisational commitment determines the organisational behaviour with the employees. It represents organisational bonding with the employees.

4. Process of Internal Marketing

The model shows three elements of internal marketing process :-

A) Motivation and satisfaction

The first most important element of the internal marketing process is the motivation and satisfaction of employees. Various researchers, Berry (1981); Grootenboer (1985), Ahmed and Rafiq (1991), Dr. Teena mishra (2014), confirmed that motivation and satisfaction improves organisational performance. Motivated and satisfied employees are more committed for work. Internal marketing is the process of motivating and satisfying employees so that they can organisational goals. It is the exchange process in which organisation sells jobs products and employees provides their services to the organisation. Dr. Teena Mishra (2018) clarified the exchange process of internal marketing in which organisation and employees both works as marketer and customer.

As a marketer organisation sells job products and employees as a customer pay cost in the form of psychic, time energy, opportunity cost etc. On the other hand employees as a marketer sell their services to organisation and organisation pay in the form of monetary and non-monetary benefits to employees. In the research proposed model, motivation and satisfaction makes employees committed for work.

B) Internal customer orientation

Internal customer orientation means understanding needs and wants of employees so that they have knowledge, idea of products and services provided by the organisation. It makes employees sales oriented. Without creating internal customer orientation employees do not understand the value of the organisation. Organisation sells their products and services to the external market. Before this, it is necessary to sell it in the internal market. Internal

customers creates value addition in the internal market that improves market orientation and makes organisation profitable.

C). Internal service quality

Internal Service quality is the third most important element that represents in the model. In the internal market employees works as internal customers and internal suppliers. Organisation and internal suppliers are providing services to the internal customers. In the internal market there are two types of products that are manufacturing in the organisation which are products/services manufacturing to sell in the external market and the job products that are selling to the internal customers. To improve the internal service quality it is necessary to increase the coordination between the internal customers and internal suppliers. Internal customers understand well about the need of the organisation for their growth. Internal market is also integrated market in which all departments and all functions ie. Marketing, finance, human resource, production, administration and research and development have to work together.

5 . Organisational commitment is antecedent of market orientation

Employees who are willing to work in a organisation are known as committed employees. Employees who are committed to the organisation are also expecting the same for the organisation. Organisation have clear mission, vision, values, goals representing that they have high potential to achieve long term goals. Employees are interested to work with the growing organisation. They also get benefits from the organisation. Thus employees and organisation works for mutual benefits.Organisational commitment creates market orientation thus it is antecedents of market orientation. Market oriented organisation first looks at the market and its target customers. Before any sales activities takes place organisation learn about the potential customer need and wants from the organisation. The products or services offering by the organisation is therefore created with the customer in mind. Organisation not only understand the needs or wants of the existing customer but also potential customers. In the strategic terms market orientation revolves around culture, internal behaviours and values that focussed on satisfying customer needs.

5.1 Findings

The objective of the study was to find out the relation between internal marketing, employee commitment and organisational commitment. The findings of the study are :

1. To implement internal marketing, employee commitment and organisational commitment both are required.
2. Job satisfaction is antecedent of employee commitment
3. Organisational commitment is antecedent of market orientation

6.1 Discussion and Conclusion

This research paper focussed on the relation between commitment and internal marketing. To understand the relationship between internal marketing and commitment first need to understand commitment based management.¹ When an organization is committed towards internal customers, then internal customers also committed towards organization to achieve organization goal. Therefore employee commitment and organisational commitment both required. Internal Marketing is not looking on one parameter of commitment by employees to provide service to external customers or working with full potential. There are five building blocks of the models which are, job satisfaction, employee commitment, internal marketing, organisational commitment and market orientation. There are three elements of the internal marketing which are motivation and satisfaction, internal customer orientation and internal service quality. According to this model, employees are committed to work when they are satisfied with their job. Committed employees are ready to implement internal marketing process. They need motivation and satisfaction before creating internal customer orientation in the organisation. Employees or internal customers understand the mission, vision of the organisation. They get knowledge about the products and services provided by the organisation. With the employee commitment, organisational commitment is also required for the implementation of the internal marketing. Organisational commitment helps in the bonding between employee and employee to achieve organisational goal thus it leads to market orientation. This creates positive relation between organisation and employees. Organisation commitment shows they are interested to provide services and benefits to the employees for achieving their goals. It creates positive work culture in the organisation. Organisational commitment is the antecedent of the market orientation. Committed organisation understands the vision, mission and goals of the organisation. Such organisation always ready to satisfy the need of the customers whether they are internal customers or external customers. Market orientation means to understand the need or wants of the external customers and understand the market requirements. Before sell the products or services to the external customer it is prerequisite to understand their needs or wants. Organisation who

¹Shekary Op.cit.

are committed are always ready to work according to the need or wants of their customers.

In a summarize way five building blocks of the model can be explained as, job satisfaction makes committed employees, employee commitment and organisational commitment is necessary for the implementation of the internal marketing process that includes, motivation and satisfaction, internal customer orientation and internal service quality and committed organisation creates market orientation.

Limitations of the study and Future Scope

This research study includes only theoretical aspect. To clarify the relationship between commitment and internal marketing a research proposed model is developed. This model is not empirically tested. In the future study this model can be empirically tested in the service and product industry. More studies are required in the field of commitment and internal marketing so that organisation can be benefited.

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THEATRE: A SOCIAL BAROMETER FOR AFRICAN AMERICANS ACTIVISM

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Abstract:

The main aim of this paper is to bring out the African Americans phenomenal success in the white dominant world. To be effective in advocating the political agenda and to redefine their suppressed community, the African American dramatists have adhered to a deeper and more emotional level of exposing their creativity through their theatre of activism. Throughout history, the most effective political activists have united themselves with drama in campaigning for a social change. For example, Martin Luther King Jr., who was highly acknowledged for his moral courage could reach the pinnacle of success only through drama for which he was acclaimed by the social movement historian Doug McAdam as, “genius for strategic dramaturgy”. In the staging of demonstrations, King and his lieutenants engaged themselves in signifying work, mindful of the messages and potent symbols which they encoded in their actions. Theatre plays a vital role in the social transformation of African Americans.

Key words: Theatre, African Americans, Activism, Social change

Introduction:

African American dramas represent a fundamental break from traditional playwriting. Traditionally, the playwrights established conventions in the portrayal of characters that remained consistent throughout the play. In the new playwriting of African American drama, the terrain of characters that remained consistent throughout the play gets shifted.

The history of black theatre chronicles the many significant plays which were produced to expose and explode the definitions of blackness. William Wells Brown’s *The Escape or A Leap to Freedom*(1858) was the first black play published in the United States. In this work, black performers exploited the theatricality of the construction of blackness. The power of theatre acts as a cultural force within and as a social barometer of African American experiences. African American dramaturgy offers an insight into the evolution

of blackness, a device, continually reconstructed and redefined within the theatre.

Blooming Activism:

African American theatre began in the Harlem Renaissance of the 1920s and 1930s. This was a time when big cities like New York, Chicago, and Washington, D.C., saw a flowering of African American art, blues, jazz, poetry and fiction. They produced musicals that were successful and popular with both, whites and blacks. The musicals were introduced African American life. By witnessing the success of musicals, white investors began to get into the business and shunned the blacks out. During the Great Depression (1930-1940) of the theatre, there arrived a government jobs program called the Federal Theatre Project, or FTP. The FTP served as a training ground for black actors, most of whom had only found work previously as extras or chorus dancers. The project also employed and schooled African Americans in lighting, sound and other technical parts of theatre. The art of theatre is a mirrored performance of life. It serves to assist in achieving a transformational shift amidst the psyche of the audience.

The FTP produced plays with all-black casts by well-known African American writers of the time like Frank Wilson's folk drama, *Walk Together, Chillun* (1936) and Theodore Browne's *Lysistrata* (1936). In 1939, the FTP shut down. African Americans kept writing good plays, but they found little support for their work. Even the best-known black actors got only stereotyped roles such as servants. Black community cropped up in the late 1930s. The Negro Playwrights' Company and the American Negro Theatre, both founded in 1940s encouraged black writers, actors and directors to develop their talents.

From the arrival of the first African slaves on the American soil, the discourse on race, the definitions and meanings of blackness have been intricately linked to the issues of theatre and its performance. In the past, the Westerners treated the blacks with intellectual inferiority and cultural primitivism. It is believed that colonization as well as the slave trade was possible because of the superior technology of the West, which gave it much economic and military power. The Africans did not show interest in the improved technology of the West and they failed to realize that these would bring about a technological revolution. This lack of interest for the new and resistance to change help the Westerners to treat blacks with inferior intellectualism. As for as cultural primitivism is considered, the opinions that other people have of Africans, have played a paramount role in their awareness of themselves. African traditions were almost totally oral. Most of the writings on Africa, by which African culture begun to be objectified, were done by the foreigners who were often prejudiced. At a particular moment, the

representation of African inferiority began to take shape. It was increased and given formal status by racialist views which were largely motivated by political and economic interest. Imperialistic expansions combined with capitalism were considered to have been the main causes of the Trans-Atlantic slave trade. To justify the slave trade, the myth of the inferior black humanity was propagated. To a certain extent the Christian missionary venture was based on similar assumptions. The slave trade provoked a disintegration of the socio-political and economic structures of Africa and a real degradation of the slaves themselves. In this way the concept of black cultural primitivism was reinforced.

Pioneers of Social Activism:

The plays of Alice Childress and Lorraine Hansberry have stood as examples of creating a social revolution. Both these dramatists through their dramatic texts and through their performance have transcended the written pages to a form of political activism. As the feminist assertion that the personal is political, the plays of these two writers have opened up a political stage of resistance in which their black characters have become conscious constructive agents and have proved themselves to be informed actors of the society.

In the 1960s, activism became the dominant theme of the black theatre. The interracial free Southern Theatre brought an eclectic array of plays to the rural South as part of the Civil Rights Movement. It was LeRoi Jones who later adopted the name Amiri Baraka wrote *Dutchman*, an inflammatory one act play in which a white woman murders a black youth on a New York subway, and James Baldwin produced *Blues for Mr.Charlie*, an embittered view of the Civil Rights Movement.

Theatre as a Social Barometer:

It was from the middle to the late 1960s, owing to the passage of Civil Rights Act (1965) and with the escalation of the Vietnam War and the Black Power Movement, a huge explosion of black theatre sprang nationwide. Over six hundred companies were founded, of which the National Black Theatre and the New Federal lasted for years and made major contributions. Theatres like, The New Lafayette (1966-1972) produced group-created rituals on social and political themes, which includes Ed Bullins, *In the Wine Time* (1968) and *Goin' a Buffalo* (1968); Douglas Turner Ward's *Day of Absence* (1965) were performed. From the 1970s, the black feminists like NtozakeShange produced plays of radical activism.

The 1960s and 1970s were transformative years for African American descent in innumerable ways. The theatre that LeRoi Jones proposes is inextricably linked to the Afro American political dynamic. This link is perfectly consistent with Black America's contemporary society. The Black

American Theatre dated roughly from 1965 to 1976, has been called the 'Second Black Renaissance,' suggesting a comparison to the Harlem Renaissance of the 1920s and 1930s. The two periods were alike in encompassing literature, music, visual arts and theatre. Both the movements emphasized racial pride, an appreciation of African heritage, and a commitment to produce works that reflected the culture and experiences of black people. Black Theatre's dominant spirit was politically militant and racially separatist.

In 1968 manifesto, The Black Arts Movement critic Larry Neal calls the transformative potential agent of theatre as 'potentially the most social of all the arts' and as 'an integral part of the socialization process' (qtd. in. Anadolu-Okur 95). Even other black theatre critics like LeRoi Jones, Maulana Karenga comment the theatre as a potent space for the articulation of black social and cultural agency and self-determination. African American theatre critics and artists from W.E.B. Du Bois to Amiri Baraka and to August Wilson have asserted that the black practitioners must use the theatre as a means of protest and revolt in order to change black lives and fight oppressive conditions. The genre of theatre, like much of early African American literature, sprang forth from the years of enslavement, Jim Crowism and inequality that African American faced in the United States. With its theatrical voices, nursed at the hands of Du Bois, protest drama became the first real area of African American theatrical presentation composition. Du Bois believed that the purpose of an African American theatre was to present characters who reflected the possibilities of African American culture. In his 1926 manifesto, Du Bois states that "a real Negro theatre" must be "About us, By us, For us, and Near us"(134). Amiri Baraka formerly known as LeRoi Jones and Imamu Amear Baraka has left a radical legacy in theatre. In 1965, he wrote a blistering commentary entitled The Revolutionary Theatre which imparts the totality of black experience without losing any of its African essentialities. He was stubborn that 'The Revolutionary Theatre must take dreams, and give them a reality.' August Wilson aspires to re-present African American history in a light totally of its own and separate from that of comprehensive American history. Wilson expands the historical vision of his dramatic ancestor to examine the ties African Americans have with an African-spiritual heritage. To him, music and spirituality are the two cultural components that strengthened African Americans' position within American society. This is most evident in the plays of Joe Turner's Come and Gone, Ma Rainey's Black Bottom and The Piano Lesson. They believed that 'you sing 'cause that's a way of understanding life.' (Wilson 491) He was fascinated by the power of theatre as a medium where a community at large could come together to bear witness to events and currents unfolding. He remarked in The Paris Review, that his plays offer white Americans a different way to look at black Americans. They confronted ways in

which African American theatre and performance have operated as social barometer and tools of protest.

African American Theatre, A symbol of Social Change:

This paper explores the intersections of black race, theatre and its performance in America. These intersections are always dynamic and multidimensional. The theatrical performances of blacks reflect the social and historical lives of their society. This examination of African American theatre and its technique offer an insight into the continuity and continuum of theatrical practices over time.

Program from the production of "On Strivers Row" Scene from American Negro Theatre Production of "On Strivers Row," Manuscripts, Archives and Rare Books Division, 1946, with Harry Belefonte – Photographs and prints Division, SchomburgCenter for Research in Black Culture SchomburgCenter for Research in Black Culture

Fig

The American Negro Theatre (ANT), co-founded in 1940 by Frederick O'Neal and Abram Hill, was established to provide black actors, playwrights, directors and other theater professionals with the opportunity to work in productions that illustrated the diversity of black life.

Lorraine Hansberry's pioneer Alice Childress in enacting her plays in theatre exclusively allotted for blacks. Lorraine Hansberry debut through the Black Arts Theatre which received immense success. It was the success of the series of plays which awakens the consciousness of Black theatre which made them to pay a tribute to their dramatist by naming a theatre in her name which is presented below.

Fig.

Alice Childress and Lorraine Hansberry shared a vision that blacks must struggle together to secure political, social and economic gains. These dramatists had very definite and similar views about racism, poverty, education, politics and sexism. The symbols in their plays serve as an index to the authors' attitudes about these subjects. Childress uses her keen mind to address the struggle of her people with the aim of effecting social change. She commented in 1968, "The plaster now slapped on our wounds is welfare and poverty programs...This society tells us they would rather support us as charity cases than open the doors and let us win or fail, live or die, as full citizens of this country" (86). In *A Candle in a Gale Wind*, Childress also states that black Americans are "besieged with accusations of inferiority in learning skills" (113). On the subject of education, she poignantly reminds America that 'blacks were the only racial group in America ever forbidden by law to read and write, and to enter libraries, concert halls, theatres and public schools' (113)

Joseph Roach, a remarkable theatre theorist remarks that: "Performance is one powerful way in which cultures remember who and what they are. [It] is also one powerful way of making them who and what they are" (Kruger 711). The particular history and stereotypes, each racial group of slavery and immigration has to deal with obviously shape their dramatic production. Organized theater

and performances, then become good sites for historians to investigate the formation of racial expressions and racial stereotypes, as theatre often constitutes a repertoire of actions which repeat themselves in the surrounding society. Genevieve E. Fabre notes in the introduction to Afro-American poetry and drama,

the stage is used with double purpose: it becomes a platform from which to launch protest against the ills inflicted upon black people by white society, as well as a place where black life could be not simply duplicated, but also recreated, receiving its proper scope and depth. The theatre could thus offer and legitimize new images of black people in reaction to the stereotypes that still existed in the white psyche and had often been revitalized by white dramatists.

(258).

Conclusion:

Theatre, as a potent space, created the rebellious potential in an individual particularly in the black women by not only redefining themselves but also in reconstructing their neighbourhood. The interrelatedness of the dramatic text with the theatrical performance exhibits the transformation both in the theatrical time and in the mind of the audience. Human dignity is at a premium in the works of Alice Childress and Lorraine Hansberry. They defined themselves as perfect citizens of the theater, great collaborators, and inspiring women amidst the African American audience.

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WITNESS PROTECTION IN INDIA

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Abstract

Witness plays a significant job in the criminal equity framework. The result of any trial depends on the testimony witness. Without his help Court couldn't sum up with a prudent choice. Be that as it may, it has been seen in different occurrences that observes turn antagonistic over the span of a trial. The principle purpose for antagonistic vibe is that the observer is undermined and being pressurized by the charged or his relatives to offer declaration in his/her kindness. This has gone to a premature delivery of equity. Accordingly, there is a need to embrace an appropriate and successful observer insurance arrangement in the nation. Considering the above issue, the Union government had advised a Plan called Witness Protection Scheme, 2018. In spite of the fact that the plan was received in full eagerness and enthusiasm it has not filled its need. There are different nations like USA, UK, Australia, Germany, Canada, and so on who have fused Witness Protection program in their local laws.

Introduction

Commission of a crime is a diverse procedure, zenith of the set of associated occasions and arrangement of acts. One of the primary goals of criminal equity framework is to secure and rebuff the wrongdoer which should be possible simply after the cautious and precise examination distinguishing the arrangement of acts basic to demonstrate the wrongdoing. Efficient assortment and introduction of proof is basic to the insightful procedure as the barrier perpetually try to undermine its veracity to cast away the criminal risk during the trial. The instrument of evidence is the medium through which realities, either questioned or required to be demonstrated, are adequately passed on to the legal executive in common too criminal issues. The proof under the steady gaze of the court or a legal authority can be comprehensively separated into two (1) narrative evidence and (2) oral evidence. Oral proof is commonly given by the observers, be it the casualty himself, the denounced or some other individual having any data identifying with the issue. Here the observer assumes a significant job in the criminal preliminaries and helps the court in the organization of equity. It is by methods for witnesses that both the narrative and material confirmations are normally introduced to the court. An observer may along these lines be comprehensively characterized as an individual who offers

proof to a legal counsel. All semi-legal courts and councils of every single other kind get proof through observers.¹

Definition of Witnesses

An observer in a criminal preliminary assumes a crucial job in deciding the destiny of the case. "Witness" has been characterized no place in the Criminal Procedure Code. An observer might be characterized as one who gives proof for a situation, an uninterested individual to each gathering, promised to talk reality, every bit of relevant information and only reality.²

As indicated by Black's Law Dictionary, "Witness is one who sees, knows or vouches for something or one who gives declaration, having sworn to tell the truth or certification in the individual or by the oral or composed statement, or by Affidavit".³

As indicated by J. Wadhwa, "A criminal case is based on the building of proof,proof that is acceptable in Law. For that witnesses are required, regardless of whether it is immediate proof or fortuitous proof".⁴

Concept of witnesses under Old Hindu Law

The Dharma Sutras in old India harps on the time at which and the manners by which witnesses are to be analysed and how they are to be tried. The law suppliers set out that in the contested cases reality will be set up by methods for witnesses. Be that as it may, there was a sharp qualification between adduction of oral proof in common issues and criminal offenses. As brought up by B. Master Rajah Rao, they demanded high good capability of an observer in common issues and didn't allow anybody being picked from avenues or from the court premises and made to oust, as is exceptionally regular in the advanced Indian courts.⁵

The strategy for looking at witnesses set out by Manu is an occasion of assessment in court and within the sight of parties. This makes it apparent that that the observers were likewise analysed on commission. As indicated by Hindu practice, it was the appointed authority who put inquiries to witnesses looking like common law preliminaries. They were coordinated to intently watch the activities and lead of the observers in the dock and settle on their unwavering quality.⁶

¹Whittaker Chambers, Witness Quotes (Jan. 7, 2014, 10:30 AM), <http://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/keywords/witness>.

²P. RamanathaIyer "Concise Law Dictionary", p. 896(Wadhwa & company, Nagpur, 8th Edn., 2004)

³Bryan a Garner (Ed.), Black's Law Dictionary, p.1596.(West group, St. Paul, Minnesota, 17th Edn., 1999).

⁴Swaran Singh V. State of Punjab 2000 Cri.L.J 2780.

⁵B. Guru Rajah Rao, Ancient Hindu Judicature 60 (Ganesh & Co, 1920).

⁶G. Buhler, The Laws Of Manu 268 (Sri Satguru Publications, 2001).

Under the Mohammedan law, like cutting edge manages, the proof in legitimate issues is named oral and documentary. The oral proof is sub-separated into immediate and prattle. Witnesses were inspected and interrogated independently out of the knowing about different observers. Driving inquiries were not permitted on the ground this would prompt doubt that the court was attempting to assist one with celebrating to the preference of the other. In any case, if an observer was startled or befuddled, the appointed authority could pose such inquiries to expel the disarray in any event, when they add up to driving inquiries. It was urged that the adjudicator would be at risk to the charge of predisposition on the off chance that he was placing question so as to find solutions to certainty which should be demonstrated by the observer.⁷

Concept of witnesses under Old Modern Law

A witness is somebody who has first-hand information about wrongdoing or sensational occasion through their faculties (for example seeing, hearing, smelling, contacting) and can help guarantee significant contemplations to the wrongdoing or occasion. It has been properly repeated that witnesses are gauged, not numbered. As the declaration of witnesses gives a broad guide to the courts to arrive at reality and put the lawbreakers in jail, the observers are under this moral and self-righteous obligation to talk reality and just truth. The truth and points of interest of the case must be set up with the connection of revelations made and confirm created in the court, by observers of the case and according to the rule that everyone must follow, two observers are on a standard with hundred, in the event that they are fruitful in demonstrating the realities of the case. In this way, witnesses are for all intents and purposes the establishment stones on whom the mainstays of equity gladly stand. case and according to the rule that everyone must follow, two observers are on a standard with hundred, on the off chance that they are fruitful in demonstrating the realities of the case. In this manner, witnesses are for all intents and purposes the establishment stones on whom the mainstays of equity gladly stand.⁸

Kinds of Witnesses

The accompanying could the order of witnesses, which is generally comprehensive:

1. Arraignment or Prosecution Witness – All the people giving proof in the interest of the indictment are arraignment witnesses. The individual enduring because of the commission of the wrongdoing is known as a casualty. An

⁷ Manzar Saeed, Commentary On Muslim Law In India 345-46 (2008).

⁸ Inserted by the Code of Criminal Procedure (Amendment) Act, 2008.

announcement made by him is a significant bit of proof and he is the essential indictment witness. It likewise incorporates Investigation official.⁹

2. Defence Witness – Witnesses showing up for the benefit of the defence are guard observers.¹⁰

3. Child Witness – A kid even of 6 or 7 years old might be allowed to offer proof in the event that he has the ability to response sanely.¹¹

4. Eye-witness – Eye observer is the person who has by and by act being referred to and can give its direct portrayal.¹²

5. Factional or intrigued observer – A divided or intrigued observer is one who is in a close to a relationship with the casualty of wrongdoing and is worried about the conviction of the denounced individual.¹³

6. Chance Witnesses – If unintentionally or chance an individual happened to be at a position of an event of the episode, he is an opportunity witness. The proof given by such an observer is profoundly dependable in light of the fact that he isn't associated with either party. Be that as it may, on the off chance that he is identified with either party, at that point his affidavits might be weighed in the wake of thinking about different realities and conditions.¹⁴

7. Master as an observer – The Evidence Act gives that in the clinical assessment it is required in specific cases that a clinical official should give his report likewise in the wake of leading an assessment. For instance in instances of posthumous and the reason for death. Specialists from different fields for example penmanship specialists could likewise be called to affirm for the situation.¹⁵

8. Character observer – A character observer is an individual giving data in regard of the notoriety of someone else.¹⁶

Significance of Witnesses in Criminal Trials

The observers assume a vital job in the criminal equity arrangement of any ward—precedent-based law or common law. Equity Wadhwa properly reasoned that the establishment of a criminal case lays on the development of proof, especially which is allowable by codes of law. Along these lines an observer orders significant assurance with the exception of the offended party and the respondent. Looking for truth, he assumes that frightened job of the sun

⁹ <http://www.legalindia.in/different-kinds-of-evidences-witnesses-under-the-indian-evidence-act> (last accessed on 28/03/2020 at 8:09 pm)

¹⁰Id.

¹¹Id.

¹² http://www.citizensinformation.ie/en/justice/witnesses/types_of_witnesses.html (last accessed on 28/03/2020 at 8:17 pm)

¹³ State Of U.P vs Iftikhar Khan &Ors, 1973 AIR 863

¹⁴Dalip Kumar and Gudar vs The State, 5 November, 2012

¹⁵ <http://www.legalindia.in/different-kinds-of-evidences-witnesses-under-the-indian-evidence-act> (last accessed on 28/03/2020 at 8:26 pm)

¹⁶ <http://www.wisegeek.com/what-is-a-character-witness.htm> last accessed on 28/03/2020 at 8:29 pm

which dispenses with the murkiness of obliviousness and lights up the substance of equity, surrounded by demons of mankind and compassion. He/she plays out a significant open obligation of helping the court in settling on the blame or in any case of the denounced. He submits himself to interrogation and can't decline to respond to inquiries on the ground that the appropriate response will implicate him.¹⁷

The discipline for those observers who neglect to give the court right data and explain the punishments for the equivalent.¹⁸ Further, the competency of an observer to affirm as an observer is a condition point of reference. In the event that the witness is skilful, he can't be kept from showing up in the court and giving proof.¹⁹

There are numerous troubles looked by the observers at different phases of the examination. The time for testing ends up being the most troublesome of them. He may confront the dangerous terrorizing to himself and to his family members. Where the witness is a police source or a cop, further examination and wrongdoing counteraction exercises may get influenced because of lacking insurance gave to them. Different classes of the witness who face terrorizing are the individuals who have been deceived by their own relatives and sexual stalkers, as their individual conditions are exceptionally abnormal and amazing. These kinds of casualties are generally defenceless as they have been hoodwinked, out of blue, by their nearest and believed ones and that is the reason they require most extreme consideration, insurance and help. Obviously, the indictment to a great extent relies on their oral declaration for demonstrating the charges past a sensible uncertainty.²⁰

The danger to the lives of witnesses is one of the essential purposes behind them to withdraw their prior articulations during the preliminary. Aside from these segments, there is nothing in the law to shield observers from outer dangers, actuation or terrorizing. Political weight, self-created dread of police and the lawful framework, nonappearance of dread of the law of prevarication, an unsympathetic law authorization hardware and debasement are a portion of different explanations behind observers turning antagonistic over the span of the preliminary.²¹

The Supreme Court on account of Krishna Mochi v. the State of Bihar saw that society experiences unfair feelings and it similarly endures by wrong indications. Right, now-Supreme Court brought up that one reason might be that

¹⁷Committee on Reforms of Criminal Justice System, headed by Justice Mallimath, Vol.I, at 151.

¹⁸Section 190-195 of Indian Penal Code, 1860

¹⁹Section 118 of Indian Evidence Act, 1872

²⁰Warisha Farasat, Plea for witness protection laws, The Hindu, July 23, 2013, available at <http://www.thehindu.com/opinion/op-ed/a-plea-for-witness-protection-laws/article4944925.ece>(last visited on March28, 2020 at 08:36 pm)

²¹Ibid

they don't have the fearlessness to dismiss against a blamed in light of the fact that for dangers to their lives, all the more so when the guilty parties are constant lawbreakers or high ups in the Government or near force which might be political, efficient or different forces including muscle power.²²

Conditions of Witnesses in India

Our nation India is in critical need of enactment to direct the assurance of the observer, which as of now exists in different nations like the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada and Australia. Resultantly, the observers neither have any lawful cure nor they get appropriately treated. It is presented that the present legitimate framework has underestimated observers totally. Witnesses are gathered to court paying little mind to their money related and individual conditions. Additionally, it may be after numerous long periods of the occurrence of the supposed wrongdoing that he is gathered which fundamentally hamper his capacity to recall important subtleties at the hour of real preliminary. The offices gave to observers in old Hindu law like the sensible sum by method for transport, the reasonable condition in the court and the aware disposition of the officials of the courts towards the observers are mysteriously gone in the advanced criminal equity framework. The Supreme Court while analysing the role of witnesses in the lawbreaker equity framework saw that they assume a fundamental job in the administration of equity and security of observers through authoritative measures can go far in directing a reasonable preliminary. In the event that preliminary is vitiated it gets cleaned and incapacitated. It's never again can establish a reasonable trial.²³

Given this circumstance, the Government wanted to present new arrangements under the Code of Criminal Procedure in 2008 for witness securing observers. The 2008 corrections incorporated a few arrangements identifying with the privileges of casualties and witnesses. Casualties who may likewise be a prime observer in criminal preliminaries have been given some significant rights like the privilege to pay. In any case, it is presented that to a great extent witness are given shallow rights through the alteration. The State government plan, as a team with the Central government, a plan called Victim Compensation Scheme to repay the person in question or his wards who have endured misfortune or injury because of the wrongdoing.²⁴ Further, Section 195A has been embedded in the Criminal Procedure Code to give a chance to the observer or any individual for his sake to record an objection comparable to an offense u/s 195A of the Indian Penal Code.²⁵

²² AIR 2003 SC 886

²³ Vikas Kumar Roorkeval v State of Uttarakhand, (2011) 2 SCC 178

²⁴ Section 357A of Code of Criminal Procedure in 2008

²⁵ Section 195A of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 (inserted in Amendment 2005)

There were sure explicit resolutions accommodating the security of the character of witnesses –

1. Terrorists and Disruptive Activities Act, 1985 (TADA) – This Act through Sec. 13 offered a fastidious usual methodology for the 'identity assurance' of witnesses who were imperilling their lives while affirming in the procedure in a criminal preliminary including the demonstrations culpable under the Act. It was in this manner re-established in 1987 (by means of TADA 1987) and under segment 16 of the new Act, a similar method was referenced. The legitimacy of Section 16 of the Act was maintained by the Supreme Court in *Kartar Singh v. the State of Punjab*.²⁶

2. Anticipation of Terrorism Act, 2002 (POTA) – This Act revoked TADA, 1987. Sec. 30 of the Act accommodated in-camera procedures and security of the character of witnesses. The legitimacy of section 30 was tested in *PUCL v. UOI* wherein the Supreme Court maintained its legitimacy.²⁷

3. The Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Amendment Act, 2004 – POTA was revoked and the Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967, was altered as needs be. Sec.44 of the Act accommodates the assurance of the observers which is indistinguishably worded with Sec. 30 of POTA.

4. Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000 –It gives that no report in any paper, magazine, news sheet or visual made of any request in regards to an adolescent in strife with the law will uncover any kind of subtleties which can distinguish an adolescent in any condition or by any explanation at all.²⁸

There are plenty of cases in which point including the prominent residents. For instance, in cases like *NeelamKatara*, *Jessica Lal* and *Best Bakery* and so forth, key observers turned threatening during the preliminary bringing about the weakening of preliminary method. Idly, it focuses on the absence of a reasonable observer security program in India. Today, undeserving exonerations can be made sure about by a basic method, in particular, by guaranteeing that the primary observer either doesn't turn up or turns antagonistic. In spite of the fact that the Supreme Court has set out that proof of an unfriendly observer should be essentially be treated as being supportive of the charge, still, the preliminary courts think that it's hard to do as such. Given these reasons, without any law or program managing abundant insurance to witnesses, one can't seek after the crime percentage to plunge. Indeed, it will fill in as a protect for crooks who set out to rehash their violations without risk of punishment.²⁹

²⁶ 1994 (3) SCC 569

²⁷ (2003) 10 SCALE 967

²⁸ Section 21 of Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000

²⁹ *National Human Rights Commission v. State of Gujarat* (2009) 6 SCC 767

Credibility of Witnesses

A child witness, whenever discovered skilled to remove, to the realities is a solid one such proof could be the premise of conviction. As it were, even without a vow, the proof of a youngster witness can be viewed as U/s 118 Indian Evidence Act given that such observer can comprehend the appropriate responses. The proof of youngster witness and believability thereof would rely on the conditions of each case. Prior, the measure of deciding the competency of youngster observer when in doubt, is that none could be conceded younger than nine years, not very many under ten.³⁰ But today, no specific age is required practically speaking to render the proof of a kid acceptable. A simple sensible guideline has been received and the competency of kids is currently respected not by their age, yet by the level of comprehension, which they appear to have. A kid might be an equipped observer to give proof in court on the off chance that apparently she can comprehend the inquiries put to her and can offer reasonable responses thereto.³¹

For each reliable witness, it is his ability to comprehend and clarify what he needs to communicate. Declaration of a kid is likewise dependable in the event that he effectively gets it questions and gives normal answers to each such questions.³² Testimony of child witness ought to be acknowledged simply after extraordinary alert and circumspection. When a witness is an individual of delicate years or extraordinary mature age or an individual alarm to test his competency. Essentially, where an witness is a child, the court ought to be an alarm of the need, to choose, regardless of whether vow can be managed. Normally, this fulfilment is to be shown up at, by starter assessment of the observer by the court.³³

The Supreme Court saw that the appealing party has had the option to shake the believability of the observer. No material logical inconsistency on account of the arraignment has been uncovered. Under realities and conditions, the non-assessment of the Investigating Officer, as an observer, is of no result. It has not been indicated what preferences have been caused to the appealing party by such non-assessment.³⁴

In *Jaison V. State of Kerala*³⁵ and in *KuldipYadav and Ors V. State of Bihar*³⁶, the court talked about that proof of onlooker can't be disposed of on the ground that he was indicted and condemned in a criminal case. The revelation of their relationship with the expired, antagonistically, dismissed against the

³⁰ I Phill Evidence, (4) 10th Edn., 8, quoted in Q.E.V Maru, 10.A 207 (211).

³¹ JalwantiLodhin V. State, 1953 p.246: 32 p. 217: 1953 Cr.L.J 1344.

³² Dhani V. State., 1993 Cri. L.J 2712 (Ori).

³³ Narayan KanuDatawale V. State of Maharashtra, 1997 Cri. L.J 1788 (Bom.).

³⁴ Bahadur Naik V. State of Bihar, AIR 2000 SC 1582

³⁵ 2014 (1) KLT (SN) 19; 2014(8) R.C.R (Criminal) 3007

³⁶ 2013 (4) Ker.L..J 45 (Kerela) (D.B).

blamed is by all accounts exceptionally misrepresented, in opposition to one another and not completely confirmed with clinical proof. These errors brought about undermining the validity of the observer. At the end of the day, the indictment has not introduced a genuine form on the greater part of the material parts and hence, the observers and material set on their side doesn't rouse certainty and can't be acknowledged on the assumed worth.

Reasons for Witnesses Turning Hostile

Different reasons exist for the observers to turn threatening, for example, cash, muscle power, risk/terrorizing, prompting, power, compulsion and different methods for allurements and enticement. Significant reasons for threatening vibes were:-

1. Non-appearance of mindfulness

Witness security is required for before removal of cases. Witnesses were normally undermined or harmed or killed before having the option to give declaration in the Court, as there is no law for their security. Consequently, witnesses are denied of any insurance from risk.

2. Option to bail

Option to bail ought to be denied by the state at whatever point there is a risk to a witness or a sensible fear. The charged had information that there is an observer to his demonstration will attempt to dispense with him so the technique doesn't involve him.

3. Inadequate Remuneration

Witnesses who show up in the court have a hazard to their life and their families be that as it may, are not given the sensible costs and compensation for partaking in the criminal courts.

4. Nonattendance of Facilities

Offices given to witnesses are least and inadequate. There are no essential luxuries given to them which could be useful to them, during their stay in the court, before hearing.

5. Normal adjournment

Cases are suspended more than once to dishearten the observer with the goal that he eventually surrenders. Premature delivery of equity emerges when the suspensions are held with no explanation.³⁷

In *Madan Lal v. State of Punjab*, the announcement of a chance observer doesn't move certainty and isn't adequate to base a conviction. In the event that he didn't talk reality under the watchful eye of the court while sworn on pledge conviction can't be founded on the announcement of a purported

³⁷MamtaChaterjee, "Problem of hostile witness", available at <http://www.legalservicesindia.com/article/article/hostile-witnesses-and-efficacy-of-law-1692-1.html> (last accessed on March 28, 2020 at 10:06 pm)

eyewitness.³⁸ Chance observer, proof might be solid or relying upon the conditions and their nearness to see an offence being submitted. At the point when the offence occurred in expansive sunlight and the inhabitants have seen it. Their quality at the spot couldn't be considered unnatural.³⁹

Section 134 of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872 characterizes that "No specific number of witnesses will, regardless, be required for the confirmation of any case." A conviction can be founded on the declaration of a solitary observer, in the event that he is completely dependable. Certification is fundamental when the proof is incomplete. On the off chance that proof is unequivocal and liberated from analysis, and the court is analysed that the observer is dependable and talking reality, at that point, the conviction can be founded distinctly on his proof.⁴⁰

Witness Protection Programme as per Statutory Law

Required arrangements and the orders of law have been commanded by the statutory arrangement.

Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973: The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 clarifies the method in the open court⁴¹, camera trials⁴² and rape.⁴³ The Court needs to avoid the open for the most part or any individual from the court. The court needs to practice its attentiveness in continuing to lead the protection. The general guideline is that the trial was to be held in the open court at the same time, in offences including assault and other affirmed offences, it is the caution of the court to allow access to a specific individual. The Magistrate is compelled by a solemn obligation under the law to hold the camera preliminaries. The proof is to be taken within the sight of the charged. The past affidavit of witnesses and assent of the observer can't make the procedure substantial. Proof in one Criminal case can't be added something extra to another. Proof of a minor who has been explicitly ambushed must record their proof and the blamed ought not to be available, isn't stood up to by the denounced.⁴⁴

The Supreme Court in *Zahira Habibulla Sheik V. State of Gujarat*⁴⁵, case requested a move in setting from Gujarat to Maharashtra. The Criminal code guarantees that if the casualty is of the view that equity would be incomplete, he can get case move to another court.⁴⁶ Enabling the observer or

³⁸2012 (1) RCR (Cr) 17.

³⁹Ramvir v. State of UP 2010 (5) RCR (Cr) 226

⁴⁰Ramesh Krishna MadhusudanNayar V. State of Maharashtra 2008 Cri. L.J. 1023

⁴¹ Sec. 327 Criminal Procedure Code, 1973

⁴² Sec. 327(2) Criminal Procedure Code, 1973

⁴³ Sec.376 of Indian Penal Code

⁴⁴172nd Report of Law Commission (2000).

⁴⁵ 2004 (4) SCC 158

⁴⁶ Sec. 406, 407 Cr.P.C

some other individual to document a grievance in light of the offence secured under IPC for undermining or prompting any individual to give bogus proof.⁴⁷

1. Detainees Examination

The intensity of the Court to give Commission for assessment, as an observer, of any individual, kept or confined in jail and their assessment.⁴⁸

2. Assessment witnesses

All proof over the span of the preliminary or other continuing must be in the nearness of blamed.⁴⁹ A preliminary is vitiated by an inability to look at the observer within the sight of the denounced.

3. Demeanour of witness

At the point when a directing Judge or Magistrate has recorded the proof of a witness while recording he will think material the air of such observer under assessment.⁵⁰ It is commonly dangerous to articulate a sentiment on the believability of the observers until the entire of his proof has occurred.

4. Cross-examination to witnesses

Gatherings to the procedure gave an application recorded as a hard copy that the individual showed up before the justice to be inspected and interviewed in the court where the commission is given. The Magistrate or Court may advance any interrogatory, recorded as a hard copy, coordinating the commission, to think in the event that it is pertinent to the issue, and it will be legitimate for the Magistrate to look at, question and rethink the gathering.⁵¹

5. Proof In absentia

In the event that a charged individual has slipped off, and there is no quick possibility of capturing him, the Court capable to attempt, such individual for the offence grumbled in his nonappearance and may inspect the observers in the interest of the arraignment and record their testimonies. On the off chance that the deponent is dead or unequipped for giving proof or can't be found or his essence can't be obtained immediately, cost or burden which, the situation being what it is of the case, would be absurd.⁵²

6. Material witness

The court may bring any individual as an observer who has not been inspected, reviewed or brought before if his proof has all the earmarks of being fundamental for an equitable choice.⁵³

7. Postponement in trial

⁴⁷ Section 195A Cr.P.C

⁴⁸ Section 271 Cr..P.C, 1973.

⁴⁹ Section 273 Cr..P.C, 1973

⁵⁰ Section 280 Cr..P.C, 1973

⁵¹ Section 287 Cr.P.C

⁵² Section 299 of Cr.P.C

⁵³ Section 311 of Cr.P.C

Assessment of the observer will proceed from the everyday for prior removal of the cases in request or preliminary. The court will limit itself from delaying the procedures except if it records the explanation recorded as a hard copy.⁵⁴

8. Guilty party as an observer

Any individual blamed for an offense under the steady gaze of a Criminal Court will be an equipped observer for the protection and may give proof on pledge to disprove the charges made against him or others at the equivalent trial. The court can't draw any unfriendly surmising's for non-assessment of the denounced as an observer.⁵⁵

9. Open Trial

Open Court is held to ask or attempting any offence to which open approaches yet in an extraordinary case, the official of the court may deny access to an individual or open from entering the court.⁵⁶

Conclusion and Suggestions

Security might be given previously, during as well as after the legal continuing relying upon the sort of the observer or the level of collaboration. Compelling observer insurance enactment ought to preferably include all the three concerned offices – police, government and legal executive. The administration should show a political will to actualize vital Acts, the legal executive can investigate the lawful viewpoints and the execution might be depended to the police. A free observer insurance cell ought to be established and it must organize the arrangement of bogus characters, migration and development. The observers ought to be treated with reasonableness, regard, and poise, and to be liberated from terrorizing, badgering, or misuse, all through the criminal equity process. They ought to approach data on the status of the examination and indictment of wrongdoing. Clinical offices, social administrations, state remuneration, directing, treatment and other help might be given. Right to a quick preliminary and brief and last finish of the case after the conviction and sentence should likewise be guaranteed.⁵⁷

⁵⁴ Section 309 Cr.P.C

⁵⁵ Section 315 of Cr.P.C

⁵⁶ Section 327 Cr.P.C, 1973

⁵⁷ H Suresh, New Law Needed for Witness Protection, 4 Combat Law. (2005), available at <http://www.indiatogether.org/combatlaw/vol4/issue1/witness.htm>(last visited on March 28, 2020 at 10:42 pm)

IMPACT ON MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS AND EMPLOYEE RETENTION IN BEVERAGE INDUSTRY, PUDUCHERRY

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Abstract

Inside the globalized period, every one of the associations is going after having qualified work. The triumph of the association depends on incredible and submitted labourers. Each and every association is giving extraordinarily engaging persuasive segments to hold their labourers and reduction the trimming down. The significance of inspiration in holding the most brilliant capacities can't be over-featured. The showcase concentrate's outrageous target is to find out the important inspirational factors and its effect on delegate support in beverage industry found in puducherry. The entire test proportion of the consider is 330. They consider respondent found that there's a positive and basic connection between Motivational segments and Worker Maintenance among the beverage industry employees. The contemplate too educated that every persuasive variable has the positive and vital effect of employee upkeep in beverage industry, puducherry.

Keywords- Employee Retention, Motivation, Engagement, Leadership, Work Environment, Compensation etc.

Introduction

Employee Retention is a progressing exertion and this is one of the significant duty of the administration to empower the workers as far as improving their expertise levels, understanding their expanded manner of thinking and spurring them. Halepota (2005) recognized from his examination that there were noteworthy inspirational factors, for example, "Prize, Promotion, Recognition from the administration, Challenging work, great working conditions, great work routines that is reasonable move timetable and professional stability. On the opposite, Chiang J. what's more, Canter P. (2008) contended that the capable individuals couldn't proceed in their activity because of work pressure presented to them.

Schuler and Jackson (2006) distinguished that the administration consistently plans for empowering, rousing the current representatives to stick on the associations. Schreuder and Theron (2001) set up in their investigation that the maintenance of committed and gifted workers is because of managers basic as a result of upper hand is rarely subject to the particular information and aptitudes presented by these representatives.

Schreuder and Theron (2001) have credited the versatility idea of gifted workers, holding them turns into a matter of worry to businesses since, in the perspective on Buckingham (2000), their leaving implies a misfortune to the association of its scholarly capital or elusive resources. The significant goal of maintenance is to

forestall and control the loss of centre and equipped representatives from the business substance as this could be an explanation of having an antagonistic impact on focused yield, efficiency and administration conveyance. However, holding top gifts give predicament to the administration controlling the worker's development from one organization to other organization who expected to be a contender.

Antomioni (1999), the measure of exertion, individuals made in their work rely upon how much they feel that their inspirational needs will be fulfilled. Then again, people become de-persuaded on the off chance that they feel something in the association keeps them from accomplishing great results. In this way, the present investigation has been attempted to discover the inspirational components and their effect on worker maintenance among the beverage industry s in puducherry.

Review of Literature

In human life, inspirations are an extraordinary motivation to upgrade productivity in their working environment. Inspiration takes out the lethargic energies of the representatives who have normally had as their inclination.

Petri (1996) distinguished from his examination that there was an inspiration is a huge factor for human conduct and it will improve the individual conduct.

Pinder (1998) distinguished that there is an examination that the inspiration is undetectable, inner and speculative wonders that analyst, in this manner, needs to depend on set up ideas to control them in the valuation of noticeable indications of work inspiration.

Chaminade (2007) found that work inspiration is required to show in both attitudinal and conduct measures, though as far as an objective setting hypothesis the essential indication of inspiration is social.

Michael, S. and, Chipunza C. (2009) distinguished that preparation and advancement fundamentally impact representative maintenance in their exploration. Casual preparing is very likely the key preparing representative can get and it incorporates the total exposures of at working environment.

Chew & Chan, (2008) propelled in their investigation on workers' maintenance that it is a major test all around. The impacts are because of the enormous expense of the choice procedure, misfortunes of efficiency during the change time frame, the plausible loss of business openings, poor client compatibilities just as the shrouded expense of lost profitability and time misfortune have caused organizations to notice the extent of maintenance.

Luna-Arocas and Camps (2008) accept that workers of associations are a genuine resource. Maintenance of workers is influencing the general accomplishment of any association. Worker maintenance is one of the most basic issues looked by hierarchical directors in light of the deficiency of gifted work, financial development and high representative turnover. The essential point of maintenance is to keep the loss of able representatives from the association as this could adversary affect efficiency and administration conveyance. Be that as it may, maintenance of high performing workers has gotten all the more trying for supervisors as this class of representatives every now

and again move starting with one occupation then onto the next as they are being pulled in by more than each association in turn.

Michael S. (2008), an aggressive compensation bundle is the most basic persuasive variable that adds to holding representatives in the association. Top entertainers to be perceived by encouraging honour like "Accomplishment Awards". It will spur the workers for proceeding with his vitality level for guaranteeing future execution. At the point when the prizes are given to the representatives who accomplished greatness, it could turn into a significant instrument for the duration of the ideal objective. In the working environment, outer prizes incorporate motivations, attendant services, vacations and other fiscal types of remunerations. Chiefs regularly utilize such outside remunerations as sparks.

Michael, S. (2009) featured in their investigation that worker's turnover of the association is because of unsatisfactory employing rehearses, administrative methodology; absence of acknowledgement, absence of focused remuneration framework, Unhealthy working environment situations, the entangled methodology of the work area. Others are comprehensive of lacking enthusiasm for his work, absence of employer stability, absence of advancement and thankfulness and insufficient ability improvement process among others. These are inherent and outward persuasive components, which can help administrators to impact worker maintenance in their associations. The issue, in any case, is that supervisors have flopped in distinguishing and appropriately utilizing these factors as a maintenance system and in this manner bringing about the predominant high turnover rate in the associations.

Elements of Employee Motivation

According to Wheelhouse (1989), there are scarcely any components, which are fundamental needs to the representatives for their exhibition and may not act naturally helpers, if the administration disregards these variables it will give the negative effect on the persuasive procedure. The free factors that are basically analyzed in this investigation are reward, acknowledgement, advancement, security, compensation, preparing and improvement, intriguing work and workplace.

Employee Engagement:

The completely connected with workers won't be veered off for some other dreadful occupations and concentrate towards accomplishing destinations of the association. The representative's ability level to be satisfactorily utilized seriously. Worker commitment is the representatives' degree of responsibility and contribution of their associations and qualities. They will be exceptionally self-persuaded and objective arranged with a powerful urge to accomplish to an ever-increasing extent. The greater part of the experts has given more consideration to worker commitment, as it gave helpful results for the advancement of associations (Park and Gursoy, 2012). Commitment could be conceptualized as a high excitement position, which contributes association and vitality to a representative (Bakker, et al, 2011). The commitment procedure would persuade to arrive at expanded occupation execution, high fulfilment in their activity, customer fulfilment, more secure workplace and benefit to the association.

Workplace and Culture:

It covers generally work-life balance, augmenting vocation yearnings and the probability of preparing in a similar association. Nature needs to help the two different ways of physical and mental. The work spot to be free from poisons and medical issues. Mentally the representatives ought not to confront any dull. There is no utilization arranging inspiration for superior, while representatives are exasperated by not having the correct quality and quantum of gear they requirement for their work (Bowey, 2005). Therefore, supervisors should ensure their staff have adequate space, apparatuses, data innovation frameworks, and materials they require for the activity. The board is then asked to get ready ahead of time all the hardware as new representatives need. Supervisors ought to likewise grip a sound (physically and rationally) working condition. The learning procedure doesn't have any restrictions as the associations are confronting a lot of changes in business monetarily and in fact too. Preparing process assumes a significant job during the time spent inspiration. It bolsters the representatives from bombing because of an absence of refreshed information and attempting to delineate the ability level. Preparing can be formal, for example at a class, or casual, for example at work.

Authority and Supervision:

People participate in a decent association and leaves from the terrible chief, this is demonstrated in many contextual analyses. A representative goes to the goal of stopping at whatever point he faces the issue in his activity or in different conditions. It is the center duty of the director to rouse the colleagues and to guarantee that they are satisfied with their employments and offer great compatibility among themselves. Eisenberger and Associates (1990) state that the workers' view of the association is simply founded on the association with their chiefs. McNeese (1995) saw in his examination on Leadership conduct that there is a huge positive connection between relationship and efficiency. Griffeth, R.W., Hom, P.W. 2000 recommended that the representatives' fulfilment, the nature of the trades, frequencies and approach by the chiefs are straightforwardly identified with worker maintenance.

Pay and Benefits:

It is dominating thought in HR rehearses in light of the fact that it is a substantial motivating force for workers for their administrations and necessary to be pursued as it is a principal prerequisite according to the guidelines. Wheelhouse (1989) expressed "Payday ought to be probably the most joyful days of the week", it ought to be conveyed to workers on schedule and in a fitting way. These days the vast majority of the organizations move the pay to the representatives through the bank on the last working day of the organization in a month. However, there ought not to be any deviation in the compensation payment process. Petcharak (2002) expressed that individuals are spurred by broadening riches in light of various reasons; the need to give the necessities of life rouses the vast majority. According to Michael S. (2008), an aggressive compensation bundle is the most basic persuasive variable that adds to holding representatives in the association. Top entertainers to be perceived by encouraging honour like "Accomplishment Awards". It will spur the workers for

proceeding with his vitality level for guaranteeing future execution (Nidhi Srivatsava, 2015). At the point when the prizes are given to the representatives who accomplished greatness, it could turn into a significant instrument for the duration of the ideal objective. In the working environment, outer prizes incorporate motivations, attendant services, vacations and other fiscal types of remunerations. Chiefs regularly utilize such outside remunerations as sparks. In any case, Herzberg contends that inspiration originates from work itself and these outer prizes are simply fulfilling or disappoints. When workers are inspired, they will have the option to satisfy the clients' needs and together accomplish the organization's objectives (Bowen, 2000). The prize is the most significant persuasive ascribes that add to holding representatives in the association (Michael, S. 2008).

Objectives of Study

- To observe the motivational factors affecting the employee retention among the employees in beverage industry.
- To recommend a retention technique to arrive at high-level retention in beverage industry.

Methodology

The present investigation's centre target is to determine the significant variables of employees and its effect on worker maintenance of the beverage industry in puducherry. The investigation utilized both auxiliary and essential information. The information was utilized to accomplish the above destinations. The investigation was directed in puducherry, India. The example for this examination comprised of 350 representatives drawn dependent on straightforward arbitrary inspecting from drink workers in puducherry. Out of 350 examples, 20 examples were dismissed because of insufficient data gave by the workers. At last, 330 respondents are utilized for investigation. The statistic information of the employees was additionally gathered through essential overviews, for example, age, sexual orientation, educational qualifications, marital status and branch of working. The essential information gathered from the objective respondents were examined utilizing elucidating, Pearson relationship and various relapse examinations. The information was investigated utilizing SPSS 21 adaptation.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Table-1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	304	92.13
Female	26	7.87
Age		
Up to 30 Years	170	51.51
31- 45 Years	130	39.39
46 - 58 Years	30	9.09
Marital Status		
Married	231	70.00

Un married	99	30.00
Educational Qualification		
Up to HSC	40	12.12
Under Graduate	87	26.36
Post Graduate	32	9.69
I.T.I.	60	18.18
Diploma	80	24.24
Professional	24	7.0
Others	7	2.12
Department		
Accounts	25	7.57
Logistics	27	8.18
Maintenance	30	9.09
Production	149	45.15
Quality	60	18.18
Stores	23	6.96
Others	16	4.84
Total	330	100

Table-1

1. The demographic profile of the respondents shows that 92.13% were male and 7.87% were female.
2. The age of the respondents were 51.51% less than 30 years and 39.39% were between 31 to 45 and 9.09% were 46 to 58 years.
3. Marital status of the respondents 70.00% respondents were married and 30.00% were single.
4. The educational qualification of the respondents indicates 26.36% were under graduates; 24.24% were diploma holders; 18.18% were ITI; 12.12% were up to higher secondary; 10.6% were postgraduates; 9.69% were professionals and 2.12% was others.
5. The respondents working in various departments shows that 45.15% were from production department; 18.18% working in Quality department; 9.09% from Maintenance department; 8.18% were from logistics department; 7.57% working in accounts department; 6.96% were from stores department and 4.84% working in other departments.

Table – 2 Mean and Standard deviation for employee motivational factors and employee retention

Motivational Factors	N	Mean	SD
Work Environment and Culture	330	3.63	0.678
Leadership and Supervision	330	3.52	0.662
Employee Engagement	330	4.32	0.722
Compensation and Benefits	330	4.35	0.712

Table-2

Shows that Mean and Standard deviation for employee’s motivational factors and employee retention among the beverage employees in Chennai city. It is noted from the above table, among the motivational factors Compensation and Benefits (4.35) has the highest mean value followed by Employee Engagement (4.32), Work Environment and Culture (3.63) and the least significant factor is Leadership and Supervision (3.52).

H_0 : There is no correlation between motivational factors and employee retention among the employees of beverage industry in puducherry.

Table-3: Relationship between Employee Motivational Factors and Employee Retention

Motivational Factors		Employee Retention
Work Environment and Culture	Pearson Correlation	0.763
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000**
	N	330
Leadership and Supervision	Pearson Correlation	0.710
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000**
	N	330
Employee Engagement	Pearson Correlation	0.810
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000**
	N	330
Compensation and Benefits	Pearson Correlation	0.863
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000**
	N	330

Table-3 emphasizes that Karl Pearson correlation between motivational factors of employees and retention of employees. It is identified from the above table there is encouraging and significant relationship between compensation and employee retention r value is 0.863 and p value is 0.000, employee engagement and employee retention r value is 0.810 and p value 0.000, working environment and culture and employee retention r value is 0.763 and p value 0.000, leadership and supervision and employee retention is r value 0.710 and p value 0.000. It is concluded that in all the factors, the p value is less than 0.01; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level of significant. Hence, it is concluded that there is positive correlation between motivational factors and employee retention among the beverage employees in puducherry.

Regression Model

The equation of multiple regressions on this present study is generally built around two sets of variable, namely

1. Dependent variables (Employee Retention) and
2. Independent variables (Employee Engagement, Work Environment and Culture, Leadership and Supervision and Compensation and Benefits).

The basic objective of using regression equation on this study is to make the researcher more effective at describing, understanding, predicting, and controlling the stated variables.

Regression equation for Employee retention on the employee motivational factors:

$$Y_i = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4$$

Where Y is the dependent variable:

Dependent variable	Employee retention (Y)
Independent Variables	: Compensation and Benefits (X1)
	: Employee Engagement (X2)
	: Work Environment (X3)
	: Leadership and Supervision (X4)
R Square Value	: 0.768, Value: 20.512 , P Value: 0.000**

Table – 4: Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
(Constant)	1.360	12.997	0.000**
Compensation and Benefits	0.074	6.701	0.000**
Employee Engagement	0.067	6.668	0.000**
Work Environment and Culture	0.065	6.182	0.000**
Leadership and Supervision	0.062	3.292	0.001**

The Coefficient of Determination R-square measures the goodness-of-fit of the estimated Sample Regression Plane (SRP) in terms of the proportion of the variation in the dependent variables explained by the fitted sample regression equation. Thus, the value of R square is 0.768 simply means that about 76.8% of the variation in adjustment is explained by the estimated SRP that uses Compensation and Benefits, Employee Engagement, Work Environment and Culture and Leadership and Supervision as the independent variables and R square value is significant at 1 % level.

The multiple regression equation is

$$Y = 1.360 + 0.076X_1 + 0.067X_2 + 0.065X_3 + 0.062X_4$$

Here the coefficient of X1 is 0.076 represents the partial effect of Compensation and Benefits, holding Employee retention as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive the adjustment score would increase

by 0.076 for every unit increase in Compensation and Benefits and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. The coefficient of X₂ is 0.067 represents the partial effect of Employee engagement on Adjustment, holding employee retention as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive the adjustment score would increase by 0.067 for every unit increase in employee engagement and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. The coefficient of X₃ is 0.065 represents the partial effect of work environment and culture holding employee retention as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive the adjustment score would increase 0.065 for every unit increase in work environment and culture and this coefficient value is significant at 1%. It is noted from the above table 4 the coefficient of X₄ is 0.062 represents the partial effect of Leadership and supervision holding employee retention as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive the adjustment score would increase 0.062 for every unit increase in leadership and supervision and this coefficient value is significant at 1%.

Implication and Suggestion

1. The scientist gives the accompanying proposals to improve representative maintenance by filling the holes in the persuasive procedure in the beverage industry.
2. The beverage industry is an occasional consequently inspiration is required for nonstop commitment of the representatives.
3. On evaluating the ongoing specialized progression, the beverage industry develops with rocket speed. Truth be told, it underpins for improvement of GDP of India. So as to create and to continue the developing beverage industry division, the four fundamental elements of Employee Engagement, Work Environment and Culture, Leadership and Supervision and Compensation and Benefits are affecting the worker maintenance to be focused by the beverage industry.
4. It is energetically proposed to fuse the maintenance of colleagues among the directors. Listening society and correspondence to be created, Conducive workplace and adaptability will inspire employees to forestall stopping goals. Henceforth, the persuasive components empower the workers to proceed with their residency in a similar industry.

Conclusion

It is seen from the examination, there are four transcendent inspirational variables were influencing the worker maintenance among the employees of the beverage industry at puducherry. The four essential components are to be specific Compensation and Benefits, Employee Engagement, Work Environment and Culture and Leadership and Supervision. The aftereffect of the investigation found that the most noteworthy persuasive factor among the employee in beverage industry is the compensation and Benefits pursued by Employee Engagement, Work Environment and Culture and Leadership and Supervision. There is a positive and huge connection between persuasive components and employees maintenance. The conjectured model is fit. The four inspirational variables Compensation and Benefits, Employee Engagement, Work Environment and Culture and Leadership and Supervision have a positive and critical impact on worker maintenance.

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MCDONALDIZATION AND CONSUMERISM IN THE CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY

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Abstract

Recent sensational developments in the transnational issues of capital flow, individuals, products, data, and culture have transformed the contemporary world. The globalization of society may result either in a pattern toward homogeneity of regular codes and practices, or situations in which numerous societies interface to make a sort of pastiche or heterogeneity. The pattern toward homogeneity is frequently connected with cultural imperialism. The dynamics of universalisation, homogenisation versus heterogeneity, and other features of global society have influenced life. Life in global society, information society, and consumer society has been made great, with much technological development in many domains in society. The concept of “the McDonaldization of society” was discussed by Ritzer (2011) in his book entitled *The McDonaldization of Society*, which includes ideas from human science, management, and economics aspects to give a significant comprehension of modern society. McDonald’s is attempting to standardise and homogenise different parts of the world; in that capacity, it is a globalising power. McDonaldization can be viewed as an illustration of either the globalisation or glocalisation. Consumerism can display the individual’s well-being and happiness that depends to a substantial degree on the level of individual consumption, especially on the purchase of goods and services. The thought is not just that well-being relies on a way of life above some edge. This essay includes the dimensions of the McDonaldization; the main characteristics of consumerism, and influences in the society. Lastly, I will discuss the impact of McDonaldization and consumerism, particularly on our daily lives.

Keywords : McDonaldization, consumerism

McDonaldization

The first dimension of McDonaldization is efficiency. The functioning of a McDonaldized system depends on efficiency, or the discovery and execution of an ideal approach to do virtually everything. Hence, the fast-food eatery itself is a more efficient method for acquiring a meal than setting it up at home from a several raw ingredients. Later, the utilisation of the drive-through

window is demonstrated to be more efficient than dining inside a restaurant. All activities are efficiently organised by the employees, and the same is valid for the things done by customers in the eateries. Despite the fact that the fast-food industry did not create the desire for efficiency in the public eye, it has assisted with transforming it into a widespread reality in regular life. The streamlined procedure of McDonalidization has spread to different restaurants in this industry. As an example, As an example, Burger King and Domino's aim to get customers in and out as quickly as possible. And such restaurant practices are not the only manifestation; the frozen food industry also sprang up as an aftereffect of this interest in acceleration. Consuming fewer calories and exercise has been influenced by McDonalidization. Books on dieting now guarantee alternate ways to weight reduction, pills are sold for weight loss, and diet centres offer instant prepackaged food. Many other areas of society that have been influenced by McDonalidization are the shopping, university education, healthcare services, and entertainment domains (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011).

Ritzer utilises the term calculability to portray the second dimension of McDonalidized society like the United States of America: stressing quantity over quality. The accentuation on quantity in fast food eateries prompts diminished quality for the customers. However, customers are not, by any means, the only individuals who experience the ill effects of the restaurants making progress toward quantity rather than quality. There is an accentuation in the McDonalidized framework on calculability—on things that can be tallied and evaluated. This accentuation on quantity tends to be accompanied by a de-accentuation on quality (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011).

Predictability is the third dimension of McDonalidized frameworks. The settings, the sustenance, and the behaviour of the workers are much the same from time to time or from place to place. For instance, the French fries are predictable, just like the “marquee” behind the counter to help customers in putting in their requests. This predictability guarantees that workers act similarly and that purchasers feel safe, whatsoever they eat and anywhere they eat it. At the point when customers walk into a McDonald's at any place on the planet, they will get a similar experience, paying little mind to their location. The workers will be wearing the same outfits and address the client with the same essential responses. The same tedious tasks build productivity, as well as empower organizations to create reliably the same items every time, in this way making the workers' duties predictable (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011).

Predictability and McDonalidization have massively influenced the film industry in the United States. The customers' requirement for predictability in a McDonalidized society has led to a critical increment in pictures with unimaginative plots and films with different sequels. Ritzer utilises films like The Ring, Spiderman, Saw, The Matrix, Shrek, and Mission Impossible to

epitomise current films that have brought forth different continuations. It appears that the customers feel better with motion pictures that are not unique. Another way that the film industry has to yield to predictability is the rating framework that is connected to all films. Predictability has influenced how individuals living in a McDonaldized society go about their shopping. Many people now do their shopping in shopping centres, which are loaded with McDonaldized shops that offer the same predictable items in the majority of their stores all throughout the world (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011).

The control is the fourth dimension of McDonaldization. There is a propensity in McDonaldized frameworks to apply this dimension over individuals, for the most part through the utilization of nonhuman technologies (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011). This implies that a procedure of “de-skilling” is ceaselessly occurring, whereby human aptitudes are being detracted from workers and non-human technologies are being incorporated. Thus, for instance, it is the modern French fry machines themselves, and not the humans, that choose when the fries are superbly cooked and should be lifted out of the hot oil. When it is monetarily and innovatively feasible, the logical aftereffect of this procedure is to replace human specialists with mechanical robots. As per Ritzer, the non-human technological innovation is controlling workers as well as consumers. McDonald’s non-human technology enhances control over the workers, ensuring that customers are getting precisely what they need each time they put in an order. Ritzer discusses US aircraft and how each moment of employees’ work on the clock must be represented. When you think about a pilot and the amount of control he or she has of a plane, it would be a really difficult task. Ritzer (2008) clarifies how despite what might be expected, pilots’ employments have been McDonaldized by loading up PCs that fundamentally run the plane between the takeoff and arrival of the plane. To put it plainly, most occupations are controlled by a system that is set up (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011). The bureaucracy offers numerous advantageous points, and it also experiences what Ritzer portrays as the irrationality of rationality (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011). Administration can make a dehumanising place for a man to work in. Beside the dehumanising impact, there are a few different irrationalities. Organisations may become inefficient when there is an excess of regulation. Also, administrations can become unusual as workers become foggy about what they should do and customers do not receive the administration that they anticipate. In a McDonaldized society, customer service is getting to be institutionalised and drained of any genuine cordiality. Thus, it is getting to be ineffective. Another case is that individuals know fast food isn’t useful and good for their health, yet despite everything, they eat it, in light of the fact that food is effective, cheap, and fast.

The idea of globalisation is that worldwide institutions and establishments are brought into the nearby community. McDonaldization can be viewed as globalisation. Globalisation is nothing but the most straightforward route for organisations to grow in light of the fact that they make everything the same, in each area, and the business sector is the same. Therefore, the procedure of McDonaldization is spread on a worldwide scale. McDonald's and other fast-food eateries are viewed as titan multinationals that come into different countries to bring institutionalised foods and procedures that mean nothing to the people in the local community. McDonaldization can bring neighbourhood restaurants to change to end up more like McDonald's and spread the procedures of McDonaldization to the other parts of the world (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011). Because the local communities have the capacity to change the way that things are done, they can view the McDonaldization forms as their own. McDonald's attempts to adjust itself in numerous ways to be viewed as a major part of the local society, as could reasonably be expected. Hence, in this way, it can be seen as the globalisation of something. Despite the fact that the essential procedures and menu may remain, McDonald's tries to tweak its menus in light of neighbourhood tastes, inclinations, and customs (Ritzer, 2008 & 2011).

Consumerism

The contemporary society can also be referred to as consumer society. In many cases, the terms consumption and consumerism are used as equivalent synonyms. Consumption is regularly considered to incorporate the buying, use, and transfer of consumer goods. The growth of wealth in numerous parts of the world and across several social strata has driven analysts to refer to the rise of a consumer society in which individuals are depicted as having an extensive variety of choices in a broad range of consumer and services, identity, and social inclusion (Smart, 2010). Consumerism can display the individual's well-being and happiness that depends to a substantial degree on the level of individual consumption, especially on the purchase of goods and services. Consumerism became a social, cultural, and economic order in the society, encouraging a desire to acquire goods and services in greater amounts. The dynamics of consumption are enhancing inequalities in the society. We consume a wide range of resources and items today, having more than essential needs to include luxury items and technological developments to attempt to enhance effectiveness. All through history, we have constantly looked to discover approaches to make our lives easy to live. Consumerist procedures reflect the opportunities and limitations of modernity (Smart, 2010).

Consumption can be viewed as an institutional field. It displays how consumption bridges financial and social institutions, major changes in social structure, and discourses. Innovations, philosophies, and delivery frameworks

create consumption spaces in an institutional structure moulded by the main social gatherings. The basic structural changes in the economic sector, infrastructure, and society develop a system of mass consumption, while the changes in values, attitudes, and behaviour of an individual lead to consumer culture in the society. The consumer culture develops and works with the corporate economy (Smart, 2010). Mass consumption is regarded as an institutional field due to the interconnectedness of financial and social institutions focused on the creation of things for individual demand. Contemplating the institutional field requires investigation of consumer products, commercial enterprises, and sites; developing both the devouring subject and aggregate identity on the part of consumption; and historical movement toward a consumer society. Ethnographic exploration, qualitative studies, and historical analysis demonstrate a global consumer culture encouraged by media and advertising professionals yet subject to diverse regional interpretations (Smart, 2010).

There are numerous different factors involved in the development of the new method for consumption. The booming economy, particularly the sensational expansion in the 1990s as reflected in the surprising upturn in the money markets and an insignificant unemployment rate, has left huge numbers of individuals with phenomenal measures of disposable salary. For such individuals, consumption, particularly shopping, has become a major type of amusement. Progressively, numerous individuals have sufficient time to spend their huge salaries (Ritzer, 2010). For instance, their life expectancy is enhancing in the life cycle, which emphasises, to a vast degree, consumption. As a result of the booming economy, an expanding number of retirees have the fortitude to be dynamic consumers. In a consumer culture, the aspects of the demographic, geographic, and social structure reflect individual identity. The consumer culture shapes the expressions of collective identity like ethnicity, holidays, occasions, and national or transnational citizenship. A main structural change like the fall of communism in Eastern Europe, or the shift of socialism to a market economy in countries like Russia and China, has led to consumer society in many countries of the world (Ritzer, 2010).

Ferguson (1998) pointed out the five structural factors based on the concept of cultural field. They are a) social and social changes; b) new consumption sites; c) new rules of gastronomy; d) development of specialisations; and e) network of producers and consumers (Ferguson, 1998; Zukin, & Maguire, 2004). To start with, social and social changes inclining toward democratisation fortified the middle-class interests and value-added culinary procedures. Second, new sites like restaurants and food courts for consumption emerged in the community. Third, the publication of cookbooks, the texts of gastronomy, and restaurant reviews came along. Fourth, the

development of food specialties in gastronomy occurred. Finally, the development of networks of consumers and producers made social prestige for the new type of consumption in the society.

The sociological theories of consumerism can be classified into three classes like a) structural approaches; b) individual approaches; and c) social practices approaches (Kennedy, & Krogman, 2008). The structural methodology offers important ways to deal with evaluating the political economy and power bases that encourage consumerism. The individual approach supports a grant that unloads the situational, social, and mental instruments of consumerism. The social practices methodology concentrates on the ways of life and routines that stifle our consciousness of our patterns of utilization and consumerism. Basic to all structural approaches that deal with consumerism is a thought of the influence of substantial social institutions, such as political institutions like the legislature and financial institutions like corporations and trade institutions. Sociologists assume that modern capitalism promotes consumerism (Kennedy, & Krogman, 2008). Juliet Schor pointed out that data about the structure of work and leisure time in capitalist society describe the growth of consumerism. New means of consumption and consumption spaces exist in a consumer society (Kennedy & Krogman, 2008). Baudrillard analyses the consumer society and reprimands the market all the more, by and large developing on the alienation of Marx's work and the structuralism of Levi-Strauss to demonstrate how products are progressively purchased for their symbolic worth (Kennedy & Krogman, 2008). McDonald's and Disney themes can be referred to as a new means of consumption and cathedrals of consumption. Citizens in modern capitalist society are encouraged to reinvent themselves ceaselessly, disposing of old objects and obtaining new ones; that leads the consumerism cycle in the society. I have many experiences of McDonaldization of department stores, shopping malls, and gas stations in my area. Because of McDonaldization, they became streamlined and allowed me buy products quickly and efficiently, without any wastage of my quality time and resources. I see the McDonaldization of the educational system in Massey University, where the students are quantified by their grade point average (GPA) and their GPA positions with respect to other classmates. The university is delivering results and other academic material efficiently, directly to the students' mail. I have experiences of McDonaldization of entertainment like Netflix, which delivers movies directly to my home, where I can enjoy them with my family members and friends.

I used to go shopping and have dinner in a restaurant like a McDonald's restaurant in my area. As a consumer, I purchased the best quality shirts, jeans, and trousers at the best prices in the shopping malls. As a runner, I know precisely what features I want in a running shoe. I performed thorough research in footwear shops in Pine Centre Mall, The Warehouse Ltd Westgate Extra

Store and Farmers Westgate in Massey, and finally, I landed on the Warehouse Ltd Westgate Extra for Nike running shoes. I selected Nike shoes over Puma and Reebok shoes in the store. I bought a bright shoe and was pleased with the two-toned colour pattern. I got this Nike running shoe for discount prices on Waitangi Day. I usually had pizza and burgers offered buy one, get one free at McDonald's restaurant on the weekend in the shopping malls. Sometimes, on Sundays, national holidays, or weekend holidays, after reviewing the offers and discounts, I used to order pizza and drinks for home delivery and made my payment with Internet banking. The information revolution and technological developments facilitated me to be a sensible consumer with happiness.

Conclusion:

To sum up, McDonaldization is an economic model and process influencing life in many ways. Due to McDonaldization of the society, the public is addicted to fast, convenient, and predictable products and services in many domains of life. People enjoy the comfort of the rationalisation and the predictability of McDonaldization. In many contexts, McDonaldization is a means of consumption. In the consumer society, structural and social practices and individual models encourage consumerism and facilitate well-being and happiness. In many situations, McDonaldization and consumerism directly and indirectly influence the quality of life.

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SURVEY OF OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY AMONGST SCHOOL CHILDREN AGED 10 - 15 YEARS OF TUMKURU

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to conduct the survey of overweight and obesity in school going children aged 10 to 15 years of Tumkuru. Total 400 girls and boys were selected from different school of Tumkuru. The study further delimited to western part of Tumkuru. Total 200 (50%) girls and 200 (50%) boys were surveyed for the study. Height and weight were measured and BMI was calculated. Overweight and obesity was assessed by BMI for age. The 85th and 95th centiles of BMI for age and sex based on International curves have been recommended as cut off points to identify overweight and obesity. The results found that total 32% girl and 23 % boy subjects were found overweight and 21.5% girls and 19.5% boys were reported as obese in the study.

Keywords: BMI, Over Weight and Obese.

Introduction

Body Mass Index (BMI) is a number calculated from a person's weight and Height. BMI is a reliable indicator of body fatness for people. BMI does not measure body fat directly, but research has shown that BMI correlates to direct measures of body fat, such as underwater weighing and dual energy x-ray absorptiometry (DXA). BMI can be considered an alternative for direct measures of body fat. Additionally, BMI is an inexpensive and easy-to-perform method of screening for weight categories that may lead to health problems".

In India, under nutrition attracted the focus of health workers, as childhood obesity was rarely seen. But over the past few years, childhood obesity is increasingly being observed with the changing lifestyle of families with increased purchasing power, increasing hours of inactivity due to television, video games and computers have replaced outdoor games and other social activities. Television is major cause. Research indicates that children eat junk foods high in fats, sugar, and carbohydrates while playing video and computer-based games, united with a lack of physical activities. The World Health Organization has described obesity as one of today's most neglected public health problems. Following the increase in adult obesity, the proportions

of children and adolescents who are overweight and obese have also been increasing. Globally, an estimated 10 per cent of school-aged children, between 5 and 17 yr of age, are overweight or obese. The obesity causes the high health risks including diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, osteoarthritis and cancers. Obesity affects both the mental and physical health. The potential medical complications like hypertension, coronary artery disease, diabetes Mellitus and psychological issues of depression, poor self-image, and difficulties in both the home and social environment. Obesity problem in children is main focus of parents as well as teachers. There are multiple causes of being overweight. Fatness is rooted in genetic, biological, behavioural and cultural factors. Normally children become obese when they take more calories than the body burns up. Today's parents are quite busy in their professional career and have less time to prepare nutritious meal for their school going children. Children become habitual to fast food because these foods are easily accessible and they enjoy eating with friends. New research published in the International Journal of Obesity notifies that obesity doesn't affect a child's health but it can also have damaging effect on their education and ability to learn. Overweight children are isolated and feel awkward in many situations and it directly affects their studies.

BMI: Body mass index a useful technique for categorizing people with respect to their degree of body fat. The body mass index is simply the ratio of the body weight (kilograms; Kg) divided by height squared (Meater^2). BMI clearly indicate a person under weight, overweight, obese, and normal body weight.

BODY: A collection particulars considered as a system, “a body of law”, a body of doctrine”, a body of precedents.

MASS: Measure of how much “stuff” something as. Mass determines the inertia of an object and how much gravitational force it exerts another object.

INDEX: A numerical scale used to compare variables with one another or with some reference number.

UNDER WEIGHT: According the BMI weight status categories anyone BMI below 18.5 would be considered as Underweight.

OVER WEIGHT: According to the BMI weight status categories anyone with a BMI over 25 would be classified as overweight.

OBESE: According to the BMI weight status categories anyone with a BMI over 30 would be classified as obese. Defined as a more serious degree of over weight; the cut off point for obesity may be set in terms of percent body fat or in terms of some measure of total body weight.

NORMAL WEIGHT: According to the BMI weight status categories anyone with a BMI above 18.5 to below 25.5 would be classified as normal.

Methods

The subject (N=400) were selected from government high school of 8 to 10th standard aged from 10 to 15 years of Tumkuru city by random sampling technique. Height and weight were measured and BMI was calculated. Overweight and obesity was assessed by BMI for age. The 85th and 95th centiles of BMI for age and sex based on International curves have been recommended as cut off points to identify overweight and obesity.

Results

Table 1 Classification of Normal, Overweight And Obese Students

Years	Boys (200)			Girls (200)		
	Normal	Over Weight	Obese	Normal	Over Weight	Obese
10-11	60	15(25%)	13 (21.66%)	34	15 (41.66%)	07 (20.58%)
12-13	30	14(46%)	08 (26.66%)	30	27 (90%)	17 (56.66%)
14-15	25	17 (68%)	18 (72%)	29	22 (75.86%)	19 (65.51%)
Overall	115	46 (40%)	39 (33.91%)	93	64 (68.81%)	43 (46.23%)

The 25% of the total strength of boys were found overweight and the 21.66% were found obese. In girls 41.66% and 20.58% were found overweight and obese respectively in 10-11 years. In 12-13 year boys 46% overweight and 26.66% obese students were reported. While in girls overweight and obese were noted 90% and 56.66% respectively in same age group. In 14-15 years, age group prevalence of highest overweight and obese boys was found (68% and 72% respectively) in selected samples. Children's daily physical activity and inactive time were compared between obese children by t-test 6.4 and it was founded highly significant. Further the result shows that the television watching average time in normal is less than 35 minutes and in the other two groups it is more than 1 hrs. The result of parent education is also differing in the normal, overweight and obese. More than 76% Parents of normal subject are educated till HSC level. In the other hand the obese and overweighed children's parents were educated highly but working.

Recommendations for controlling obesity and overweight

- ❖ Involving in regular physical activities especially aerobic activities, like swimming, cycling, walking jogging, and playing games (more than 30 minutes). etc
- ❖ Lead of life style improvements.
- ❖ Consume required optimum calorie of nutrition.
- ❖ Additionally, the most people recommended that **Yoga and yogic lifestyle** to be followed.(which helps to burn calories from the fat)

Conclusions

The prevalence of overweight and obesity in children of school in Tumkuru city was high. Lack of physical activity is a main cause of obesity in

children. The inclination towards a sedentary lifestyle such as lack of physical activity, watching TV and playing game on mobile was evident amongst the school children. Further it is advised that obesity can be prevent by adopting healthy life style including the eating pattern, increasing physical activities and decreasing sedentary activities.

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orEku ea;ks dh ikl bcdrk

MWewhkk xlnkj

I g vtpk;] I l drr]

jkt dh; clxM+Lukrdlkj egkfo|ky;

MhMokuk

I kj

Hkkjrh; n"ku ey : i l s nks oxka ea fohkfr gš vkfLrd n"ku rFkk ukfLrd n"kuA on ds nf'V&fclnq l s thou n"ku dh 0; k[; k djus okys n"ku vkfLrd dgs tkrs gš rFkk rfnrj n"ku ka dh ukfLrd l k k i MhA ; ksx n"ku vkfLrd n"ku ka ds vlr xzr gš ošnd okle; ea ; ksx ds rüo fc[kMš i Mš gš ; ksx "kkL= dks nk"kuud : i inku djus dk Jš egf'kz iratfy dks gš 0; kdj .k "kkL= ea "; q-tj-; ksxs rFkk **; q-t- l ek/kkS" , d h nks /kkrq; feyrh gš ; gk; **; q-t- l ek/kkS" l s fu' l lu ; ksx "kCn xfgr gš iratfy }kjk mifn'V ofÜk fujksk okyh ; ksx & l k/kuk fo; ksx & i /kku gksus l s ; gk; l a ksx kRed ; ksx dks ugha fy; k x ; k gš fpÜkofÜk; ka ds fujksk dks ; ksx dgrs gš fpÜk f=xqkkRed gš D; kšd mudh dkj .kHkr idfr f=xqkkRedk gš l Uo] jtl - , oa rel } ; s rhu xqk gš fpÜk ds fo'k; kdj ij .kke dks ofÜk dgrs gš fpÜk , d egkl epz gš ftl ea ofÜk : ih mnake rjxs mBrh , oa yhu gsrh jgrh gš fpÜk dh ikp ofÜk; k; gš & i ek.k] foi ; }] fodYi] fodYi funk , oa LefrA ofÜk&fujksk dk vFZ ofÜk; ka dk vHkko vFkok uk" k djuk ugha gš D; kšd ; ksx l Rdk; Bknh gš l Rdk; Bkn ds vuq kj fd l h Hh l r- inkFZ dk uk" k ugha gks kA "fujksk" "kCn vFkHko , oa frj kHko ds vFZ ea vk; k gš fpÜk dh ikp Hkie; k; gš & f{klr} ew] fof{klr} , dxxz , oa fu:) A fpÜk dh bu ikp Hkie; ka ea ofirfujksk n[kk tkrk gš fpÜk , d fo'k; dks NkMlej nu js fo'k; dks xg .k djrk gš bl idkj igys okys fo'k; dh ofÜk dk : duk fujksk gš yšdu ; ksx "kkL= ea bl idkj l s ofr&fujksk dks ell; rk ugha feyh gš fpÜk dh igyh rhu Hkie; k; ksx ds fy, mi ; ksxh ugha gš , dxxz , oa fu:) Hkie ea gksus okyk ofÜk fujksk gh ; ksx dgk tkrk gš fpÜk dh f{klr vkfn rhu voLFkk; i z Ru&fujk vkfn LokHkkfod gš fpÜk dks f{klr vkfn Hkie; ka l s Åij mBkdj , dxxz , oa fu:) Hkie; ka l s i frf'Br djus ds fy, i z Ru vi f{kr gš fpÜk dh ofÜk; ka dk fujksk fd l idkj l s gks bl ds fy, egf'kz iratfy us vkB vaxk& ; e] fu; e] vki u] i .k; ke] i R; kgkj] /kj .kk] /; ku , oa l ekf/k okys v'Vax ; ksx dk ifriknu fd; k gš

ef; "kCn % fpÜkofÜk] i .k; ke] /kj .kk] /; ku] l ekf/k] dšY; A

ilMouk % ; ksx dk "kfcnd vFZ gš & tMko & nks ; k nks l s vf/kd oLrq/ka dk ; k vo/kj .kkvka dk vkil ea feyuk ; k tMkA ; ksx okLro ea "kjhj] eu , oa vkrk dk tMko & ; g tMko fpÜk dh ofÜk; ka ds fujksk l s l Hko gš *; ksx "pÜkofÜk fujksk" vFkz- fpÜk dh ofÜk; ka dk fujksk dj ds ge eu] "kjhj , oa vkrk dk , dh dj .k dj yrs gš tks ; ksx dgykrk gš ; ksx , d vkr&mlufr dh thou i) fr gš gekjs ikl bl s viukus ds vfrfjDr vl; dkbz fodYi ugha gš D; kšd vkr mlu; u , d lrr ifØ; k gš ; fn ge mlu; u djxs rks vou; u gks tk; s k D; kšd LFkk; h dñ Hh ugha gš vkt bl h fxjkoV ds dkj .k eku o brus d'V] n[ek] i Hk] l ækl] vl gk vkfn Hksc jgk gš ekuork dh bl i Hk dk ef; dkj .k ; ksx thou i) fr l s HVduk gš bl h thou i) fr dks viuk, fcuk ekuo thou ds d'Vka dk fuokj .k gks gh ugha l d rka bl h l s fpÜk dh ofÜk; ka ea ifjorü gsrk gš vFkz-0; fDr dh i ofÜk ea vk/kj Hkr ifjorü gsrk gš ftl l s og vius dks ykHk] ykyp] bž; k; Øk] ek] vgnkj vkfn eukfodkj ka l s "ku% "ku% ni] gsrk tkrk gš fo"o vkt ; ksx ds bl h vk; ke dks l e> dj bl s viukus dks iLrq gš 21 tw dks vlrjzVh; ; ksx fnol euk; k tkuk ; ksx dh egÜk dks ifriknr djrk gš

vkt dsl d kj ea euq;] tho&tUrq; gk rd fd izdfr Hkh m}fyr gš v"kkar gā ik; %fdl h dks Hkh "kkār ugha gāfo"o&iVy ij dke] Øksk] ykkk] eksj] vgrdkj ds o"khHkr gksdj ekuo fgā d gks mBk gā ekj&dkV] plgh&Mcdš]h] gjk&Qj]h] 0; fHkpkj vc vie ckr gks x; h gā eV/Bh Hkj fo}ku-vš] tix: d yks NViVk jgs gā & "kkār dh [kkst ea l d kj dks; fn bl dk l ek/kku pkfg, rks og dōy "ol qkō dV/qcde" d k l n'sk nus okyk Hkkjr gh nsl drk gā ge gou ds le; l ex: tM&pru iFoh&vldk" k vkfn l Hkh dh "kkār dh ikfZuk djsr gš; gk rd fd eR; qij tho dh vkrEk dh "kkār dsfy, gj 0; fDr ds an; l s ikfZuk LOqVr gsrh gā bl fo'ke ij fLFkr ea Hkkjr dk "; l x: n"lū" l d kj dks "kkār vš] l nHko inku djus dh "kFDr j [krk gā "; l x: D; k gš ftl dh ppkz l Ei wZ fo"o ea gks jgh gš; g tkuuk vko"; d gā dN yks "kjhj dks foHkUu izdkj l s rkm&ejkM+yrs gā mul s vPNk; l x: dks gks l drk gš yEcs le; rd "okl dks jkduk gh; l x: gkr rks ftrus Hkh ukfod vš] rškd gā os l c; l x: gks x, gkrā ek= vš] [ka cn djds cBus l s; l x: cu tkuk l c l s vPNk rjhdk gkrā olr r% orēku ea; l x: dks cgr gYds rjhds l s l r r; fd; k tk jgk gā fo"sk rš] ij vesj dk vš] ; jk; ea t gk; bl s dfr i; vkl u] ik. k; ke , oa "kkj hfjd 0; k; ke rd gh l hferdj fn; k x; k gā; l x: "kMn"lū ea l s, d n"lū gā; l x: n"lū ds vfrfjā vū; ikp n"lū gš & l k;] U; k; & oš k'kd] i mZ eheda k , oa mUk j eheda kA bu n"lūka ij gh eyw Hkkjr h; l f dfr , oa l H; rk vk/kkfjr gā; l x: Hkh vū; n"lūka ds l eku vR; Ur foLrr] rkd d] l k j x fHkz , oa mrd'V pruk dk fupkM+ gā iratfy jfpr; l x: l = ij l oā fke vR; Ur ikf. MR; i wZ *0; kl Hkk'; * fy [kk x; kA U; k; & oš k'kd dh Hkkfr *l eku rU= " ds fuokj d gā l k; , oa; l x: n"lūA l k; v/; kRe fo l k dk l š k fUr d : i gš; l x: ml dk 0; kogkfjd : iA l k; n"lū ea; g fl) kUr ifrf'Br gpk fd *food&Kku l s dōy; i klr gkr gā; l x: n"lū *food&Kku* fdl izdkj i klr gks l drk gš bl 0; kogkfjd i {k dk 0; k; ku djrk gā nkska , d nū js ds ijd gā iratfy dk; l x: n"lū l ekf/k] l k/ku] foHkfr vš] dōy; bu pkj Hkkxha ea foHkDr gā

v'Vlak; l x: % v'Vlak; l x: "kCn l s gh Li'V gš fd; g; l x: vkB vaka okyk gā vkB vak gā 1/2 ; e] fu; e] vkl u] ik. k; ke] iR; kgkj] /kkj. k] /; ku , oa l ekf/kA ; e % *; e; flr fuorZ Urhfr; ek% bl 0; i fūk ds vuq kj tks vokāNuh; dk; kA l s fuor djkr gš os; e dgykrsgā fuofūk eyd; e ikp gš 1/2 & vfgā k] l R;] vLrš] cāp; ZrFkk vijxgA fu; e % *fu; e; flr ij; Urhfr fu; ek% bl 0; i fūk ds vuq kj tks "kkk dk; kA ea i mUk djkr gš os *fu; e* dgykrsgā iofūk eyd fu; e ikp izdkj dk gš & "kkp l Ursk ri Lok/; k; šojif. k/kkfu fu; ek% 1/3

"kkp] l Ursk] ri] Lok/; k;] bZoj if. k/kkua
vkl u % *vkl; rsusfr vkl ue] bl 0; i fūk ds vuq kj ftl voLFkk ea "kjhj vi fkr le; rd l k l s jg l d] ml s vkl u dgrsgā "ftrus izdkj ds tho𝔱 k; gā mrus gh izdkj ds vkl u gā 1/4 1/2 vkpk; ZfoKku fHk] q "kCnā l s Li'V gš fd vkl u dh fuf'pr l k; k ugha gā i d k vkl u gš & i nekl u] fl) kl u] Hknkl u] "kokl u] e; jkl u] deykl u] otkl u vkfnA

ik. k; ke % "okl i'okl dk xrfopNn ik. k; ke gā l r q cāh; UrjLrEHkofūknškdky l k; kfhk% ifjn'Vks nh'kz i e% 1/5 1/2 egf'kz iratfy us ik. k; ke ds pkj Hkn fd; s gā & cāofūkj pd] vkh; Urjofūki j d] LrEHkofūkd fHkd rFkk cāh; Urjfo'k; k {k h d fHkdA

iR; kgkj % *bfūnz. kf. k fo'k; H; % i R; kfā; Urs foed'khf; Ursusfr i R; kgkj gš bl 0; Ri fYk ds vuq kj bfūnz; ka dks vi us fo'k; ka l s gVkdj ml gā vūre fkh cukuk i R; kgkj gā Āij dgs; e l s i R; kgkj rd ds l k/kuā dk l kefgd uke cfgjx gš D; kīd budk y {; fpūk dks Hkkšrd cā inkfWā dh vš] tkus

I s j k l u k g l k r g a b l d s c k n / k k j . k k v k f n r h u f 0 ; k v k a } k j k f p 0 k d h , d l x r k d s f o f f k u : i k a d h l k / k u k i k j e h k g l s r h g a m l g a * v l r j a k l k / k u d g k x ; k g s d ; k f d i n k f k z f p l l r u v l r e a k h g l s r k g a / k j . k k % f d l h n s k & f o n s k e a f p 0 k d s f l f k j h d j . k d k s / k j . k k d g r s g a / k j . k k d s u k f f k p 0 a n ; d e y] d . B] e [k v k f n v k u r f j d n s k g a l w j p l n j v f x u v k f n / k j . k k d s c k a n s k g a / ; k u % / k j . k k d s n s k & f o n s k e a t c / ; s o l r q d k k k u , d k d k j : i l s g k u s y x r k g s r c m l s / ; k u * d g r s g a v f k k z - o r ; U r j & " k u ; f p 0 k d k / ; s f o k ; d l n " k i o k g " / ; k u " g a v f k k z - u k f f k v k f n v k h ; U r j n s k a v l s j l w z v k f n c k a n s k a e a f p 0 k d h l f k i u k d j u k / k j . k k * g s v l s b l u g h a n s k a e a b z o j] n o r k v k f n d k f p l l r u d j u k / ; k u g a

I e m / k % t c / ; k u / ; s e k = d k i d k " k d r f k k v i u s / ; k u d k j : i l s j f g r d s t s k g l s t k r k g s r c m l s * l e k f / k * d g r s g a o f 0 k & f u j k s k k r e d ; k s n k s i d k j d k g s %

1/4 1/2 I e i k k r v l s j 1/2 1/2 v l e i k k r a

e g f ' k z i r a t f y d s v u q k j f = x q k k r e d l f ' v d s n k s i z k s t u g a & H k k s , o a e k s k a i q ' k d s H k k s d s f y , i g y s = x q k k r e d k i d f r b l d s l e { k f o ' k ; m i l f k k f i r d j r h g a H k k s d s c k n m l d k d k e g s i q ' k d s f y , e k s k d k l e i k n u d j u k a ; k s & l k / k u k d s v h ; k l h d h d r d r ; r k d b y ; i k l r d j u s e a g a t h o u d h l q y r k , o a i f j i w k z k b l h e a g a i r ; d 0 ; f d r i f r d y & o n u h ; n e [k l s n l y d k j k p l g r k g a * d b y ; * g h , d h v o l f k k g s f t l e a f u f " p r : i l s r f k k i j h r j g l s n e [k d k u k " k d j u s d h l e f ; z g a e k s k] e f d r v k f n b l d s i ; k z g a l e k f / k d s n k s H k n g s &

1/4 1/2 I e i k k r l e m / k % f o r d k z u q r] f o p k j u q r] v k u l n u q r r f k k v l e r k u q r b l d s p k j H k n g a

1/2 1/2 v l e i k k r l e m / k % l e i k k r l e k f / k e a d n o f 0 k ; k j g r h g a i j u r q v l e i k k r l e k f / k e a l H k o f 0 k ; k a d k f u j k s k g l s t k r k g a

b z o j o n % ; k s " k k l = e a * b z o j * r 0 o d h v o r k j . k k t x r - d s e w d k j . k 1/2 m i k n k u d k j . k 1/2 d s : i e a u g h a g b] v f i r q ; k s & l k / k u k d s l U n H k z e a b z o j d k e g l o i w k z l f k k u i f r i k f n r g y k g a

; k s n " k u e a t m + v l s j p r u n k s i d k j d s i n k f k k z d k o . k u m i y c / k g l s r k g a b z o j p r u o x z d s v l r x z g a p r u r 0 o i q ' k g s v r % b z o j H k h i q ' k g s y s d u o g l o z k / k j . k i q ' k u g h a g s v f i r q i q ' k & f o " k s k g a c)] e p r l e 1/2 o n g v l s j i d f r y ; 1/2 e p r r f k k l n k e p r] p k j i d k j d s i q ' k k a e a o g l n k e p r g a i q ' k k a d h c) k f n J s . k ; k a e a v l e ; 1/2 u s d 1/2 i q ' k v k r s g s y s d u l n k e p r J s k h e a , d g h i q ' k & f o " k s k g s v u d u g h a v f k k z - i q ' k & f o " k s k b z o j v f } r h ; g a v l ; i q ' k k a d h v i s k k b z o j e a f o y { k . k r k b l d k s l s g s f d o g v f o l k v k f n i k p D y s ' k] " k k k " k k k d e j d e z f u r] t k f r] v k ; q r f k k H k k s : i f o i k d 1/2 Q y 1/2 r f k k d e & l h d k j 1/2 d e k z k ; 1/2 l s l o h k , o a l o f k k v l l i ' v j g r k g a i r a t f y u s v l e ; i q ' k k a e a l s , d i q ' k e a D y s ' k k f n d k v k r ; f l u r d : i l s v H k k o j g u s d s d k j . k m l s * i q ' k & f o " k s k b z o j * d g k g a b z o j d k y d h l e k l s i j s g a b l h v k " k ; d k s ; k s l = e a * d k y k u o f P N U u * d g k x ; k g a b z o j d h v i f r g r " k f d r d k d H k h H k h f o ? k k r u g h a g l s r k a o g f d l h H k h l e ; v l s j f d l h H k h i n k f k z i j v i u h i H k k o " k f d r d k i z k s d j r k g a b z o j d h x q r k H k h v f o l e j . k h ; g a o g v u k f n d k y l s * i j e x # * d h m i k f / k / k j . k f d ; s g a b z o j e a k k u " k f d r] b P N k " k f d r , o a f 0 ; k " k f d r r h u k a i j e m r d ' k z d k s i k l r g a J f r v k f n x H f k k a e a b z o j A p k j d k n l j k u k e i z k o g a b z o j , o a i z k o e a o k p ; o k p d H k k o l E c u / k g a b z o j i z k o d k o k p ; g s v l s j i z k o b z o j d k o k p d g a n k u k a d k ; g l E c u / k v u k f n g a v f k k z - o r e k u l x l e a g h u g h v f i r q l e l r v r h r l x k a e a b z o j i z k o u k e l s t k u k x ; k v l s j v u k x r l x k a e a H k h b z o j * i z k o * d k o k p ; j g x k a f p 0 k d k s , d k x z c u k u s d s f y , e g f ' k z i r a t f y ; k s d s v h ; k f l ; k a d k s i z k o d k t i d j u s d k i j k e " k z f n ; k g a b z o j d h d i k l s l k / k d ; k s d h v l r e v o l f k k * v l e i k k r * d k s i k l r d j r k g a

; k s d h m i ; k s r k % i k p h u t h o u i) f r f y ; s ; k s v k t d s i f j o s k e a g e k j s t h o u d k s l o l f k , o a [k q k g y c u k l d r k g a ; k s d s v u d v k l u t s s f d " k o k l u m P p j D r p k i d k s l e k u ; d j r k g s t h o u d s f y , l a t h o u h g a d i k y H k k f r i k . k k ; k e] H k k e j h i k . k k ; k e e u d k s " k k r d j r k g s o t k l u g e a

vud chekfj; ka l s cprk gA vkt dEl; Wj dh nfu; k ea fnuHkj ml ds l keus cB&cBs dke djus l s vud yxka dks dej nnZ ,oa xnZu nnZ dh f"kd; r , d vke ckr gis xbz gS , d s ea "kyHkl u rFk rMkl u gea nnZ fuokjd nok l s efa fnykrk gA iouepajl u vius uke ds vuq i iV ea xS dh l eL; k dks nij djrk gA xfb; k dh l eL; k dks es nMkl u nij djrk gA ; l s; ea , d s vud vkl u gS ftuds thou ea viukus l s dbZ chekfj; k l ekr gis tkrh gS vS [krjukd chekfj; ka dk vl j Hkh de gis tkrk gA ; g dguk vfr" k; kfa ugha gsch fd ; l s; gekjs fy, gj rjg l s vko"; d gA ; g gekjs "kkjhfd" ekuf d vS vkfRed LokLF; ds fy; sykHkrk; d gA ; l s; ds ek/; e l s vkfRed l rfv "kkar vS Atkku pruk dh vuHkr ikr gsrh gS ftl l s gekjk thou rukoeja rFk gj fnu l dkjRed Atk ds l kF vxsc<Fk gA ; l s; k; kl l s jskka l s yMeus dh "kfa c<rh gA "kjh LoLFk fujks ,oa cyoku curk gA ik.k; ke ds }kjk "okl izokl dh xfr ij fu; a.k gsrk gS ftl l s "ol u l kFku l ecfu/kr jskka ea cgr Qk; nk feyrk gA nek] , yth] utyk] tpe vkn jskka ea rks ik.k; ke cgr Qk; nain gS gh l kFk gh bl l s QOMka dh vktl htu xg.k djus dh {kerk c<+ tkrh gS ftl l s "kjh dh dks"kdvka dks T; knk vktl htu feyus yxrh gS ftl dk ijs "kjh ij l dkjRed iHko iMrk gA vkt dy /; ku vkfRed-efMV'sku dk ipkj gekjs nsk l s Hkh T; knk fons'ka ea gis jgk gA vkt dh Hkkrdokn l jdr ea fnu jkr Hkx nMk} dke dk nokj f"rka ea vfo"okl vkn ds dkj.k ruko cgr c< x; k gA , d h l kFkr ea /; ku l s cgrj vS dN ugha gA /; ku l s ekuf d ruko nij gskj xgu vkfRed "kkar egl l gsrh gS dk; Z "kfa c<rh gS uhn vPNh vkrh gA eu dh , dkrk , oa/kj.k "kfa c<rh gA ; l s; "kjh vS eLr'd dks , d l kFk l urfyr djds izdr l s tMeus dk l cl sl g fkr ek/; e gA ; l s; ds izkrk egf'kz iratfy dk ekuuk Fk fd vk/; kRed ykHka dh nf'V l s dh tkus okyh ; l s; l k/kuk gsrq ufrd l r'<Fk , oa mUke pfj= i kFfed vko"; drk gA vr'egf'kz ; l s; l k/kuk dks ; e vkfRed- l kHke pkjf=d l kkt d fun'ka l s i kEHK djrs gA bl ds vuqkyu ds fcuk 0; fa ; l s; dj gh ugha drk] ; l s; dk vHr i mZ l pkj fd; k x; k fdlurq vkl u] ik.k; ke rFk /; ku ij gh dSunr fd; k x; kA

; l s; dh ikl bcdrk % ikphudky ea ; l s; l ekt l s nij iozka vS tkyka dh xQk&dnjkvka ds , dkr ea riL; k fd; k djrs Fk os izdrk ij vkfJr l knk o l jy thou 0; rhr fd; k djrs Fk vkt ds Hkkrdokn ; a ea , d vS tgl ge foKku }kjk fodkl dh nf'V l s mlufur ds f"k[kj ij igp jgs gS ogha n h vS vk/; kRed : i l s gekjk iru ifjyfkr gis jgk gA vkt euq; ds [kku&iku] vkpkj&0; ogkj l Hkh ea ifjorZ gkus l s ml dk LokLF; ; ifrfnu [kjk gsrk tk jgk gA ; gh dkj.k gS fd vkt gea _f'k&efu; ka dh f"kk dks tkus ds fy, muds }kjk cuk; s mUke LokLF; ds jkLrs ij pyus ds fy, ; l s; dh ije vko"; drk gS ftl l s ge *cgrtu fgrk; cgrtu l r'k; * dh l r'kn dYiuk dks l kFkd dj l dA ; l s; dk iHko dny eka i s" k; ka ij gh ugha gf; ka ij Hkh i Mrk gA ; l s; ea vkl u dny "kkjhfd 0; k; ke Hkj ugha gA vkt foKku ea euq; dks 0; kogkj d thou ea vud rjg dh l r'k&l r'o/kk; i nku dh gS ftl l s vkt euq; l r'o/kkHkosh gkus l s fuf'0; vS vkyl h curk tk jgk gA ifj.kleLo: i euq; dh thou "kSyh vikfdr gkus l s og izdr l s cgr nij pyk x; k gA bl dkj.k og vud rjg ds d'V'k n'k'k' dfBukbz ka l s f'kjr tk jgk gA bu "kkjhfd 0; k/f/k; ka ds vykok og ekuf d vS vkfRed : i l s Hkh : X.k gsrk tk jgk gA ml s "kkar ugha gA vr; Ur v"kkfUr , oa ruko eajgus ds dkj.k og ekuf d : i l s detg gsrk tk jgk gA ; g l kFkr ; o'k'vka vS o) ka dh gh ugha cfYd cPka dh Hkh gA cPka ds Aj nijn"ku vS dEl; Wj] ekcbj vkn byDVmud midj.kka dk tcjnLr iHko gA bl dkj.k eL; : i l smudh nf'V iHkfor gkus l s vud rjg dh vk'kka dh 0; k/f/k; ka l s cPps xLr gsrk tk jgs gA

euq; fdruk gh egüokclqkth D; ka u gks exj LoLFk eu ,oa "kjhj ds vHkko ea dñ Hkh ugha dj l drkA pks [ksy dk ehku gks ; k thou ea l Qyrk ikr djuh gkñ dñ dj fn [kkus ds fy, LoLFk jguk igyh ikFkedrk gA ; ksx dk eñ; y{; gea ije pruk ekxZ ij ys tkuk gñ ftl l s gea vius vflRro dk Kku gks l dA ; fn "kjhj jksx xLR gS rks gea ije pruk dh vñg tkus dh bPNk Hkh ugha gkxh] D; kñd "kjhj #X.k gksus l seu ij vl j iMFrk gA ; ksx n"ku nfgd] ekuf l d vñg vkfRed nñkka dks nñj dj euq; dks vñg; rk inku djrk gA l Pps vFkZ ea; ksx "kkL= dks ng] eu rFk vkRek dk pfdRI k "kkL= dgk tkuk vf/kd mi; qñ gkxh] D; kñd bl ds ek; e l s 0; fä vius leR nñkka ij fot; ik l drk gA vkt pfdRI d vñg oKkfud Hkh ; ksx ds ek; e l s LoLFk jgus dh l ykg nsjgs gA ; gh dkj.k gS fd vkt Hkjr gh ugha vfi r q nfu; k Hkj ds yks ; g vuHko dj jgs gS fd LoLFk thou vñg fujks jgs ds fy, ; ksx l okkLe ek; e gA fu'd'kz % ; ksx , d thou i) fr gS ftl dk l Ecl/k fd l h /ke/ l l Eink; , oa er l s u gkxj l Ei w k ekuork l s gA ; e & fu; e ds fl) kura dk ikyu djrs gq ; fn ge ifrfnu dñ l e; fudkydj dñy dfV&Luku ty&urh , oa dfri; vñg uk ds vñ; kl ds l kFk&l kFk "kñkukn , oa /; ku dja rks brus l s gekjk dk Qh dñ dY; k.k gks l drk gA dfV&Luku l s gekjk ikPura= iqV gsrk gA ty&ufr ea yxHkx l kb idkj ds nasal infections dh l Hkkouk [krE gsrh gS vñg "kñkukn rks Lo; a "kjhj d] ekuf l d vñg vkfRed vñ; kl gA /; ku ds fufek "kñkukn dk dksbz fodYi ugha gA bl dk vñ; kl Lo; eñ /; ku dh volFk ea igpk nrk gA ; ksx , oa ml dh vkuqñd f0; kvka }kjk 0; fä dh l exz pruk gh gA bl pruk dks ftruk vf/kd fodfl r fd; k tk, xkA mruh gh euq; dh fof"kr Vrk c->h tk; xhA ekuo ds l kr Åtkz p0ka dh l f0; rk ml dh pruk ds Lrj dks ifjyf{kr djrh gA bu p0ka dks ; fn tkxr dj fy; k tk; rks pruk dk Lrj Hkh mPphdr gks tkrk gA ; ksx dh if0; k; a pruk ds Lrj ka dk mPphdj.k djrh gA /; ku ds l kFk ea= tki djus l s pruk ds Lrj ka ea vfr "kñkz, oa vk "kkrh of) gsrh gA ea= okLro ea Åtkz p0ka dks l f0; djus ds l k/ku gA or0ku ; q; fojkskHkl ka dk ; q; gA viuh rFkdfFkr vk/kqudrk] vñk/kñk oKkfudrk , oa eñ; ghu fopkj ka l sekuork vkt ftruh i h fMFr gsmruh i h fMFr gsmruh dHkh ugha gekjh , d h thou "ksh usvuud ekuf l d] "kjhj d fodkj mRiUu fd; s gñ ftudk dksbz l Qy mi pkj vk/kqud foKku [kxst gh ugha ik; k gA vk/kqud fo"o dh l eL; kvka dk eñ; vk/kk 0; fä dk ykñk] ykyp] 0kñk] dke] "kñä] en] vgnkj vñfn gA ; l c gh Dysk vFkZ-d'V dk dkjd gA ; ksx ds ; e" vñg "fu; e" dks vaxhr djus l s bu eukfodkj ka l s eñä fey l drh gñ vFkZ- bu Dysk ka dk mi pkj ; ksx ds ek; e l s gh l Hko gA ; ksx ds ek= ikjñHk dh vñ; kl l s gh bu ofUk; ka ij fu; U=.k ik; k tk l drk gA vius euhf"k; kus vkfndky l s gh ; ksx dks thou i) fr cuk; s tkus dk fun3k bl fy; sfn; k Fk rkd ge l c vius "kjhj] eu , oa vñkRek ds l kFk y; c) gkxj l eLr cñk.M ds l kFk , dhdr gks l dA fu'd'kz-% ge dg l drs gS fd "kjhj] eu vñg vkRek dks fu; ñ=r djus ea ; ksx l gk; rk djrk gA "kjhj vñg eu dks "kkr djus ds fy, ; g "kjhj d vñg ekuf l d vuqñk l u dk , d l anyu cukrk gA ; g ruko vñg fprk dk izl/ku djusea Hkh l gk; rk djrk gS vñg vkjke l s jgusea enn djrk gA ; ksx vñk l "kñä] "kjhj ea yphy s u vñg vkRefo"okl fodfl r djus fd fy, tkuk tkrk gA ; ksx cgrj ikpura= inku djrk gñ vkrñj d vax etar djrk gA ; ksx vLFkek] e/kpñ] fny l s l EclU/kr chekfj; ka dk bykt djus ea enn djrk gA ; ksx 'kñä vñg l gu'kñä dks c->ok nrk gñ , dksrk ea l kñk djrk gñ eu vñg fopkj fu; U=.k ea enn djrk gA ; ksx fprk] ruko vñg vol kn ij dks w i kus ds fy, eu "kkr j [krk gA ; ksx ruko de djus ea enn djrk gA ; ksx jä ifj l pj.k vñg ekñki s "k; ka ds foJke ea enn djrk gA ; ksx fo"o dks Hkjr dh nsu gA fo"o dks "kjhj d.k ds nñg ea LoLFk j [kus dk jkeck.k bykt gS ; ksx A ; ksx n"ku vñg /keZ l s ijs gA ; ksx , d , d h fof/k gS ftl s viukdj 0; fä vius 0; fdrYo dk l okñk.k fodkl dj l drk gS rFk viuh thokRek dks ijekRek ds l kFk tñk+l drk gA ; ksx n"ku ea ; ksx

"kCn dks ,d l k/ku ds : i ea crk;k tkrk gA bl l k/ku ea viuh fpUkofUk dk fujksk dj vRRe&l a e ds }kk fpUk dks ofUk"kk; dj nsuk gh ; ksx gA ; ksx dby jkska dks nj djus dh i fO; k ugha g; ; ksx dk dke "kjhj ds jkska dks nj dj] eu dks "kar rFkk ifo= cukdj vRRek dk ijekRek l s l Ecl/k cukuk gA ; ksx ds nks vFkz gS & i Fke tkM/k rFkk nk jk l ekf/kA tc rd ge Lo; a l sugha tM/s l ekf/k rd igpuk vl EHko gLokA eu dks cf) l s rFkk cf) dks eu l s tkM/rk gS ; ksxA euq; ds Hkhrj t s Hk mFky&i fky g; fc[kjk gqk gSm l s vLreU l s tkM/rk gS ; ksxA ; ksx "ol u fO; k dks fu; fl=r dj ru vL; eu ea l keatL; cuk, j[krk gS bl fy, ; ksx dks nfid thou ea vo"; "kkfey fd;k tkuk pkfg,A

I UrHkZ I pph %

- 1/4 1/2 ; ksx l # 2@29
- 1/2 1/2 ; ksx l # 2@30
- 1/3 1/2 ; ksx l # 2@32
- 1/4 1/2 ; ksx l # i*B 267
- 1/5 1/2 ; ksx l # 2@59
- 1/6 1/2 Hkkjrh; n"ku & MKW nsjkt & prfKZ l d j.k & 1992
- 1/7 1/2 ; ksx l # & 0; kl Hkk';] ruo oSkkjnh] ; ksokfrZl vkfn l fgr pk[kkEck 1935
- 1/8 1/2 l Ei wkkZun & ; ksx n"ku] fgl nh l fevr] y[kuA 1965
- 1/9 1/2 orZku ea ; ksx dh ikl ixdrk & 21 tu 2015 & jktho "keZ & yoga and nature care club.blog spot.com
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- 1/11 1/2 orZku l e; ea ; ksx dk egYo & ftrbhz ,oa t; iky fl g jkti w International Journal of physiology, nutrition and physical education

BUILDING A MULTILINGUAL ONTOLOGY FOR EDUCATION DOMAIN USING MONTO METHOD

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Abstract:

Ontologies are emerging technology in building knowledge based information retrieval systems. It is used to conceptualize the information in human understandable manner. Knowledge based information retrieval are widely used in the domain like Education, Artificial Intelligence, Healthcare and so on. It is important to provide multilingual information of those domains to facilitate multi-language users. In this paper, we propose a MOnTo (Multilingual Ontology) methodology to develop multilingual ontology applications for education domain. New algorithms are proposed for merging and mapping multilingual ontologies.

Keywords: Ontology, Methodology, Multilingual

1. Introduction

Ontology enables the natural language processing of the data in an efficient way. It retrieves the information based on the knowledge and conceptualizes the information in formal way. Enormous information is available over the internet in a specific language. It is essential to provide the information in different natural languages to benefit multi-language users. Ontologies play vital role in providing knowledge based information systems.. Ontology is a “formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization”(Asunción Gómez-Pérez, 2004). It is a collection of set of concepts, properties, relations, instances, axioms and rules which can be represented as, **(Ontology) O = {C, P, R, I, A}**. ‘C’ represents the classes or concepts of the domain. ‘P’ signifies the properties of the concept. ‘R’ denotes the binary relations between the concepts(1-1, 1-M, M-M) . ‘A’ represents axioms and rules which are used as a basis for reasoning(Kumar, 2013). In ontology a set of terms for describing a domain is arranged hierarchically that can be used as a skeletal foundation for a

knowledgebase(Asunción Gómez-Pérez, 2004). This nature of ontology enables the developer to implement semantic based personalized learning applications. The ontology developed for the educational domain contains the knowledge for developing intelligent learning system. Monolingual ontology applications for learning system are developed by adopting the methodology(Dimitris Kanellopoulos, 2006). Ontologies are used to represent knowledge which reflects the relevant information of the concepts and relations. There were many methodologies proposed to build ontology applications which have their own pitfalls. Modeling, evaluating and maintaining ontologies are a complex tasks in most applications such as healthcare, business, commerce and many other. There are many domains that necessitate satisfying the different language users. For example the users of government services, learning sites, education domains, healthcare domains demands to access information in their local language. In such scenario, ontology plays a vital role to provide knowledge based information. Numerous methods and tools are proposed for building monolingual ontologies. Very few methods like Collaborative platform are proposed to build multilingual ontologies but they are limited to some languages. This chapter proposes new methodology to build multilingual ontologies.

Rapid development of internet users demands on information in their natural languages which leads to the development of multilingual applications. The aim of this paper is to give an idea to develop multilingual ontologies for education domain using the proposed MOnto methodology. New algorithms are proposed for merging and mapping ontologies developed in different natural languages.

The paper organized as follows: an overview of ontology based learning systems are narrated in section 2. Section 3 proposes a new methodology to build multilingual ontologies Conclusions are proposed in section 4.

2. State-of-the-art of Ontology-based Learning

Learning Ontologies are used in software agents, language independent applications and problem solving methods. Ontology applications are developed using ontology development languages (OWL, RDF, TURTLE, Triple and so on) and ontology development tools(Protégé, OntoEdit, Chimaera and so on). Learning ontology application are implemented in two different techniques where method is a process of performing some task and technique is a procedure used to achieve given objective. This research work proposes MOnto methodology to build multilingual ontology applications. This methodology consists of five phases as given in Figure 3.1. viz., i) Input, ii) Building MO, iii) Ontology mediation, iv) Retrieval and v) Visualization of ontology.

Figure 3.1 MOnto Methodology for Building Multilingual Ontology

2.1 Phase 1: Input

This phase initializes the content to be considered for building ontologies. A set of methods and techniques are used for building ontology from distributed and heterogeneous knowledge and information sources. Information can be retrieved from different sources like, open corpus, closed corpus and existing ontologies. All the sources are under three categories: Unstructured sources, semi-structured source and structured source. Unstructured sources involve NLP techniques, morphological and syntactic analysis, etc. Semi-structured source elicits ontology from sources that have some predefined structure, such as XML Schema. Structured data extracts concepts and relations from knowledge contained in structured data, such as databases. Closed corpus is a text from the text books, study materials etc. Open corpus refers to the information available on the web. Corpus is used to represent the represents ontology by using a set of techniques to extract the knowledge from the text. In this phase, the scope and domain for building MO is identified. In order to build a new ontology for the specified domain, it is important to make sure that there is any ontology already available to the particular domain. In that case, the ontology has to be considered for reusing and re-engineering for building MO. The sources for building MO is collected as given in Table 3.1. The developer has to identify the domain to develop MO and has to collect the information from various sources in different natural languages. The collected resources are analyzed and classified in this initial phase.

Table 3.1 Document Matrix for Collecting Resources in Different Natural Languages.

Source/ Language	L1	L2	...	Ln
Open corpus	✓	✓	...	✓
Closed corpus	✓	✓	...	
Existing ontology	✓		...	✓

3.2 Phase 2: Building Ontologies

Once the domain is identified, the text extracted from closed corpus and open corpus in different natural languages is arranged hierarchically with the proper classifications. The terms required to build multilingual ontology are collected in different natural languages.

$$L_1 = L_1t_1, L_1t_2, L_1t_3, \dots, L_1t_m$$

$$L_2 = L_2t_1, L_2t_2, L_2t_3, \dots, L_2t_m$$

•
•
•

$$L_n = L_{nt_1}, L_{nt_2}, L_{nt_3}, \dots, L_{nt_m}$$

This can be represented as,

$$\forall i = 1 \text{ to } n \quad L_i = L_{it_1}, L_{it_2}, L_{it_3} \dots L_{it_m} \text{ for } m \text{ terms}$$

where $n \neq m$

Collected terms are analyzed and irrelevant terms are filtered. The terms are classified hierarchically and the relations between the terms are established as,

$$L_{it_j} \xrightarrow{R_s} L_{it_k}$$

The relations between the terms are established and vocabularies of the terms are formulated. Using the laddering structure ontologies are developed in different natural languages (OL₁, OL₂, ..., OL_n where OL is Ontology Language). 'n' Ontologies (OL₁, OL₂ ... OL_n) are developed for L_i natural languages using the terms that are hierarchically structured as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Illustration of Building Ontologies for Two Natural Languages (Tamil and English)

3.3Phase3: Ontology Mediation Methods

Ontology mediation enables reusing of data across applications on Semantic Web, and sharing of data between heterogeneous knowledge bases. Major kinds of ontology mediation are mapping and merging. Ontology mapping is to identify the correspondence between the terms and ontology merging is creating

new ontology which is the union of existing two or more ontologies. In this phase, ontologies developed in different natural languages are merged into single ontology and the correspondences between the terms of different natural languages are established.

For example, $OL_1, OL_2 \dots OL_n$ are the ontologies developed in different natural languages for the selected domain. where,

$$OL_1 = \{ L_{1t_1}, L_{1t_2}, L_{1t_3}, \dots L_{1t_i} \}$$

$$OL_2 = \{ L_{2t_1}, L_{2t_2}, L_{2t_3}, \dots L_{2t_i} \}$$

.

.

.

$$OL_n = \{ L_{nt_1}, L_{nt_2}, L_{nt_3}, \dots L_{nt_i} \}$$

Ontologies developed in different natural languages are merged into a single ontology.

$$ML = \{ OL_1 \cup OL_2 \cup \dots \cup OL_n \}$$

Correspondences between the terms in different natural languages are created

$$L_{nt_i} \rightarrow L_{nt_k}$$

where i and k vary from 1 to i terms in different languages.

Ontologies that are developed in different natural languages are merged into single ontology to structure multilingual ontology application. In formal, it can be represented as,

$$MO = \{ X: O_1L_1 \cup O_2L_2 \cup \dots \cup O_nL_n \} \text{ where } L_i \geq 2 \wedge L_1 \neq L_n$$

$$L_1 \cap L_n \text{ is disjoint}$$

Here, MO – Multilingual Ontology

L – Language

X – Set of elements

X is a collection of elements or terms which are integrated the sources of the same domain in different natural languages. Many tools like OntoClean, FCAMerge, and Observer are available to merge ontologies. The merged ontology composed of set of terms in different natural languages. Ontology merging can be done by using SMART algorithm (Noy & Musen, 1999). This algorithm deals with merging and aligning of monolingual ontology of the domain. In order to overcome this, the algorithms for ontology mediation methods are proposed for merging and mapping ontology (Merlin Florence Joseph, 2017). The research adapted those algorithms for merging and mapping multilingual ontologies.

3.4 Phase 4: Multilingual Information Retrieval using SPARQL

Information retrieval is the process of retrieving or extracting the information from the repository based on the user's need and query. Retrieving information in various languages can be named as multilingual information retrieval. In ontologies, SPARQL query is used to extract the knowledge from the ontology

repository. RDF tags are used in SPARQL query to filter the results by means of language. This phase enables the users to extract knowledge in their own languages using SPARQL. SPARQL provides the functionality to retrieve the information in different natural languages. The sample SPARQL query is given as follows:

```
PREFIX scs: <http://www.shctptcs.org#>
SELECT ?subject ?object
WHERE
{
    ?subject scs:verse ?object.
FILTER(lang(?object)="ta")
}
```

The given SPARQL used 'FILTER' to sort the result and give the results of information in a specified language.

3.5 Phase 5: Visualizing Multilingual Ontology

Visualization is a representation of text or object in the form of image or chart. It enables the readers to capture the knowledge effectively. Ontology is a hierarchically structured model which has numerous visualization tools (OWLGrEd, NavigOWL, IsAVizetc) and plug-ins (OntoGraf, OWLviz, CropCircles and so on). All the existing ontology visualization tools are lacking in visualizing non-English languages. Some of them require additional configuration to support different natural languages. In this phase, the new plug-in known MLGrafViz is proposed to visualize ontology in different natural languages.

For example, the passage given in Figure 3.5 is represented diagrammatically in Figure 3.6. This depicts that the graphical representation of the text is clearer than the passage where the user may feel vague while reading a passage.

Figure 3.5 (a) Steps Involved in Programming – Text

<p>To begin with, writing a program involves several steps viz., Define the external specification including the user interface and event handlers, Build the user interface, Code event handlers and write common code, Debug the program and Document the program. The external specification should show the appearance of the user interface -- which controls are on the screen and how they are laid out. It should also specify the events that can occur Build the user interface using the VS development system. Code the event handlers. For each event you define in step 1, Debugging is the process of finding and correcting your errors. The programmer must prepare documents describing both the external specification and the internal design of the program. This documentation will be of value to users and programmers who must maintain and modify your program.</p>

Figure 3.5 (b) Visualization of Steps Involved in Programming – Diagrammatic Representation

MLGrafViz is developed using Java and Graphviz algorithms. Initially, it allows the user to create a new ontology or to import an existing ontology into Protégé workspace. The imported ontology will be displayed in a class browser. MLGrafViz enables the user to select the language to visualize the ontology. The request is submitted to Google translate API which performs statistical machine translation and then the terms are translated into the desired natural languages.

Google translate API is an open source translator used to translate text, speech, images and videos from source language to target language. It provides an API which allows the developer to build an extension and software to translate the source. Google translate uses statistical analyses instead of rule based analyses. Since ontology is hierarchically structured terms, statistical machine translator

provides better result than the rule based translator. Rule based machine translation is used in translating the passage grammatically. Finally, the translated terms are displayed in MLGrafViz panel. MLGrafViz facilitates the user to visualize the ontology in different natural languages without changing the core ontology structure as depicted in Figure 3.6 (a), (b).

Figure 3.6 (a) Visualization in Tamil Language

Figure 3.6 (b) Visualization in Zulu Language

4. Conclusion

We have proposed MOnTo (Multilingual Ontology) methodology to develop multilingual ontology application for education domain. New algorithms are proposed to perform merging and mapping of multilingual ontologies. This method allows the user to learn the subject from their own natural language which gives better understanding of the subject. This research work identifies the need of building multilingual application which plays vital role in educational domain. If the learning materials are in different natural languages, the learner will feel comfortable in learning. Learning through the natural languages is an essential thing which encourages the learner to learn many things. In future, multilingual applications can be implemented for different

domain like healthcare. It is important to provide the evaluation metrics and methods to validate multilingual ontologies.

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A STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE EVOLUTION OF BUDDHIST CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF WEST BENGAL: SPECIAL REFERENCE BIRBHUM DISTRICT

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M.A History, SET and NET qualified

Introduction:

The history of the emergence of Buddha in the day of humanity's crisis is renewed in our minds, in the very past, he was the great human lover who showed the unparalleled easy path to the liberation of mankind where there was no discrimination nor any social bond. In the 6th century BCE, Buddhism called for the creation of a classless new social structure, but today its existence is at the doorstep of the extinction, where in the whole of South-East Asia, China, Taiwan, Nepal, Bhutan, countries have a significant population ,according to the 2001 census 7.5 million,[1] and 2011 census figures in West Bengal 282898 which is 0.33 percent of the entire population.[2]At a time when Buddhism was shrinking throughout India, Bengal was the last refuge of Buddhists. Therefore, Buddhist education also became involved in the cultural order of the Bengali language and culture, “charjapad” the first written book of Bengal was written by the Buddhist Siddhacharya or the Mahath Guru.[3]Bengal was location of large number of Buddhist monasteries which had a significant backdrop for the monastic center education system. Therefore, the history of the Buddhist sequence in the history of Bengal plays a profound significance. Even though many things have changed over time, in today's Bengali society and culture it can be seen in other ways.

Key words: Buddhism, Mahath Guru, Bonga, Dharma, Antara Nakeya, Golden Land, Peer, Dargah,

History of the emergence of Buddhism in Bengal:

The large tracts of India have affected people's life and culture in many ways, because of influence on the political and economic life of the area, as well as social life. The ancient history of Bengal says that Bongaor Bengal an area of agriculture located in the plains of the Ganges and the Brahmaputra, due to this cause the political and religious life in this region rotated with farming [4]. The spread of Buddhism was accelerated due to the wide system of Hinduism and the tendency of the liturgy, although in this context the patronage of great emperors like Mahamati Ashoka and Kanishka is particularly significant.[5] Buddhism arrived in Bengal in the 6th century BC, when Buddha was preaching religion in Magadha, Kapilabastu, then he travels in Bengal, this reference can be found in Bodhisattva and Abadan kolpolata. According to Angutara Nikaya, the Buddha came to the "golden land" and was for some time, mentioned in the jataka.[6] Although there was no mention name of Bengal in any Mahajan pada, among the sixteen Mahajan padas of that time. Niharranjan Roy said that golden land or Sumahajanpada was located on the west side of Howrah district [7]. During the reign of Mahamati Ashoka, an important chapter in the history of Buddhism, under his patronage, Buddhism spread widely in India, he built 84000 stupas, and also wrote on pillars, rock,cave, though the existence of the Quid portion still exists. The excavation in the Bengal has found many potteries of the NGPB style, dating from the 2nd to 4th centuries BC. From these, it is proved that Buddhism came to Bengal during the lifetime of the Buddha, but its spread took place during the Mauryan period [8]. According to the DivyabadanBuddhismspread in Bengal during the Mauryan rule, the names of two donors were found on the door of the Sanchi Stupa, a devotee (female devotee), another, Ishindan or Rishi Nandan(male).[9] The "Nagarjunikanda" where people were initiated into Buddhism was located in Bengal in the second or third century CE. During the Gupta rule, the Gupta rulers were fanatical of Hinduism but were sympathetic to Buddhism. The traveler "Fahien" (359-415ce) came to India and came to Bengal in the fifth century AD and noted that Bengal was an index of Buddhism at that time [10]. However, the partial decline of Buddhism began in the sixth century AD, during the period of the Gupta rulers, and the progress of Vaishnava and Saiva religion can be traced. Maha Samanta Shashank demolished many Buddhist monasteries, being a Buddhist extremist as well as being a follower of Shaiva religion. In the seventh century, "Hui-n-sang" (629-45 AD) came to India and during his visit to Pandruvardhana (638-45AD), he seen that the Buddhist field was one of the large monasteries or Po-C-Po and mentioned that Buddha spend three months here [11]. He also mentions that Shashank cut off the Bodhibikkha, where the Buddha attained Bodhi and also, he removed the Buddha statue from the Buddhist monastery and

replaced the Shiva statue [12]. After Shashank, the Kharag dynasty (650-700 AD), Rat Dynasty 640ad, Dave Dynasty (720-825 AD), Pambansa (750-1165 AD) the Chandra dynasty ruled successively all of them patronized Buddhism [13]. The Golden Age of Bengali Buddhism was at the same time as the Pala's, the Pala kings were adherents of Mahajan Buddhism. Gopal and Dharmapala built many monasteries. Dharmapala built the Odantpuri, Vikramasila and Sampuri Vihara [14]. But during the Pala period, Mahajan Buddhism changed and became Mantrajan, Vajrayana, SahajJan, KalChakra Jan. The influence of spells and tantric practices converts Buddhism to Tantric Buddhism. During the Sena and Barman dynasties, Buddhism became so narrow that after the rule of the Pala's no other ethnic group supported the Buddhist religion. During the Sena rule, the acceptance of Shaiva religion increased in the place of Buddhism and after the decline of the Sena rule, with the spread of Islam, Buddhism gradually began to disappear from Bengal. Buddhism immerses itself in Hinduism and Islam.

Evolution of Buddhist Culture:

Nowadays, as people change their political parties as they wish, people used to change religion in the past, they came out of Hinduism and later became Muslims. This change has occurred mainly among the lower classes of people who are considered to be untouchable in Hindu society. Statistics show that the majority of the people who adopted Islam in Bengal were Buddhists at first, who converted to Islam because of the persecution of the self-proclaimed representatives of Hinduism. Over time, the intrusion of corruption into Buddhist unions created division among themselves, as well as the revival of Hinduism under the leadership of Shankaracharya, Ramanuja, Sri Chaitanya Dev, the role of Sufi saints, the lack of patron ruler and the Tantric work weakens the foundation of Buddhist religion [15]. Even then those who remain on the way of practicing of Buddhism they leave Bengal and take shelter in Nepal and some in Chittagong Bangladesh. Basically, after the advent of Islam in Bengal, Buddhism became very tight and Most Buddhists accepted Islam slowly because they hated Hindus. According to Ramai Pandit "Niranjan's Rushma in His Dharma puja Bidhan", it is said that Dharma thakur has come to disguise Muslims to protect their devotees from persecution of Hindus of upper castes. Many Buddhists returned to Hinduism under the influence of Shri Chaitanya Deva in the Bengal Bhakti movement Among them some of the Buddhist cultures that transferred into the present Hindu religion worship that's one is dharma puja. Binay Ghosh in the West Bengal Culture says that if any influence or remnant of the Buddhist festival in Dharma puja is the ruin of the society and culture of the Pala era [16]. After the death of the Buddhist monks, stupas were erected on their body's ash keep in a vessel, later they were known

as Dharam Thakur Thana or place. Many places of dharma Thakur can still be seen in Gram Ganj or village in West Bengal there are many places of them disease treatment and medicine are provided. A survey on Birbhum district is given below.

1. Lakhindarpur (kardiya) broken
2. Hattikra(purandarpur) Hapani, eksira, badak
3. Langulia(suri) eye disease
4. goalpara(bolpur)night vision problem
5. sugunpur (md bazar) padma kata
6. tetul bandh (Rajnagar) woman Sex Disease
7. koma (Suri)amasoi (mucous diarrhea)
8. kaddang(dubrajpur)night vision problem
9. barsall (Rajnagar)dog bite
10. jamthali (Dubrajpur) seti and dhabal (leprosy)
11. ushagram (purandarpur)facture women disease
12. bale (sainthia)bone pain

Similarly, among the Buddhists who embraced Muslim religion, this culture continued to exist in the present that is the worship of Peer. In the era of Buddhism, the tradition of stupa, chaitya worship among Buddhist community is still prevalent among the converted Muslims who use to worship the peer. Even today many Dargahs are seen in the village of Bengal, the fakir who have contributed in public by their deeds, so after his death, people worshiped him in his tomb which is known as Dargah. Some such signs are the mochra peer of the twenty-four parganas, the great Kaji Ghazi, the khutiar Shareef of Kanning, the peer gara Chand, and Data baba of Birbhum.

Conclusion:

In fact, it seems that when two different cultures face the cycle of events, it is formed a conflict and relationship between change. This is how the winning culture is forced to compromise especially in the face of strong core advanced culture. that way the culture of Buddhism is still exist in the culture of Hindu and Muslim community in dharma and peer worship. Finally, we can say that culture changes over time, but we do not end at all.

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IMPACT OF DIGITAL MARKETING ON CUSTOMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract

Digital marketing is defined as buying and selling of information, products and services through computer networks or internet. Digital marketing has been considered a new form of marketing and provided new opportunities for companies to do businesses. The current study aims at finding the impact of digital marketing on customer buying behaviour in Coimbatore district. This study is based on primary data. Percentage analysis and chi square test were used to analyse the data. This study is conducted in Coimbatore District and findings reveals that people who educated, more aware of digital channel and prefer digital channels to buy different kinds of products. Mostly shopping goods are preferred by peoples and rise in buy convenience goods through digital channel.

Keywords: Digital Marketing , Internet communication , E – Marketing .

Introduction

Digital marketing is defined as buying and selling of information, products and services through computer networks or internet. Internet and electronic commerce technologies are transforming the entire economy and changing business models, revenue streams, customer bases and supply chains. Digital marketing is the use of the channels in order to reach the desired target market via some of the following channels and social media , websites , multimedia advertising , online search engine advertisement , E – marketing , interactive marketing.

Digital marketing has been considered a new form of marketing and provided new opportunities for companies to do businesses. Marketing activities conducted via digital channels enable advertisers to directly communicate with potential customers in a rapid velocity and regardless the geographical location. Digital marketing has been recently referred as one of the best means to cut through the mess and interact directly with the consumer. Hence, with the trend toward direct, one to one marketing, additional attention is being paid to the use of the digital channels as a means of effectively advertising to consumers. While considering digital channels, the recent development is mobile marketing.

Indian mobile market is one of the fastest growing markets due to the increase in the number of middle- income consumers. Thus, research on digital channel advertising would impact greatly on the way business is done. The development and widespread use of internet technologies have transformed the way society communicates both in their daily and professional life. One of the most important indicators of this transformation is emergence of new communication tools. New communication tools emerging with the development of technologies are called “Digital Marketing”. When talk about digital channels arises, what comes to intellect are face book, twitter, Instagram and similar social networks that are used online and virtual platforms like websites, micro blogs and search engines. With the advent of new communication to customers with digital channels already available communication tools are now fetching to be called as traditional communication tools. Traditional communication tools are printed(journals, newspaper , books , etc) , visual (television , cinemas , etc) and audio (radio) communication tools.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the awareness of digital marketing in Coimbatore district.
2. To analyse the impact of digital marketing on customers purchase behaviour.
3. To know about kinds of products bought by digital market.

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following hypotheses are framed in the study. They are,

- **H01** :There is no significant relationship between educational qualification and awareness about digital marketing.
- **H02** : There is no significant relationship between monthly income and kinds of products prefer to buy through digital channels.
- **H03** : There is no significant relationship between customer significant relationship between customer satisfaction and product buy through digital channel.

Review of Literature

Anjali (2017) ,“A study on Impact of Digital Marketing on Customer Buying Behaviour” found in her study to enquire about the impact of digital marketing on customer buying behaviour and awareness of digital marketing. This study reveals the customer impact on digital marketing and what type of products has purchased through digital marketing.

Ranjith P and Mahalaxmi K.R. (2016),” A study on Impact of Digital Marketing in Customer Purchase Decision in Trichy” found in their study to enquire about the purchase decision of consumer on digital marketing in Trichy District.

Sivasankaran.S.(2017), “ Digital Marketing and its Impact on Buying Behaviour of Youth” reveals the buying pattern of youth about the digital marketing. It

also found that buying behaviour and behavioural pattern of youth has as greater influence in the purchasing behaviour.

Research Methodology

- **Methods of Data Collection**

Both Primary data and secondary data has been used for collecting the data. Data has been collected through questionnaire method.

- **Method of Sample and Size of the Sample**

Convenient sampling technique has been used to collect the data. 50 respondents were taken to collect the data.

- **Tools used for the Study**

Collected data has been analysed using proper tools. They are,

- Percentage analysis
- Chi – square test

Analysis and Interpretation

1. Demographic Factor of the Respondents:

Particulars	Options	No.of Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Age	Below 20	10	20	20
	20-25	18	36	56
	26-30	10	20	76
	31-35	7	14	90
	40 and above	5	10	100
	Total	50		
Gender	Male	27	54	54
	Female	23	46	100
	Total	50		
Educational qualification	12 th std	12	24	24
	UG	18	36	60
	PG	20	40	100
	Total	50		
Occupation	Students	7	14	14
	Employees	18	36	50
	Professionals	15	30	80
	Business	10	20	100
	Total	50		
Monthly income	Below 10,000	7	14	14
	10000-20,000	11	22	36
	20,000-30,000	17	34	70
	30,000 and above	15	30	100
	Total	50		
Marital status	Single	24	48	48
	Married	26	52	100
	Total	50		

Source : Primary Data

The above table inferred that 36 percentage of the respondents are in the age group of 20 -25 years , 20 percentage of the respondents are in the age group of below 20 years and 26 – 30 years, 14 percentage of the respondents are in the

age group of 31-35 years and 10 percentage of the respondents are in the age group of 40 and above. 54 percentage of respondents are male and 46 percentage of the respondents are female. 40 percentage of the respondents educational qualification is PG , 36 percentage of the respondents qualification is UG and 24 percentage of the respondents are qualified in 12th std. 36 percentage of the respondents are employees , 30 percentage of the respondents are professionals , 20 percentage of the respondents are business people and 14 percentage of the respondents are students. 34 percentage of the respondents income level are Rs.20,000 – Rs.30,000 , 30 percentage of the respondents income level are Rs.30,000 and above , 22 percentage of the respondents income level are Rs.10,000 – Rs.20,000 and 14 percentage of the respondents income level are below Rs.10,000. 52 percentage of the respondents are married and 48 percentage of the respondents are single.

2. Awareness of Digital Marketing:

Particulars	Sources	No. of respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Which of the following digital channel do you aware of?	Social media	18	36	36
	Websites / blogs	17	34	70
	Multimedia advertising	10	20	90
	Email	5	10	100
	Total	50		
From which of the digital channels you bought products?	Social media	20	40	40
	Websites / blogs	20	40	80
	Multimedia advertising	6	12	92
	Email	4	8	100
	Total	50		
Which digital channel influence you more to buy ?	Social media	25	50	50
	Websites / blogs	18	36	86
	Multimedia advertising	5	10	96
	Email	2	4	100
	Total	50		

Source : Primary Data

The above table is inferred that 36 percentage of the respondents got awareness through social media , 34 percentage of the respondents got an awareness through websites/ blogs, 20 percentage of the respondents got an awareness through multimedia advertising and 10 percentage of the respondents got an awareness through Email.

40 percentage of the respondents purchase products through social media and websites/ blogs , 12 percentage of the respondents purchase products through multimedia advertising and 8 percentage from Email.

50 of the respondents influencing by social media digital channel to buy products , 36 percentage of the respondents influencing by websites, 10 percentage of the respondents influencing by multimedia and 4 percentage of the respondents influencing by Email digital channel to buy the products.

3. Kinds of Products Purchasing from Digital Channel.

Particulars	Sources	No. of respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
What kind of product would you prefer to buy through digital channel?	Convenience goods	10	20	20
	Shopping goods	31	62	82
	Specialty goods	9	18	100
	Total	50		

Source: Primary data

The above table inferred that, 62 percentage of the respondents purchase shopping goods from digital channels, 20 percentage of the respondents purchase convenience goods from digital channels and 18 percentage of the respondents purchase specialty goods from digital channels.

4. Satisfaction and Impact of Customers on Digital Marketing.

Particulars	Sources	No. of respondents	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Does digital channel change your opinion towards the buying decision ?	Strongly agree	18	36	36
	Agree	15	30	66
	Neutral	5	10	76
	Disagree	6	12	88
	Strongly disagree	6	12	100
	Total	50		
Are you satisfied with the product bought using digital channel?	Strongly agree	12	24	24
	Agree	20	40	64
	Neutral	10	20	84
	Disagree	8	16	100
	Strongly disagree	0	0	100
	Total	50		
How often you buy products using digital channel?	Frequently	9	18	18
	Sometimes	18	36	54
	Rarely	15	30	84
	Never	8	16	100
	Total	50		

Source: Primary data

The above table inferred that, 36 percentage of the respondents strongly agree that digital channel change the customer opinion towards the buying decision. 40 percentage of the respondents agree that they are satisfied with the product bought using digital channel. 36 percentage of the respondents sometimes using digital channel to buy products.

Testing of Hypotheses

Chi – Square Test

1. Relationship between Educational Qualification and Awareness about Digital Marketing

Digital media Qualification	Social media	Websites / blogs	Multimedia advertising	Email	Total
12 th std	3	5	0	0	8
UG	9	11	4	5	29
PG	2	4	4	3	13
Total	14	20	8	8	50

It is clear from the above table that most of the respondents who are aware about digital market are graduate and post graduate.

X 2 test			
Calculated value	Degree of freedom	Level of significance	Table value
40.923	8	0.05	15.51

According to the above analysis , null hypothesis were rejected . There is significant relationship between educational qualification and awareness about digital market.

2. Relationship between Monthly Income and Kinds of product prefer to buy through digital channels .

Types of goods & income	Convenience goods	Shopping goods	Specialty goods	Total
Below 10,000	6	10	1	17
10000-20,000	2	7	1	10
20,000-30,000	1	2	5	8
30,000 and above	1	12	2	15
Total	10	31	9	50

It is clear from the above table that most of the respondents purchase shopping goods and their income group is less than Rs.10,000 and Rs. 10,000 – 20,000 and from above 30,000.

X 2 test			
Calculated value	Degree of freedom	Level of significance	Table value
58.9	6	0.05	12.59

Based on the result null hypothesis were rejected. There is significant relationship between educational qualification and awareness about digital market.

3. Relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Product buy through Digital Channel .

Level of satisfaction & types of channel	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total
Social media	4	5	0	0	0	9
Websites/ blog	9	16	1	0	0	24
Multimedia advertising	2	4	1	1	0	5
Emails	5	0	1	1	0	7
Total	20	25	3	2	0	50

It is evident from the table that most of the respondents are agree and strongly agree and they buy product through websites/blogs .

X 2 test			
Calculated value	Degree of freedom	Level of significance	Table value
67.122	12	0.05	21.03

Based on the result null hypothesis were rejected .There is significant relationship between customer satisfaction and buying the products through digital channel.

Findings of the Study

This study reveals that,most of the customers are aware of digital marketing through social media and advertisement. These mediums are highly influencing the customers to buy products through digital channel. Most of the customers are preferred to buy shopping goods through online and customers are satisfied with the buying. Digital market have greater impact on the customers. Based on the hypotheses testing, it is found that there is a significant relationship between educational qualification and awareness about digital marketing and kinds of product prefer to buy through digital channels.

Conclusion

This study is conducted in particular region and findings reveals that people who educated are more aware of digital channel and prefer digital channels to buy different kinds of products. Mostly shopping goods are preferred to by peoples and rise in buy convenience goods through digital channel. Monthly income of the people play an important role to buy different kind of product through digital channel and customer are satisfied with the products brought through digital channel. Future study to analysis the impact of digital channels o customers on customer purchase decision for a wide geographic area to obtain more accurate results.

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THE IMPACT OF SELECTED MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES ON NSE 50 STOCK PRICES

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Abstract

Stock market performance is considered as the reflector of financial and economic conditions of a country. Since 1980's, the dynamic linkage between macroeconomic variables and stock prices has fetched increasing amount of attention from economists, financial analysts, investors and policy makers.

The relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock prices has been the focus of an immense body of theoretical and empirical research since the 19th century. The debate over the decades has been whether the movement in stock prices leads to the change in economic activity or it is one of the causes of change. Stock prices can be considered as an indicator of a country's economic status and social mood and are seen as a leading indicator of the real economic activity. This research examines the relation between selected macroeconomic variables and closing price of nifty 50. Experimental results show that short run and long run equilibrium relationship exists between the independent variables like Wholesale price index, call money rate, exchange rate, IIP and the dependent variable which are the stock prices in the NSE. The data was collected from FY'06 to FY'17.

Key words – Stock market, IIP, FII, Exchange rates, NSE

1.Introduction

The Indian stock market plays a pivotal role in the growth of Indian economy. Its every movement puts an impact on the performance of the economy. The stock market is a place at where investors, whether Indians or foreigners can invest or take the funds for capital appreciation. Their decision to invest or withdraw the funds depends upon the numerous factors. The various proponents opined that the macroeconomic variables are the one of them. Macroeconomics is the analysis of the nation's economy as a whole. Many researchers have said that stock returns vary due to changes in macroeconomic factors. Although the precise cause and effect relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock prices is not known, they are believed to be related. Furthermore, evidence of stock return predictability using macroeconomic variables for emerging markets is rather scarce whilst such evidence is extensively available for the developed economies.

The aim of this study is to investigate the long run relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock prices for the emerging Indian stock market. This is done by taking closing prices of all the companies in the National Stock

Exchange(NSE) from the period 2006 to 2017 and the data is taken monthly wise. All the data of the variables are collected from the RBI website. The base year for all of the variables is 2001-02. Macroeconomic variables such as Index of Industrial Production(IIP), call money rate, exchange rates, Wholesale Price Index(WPI) and Foreign Institutional Investment(FII) have been taken as some of the major determinants of stock prices in this research. The Wholesale Price Index (WPI) is the price of a representative basket of wholesale goods. Country like Philippines use WPI changes as a central measure of inflation. But now India has adopted new CPI to measure inflation. However, United States now report a producer price index instead. Hence, it is important to understand how these variables relate to the stock market and specifically their potential impact on stock price formation. Another macroeconomic variable is Foreign Institutional Investment which can have impact on stock prices. There are a number of studies which have investigated the relationship between exchange rate movements and stock returns using data from developed markets. Finance theory as well as prior empirical evidence suggests that shocks to macroeconomic variables should affect stock market returns; indeed, several multifactor asset pricing models, such as the arbitrage pricing theory, have been developed on the basis of this assumption. Previous studies have assumed either perfect integration among markets whereby share returns have a linear relation with a number of global factors (e.g. Ferson and Harvey, 1994; Dumas and Solnik, 1995; Harvey, 1995) or complete segmentation with share returns determined by local economic variables (e.g. Chen et al., 1986; Ahmed and Imam, 2007; Mahmood and Dinniah, 2009)

2. Literature Review

Many academic researchers, financial and industry analysts and practitioners have tried to envisage the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock market movements from the past decades. They have done several empirical and descriptive studies to check the effect of macroeconomic variables on stock prices or vice versa and the existing relationship between the two. The different conclusions have been provided by the various conducted studies according to the selection of variables, methodologies, techniques and tests used.

Many studies have been conducted to find out the determinants of changes in stock prices in nifty. Usually various measures were used to analyze the stock prices like exchange rate, IIP, FII, WPI and call money rate. There are a number of studies which have investigated the relationship between exchange rate movements and stock returns using data from developed markets.

Aggarwal, P. and Kumar, M. M. (2012) analyzed the relationship between stock prices and macroeconomic variables in India and US, using monthly frequency data from January 1994 to December 2011. Nifty and S&P 500 were used to represent the stock prices of India and US, respectively, and the macroeconomic variables used for the study include foreign institutional investment (FII), exchange rate, gold price/ (10 gm), fiscal deficit, industrial production index (IIP), inflation (WPI), interest rate and

gross domestic product (GDP). Cointegration technique was adopted as the methodology. The results suggested that the macroeconomic variables have a significant impact on stock prices.

Singh (2014) examined the relationship between macroeconomic variables and the Indian stock market. The methodology employed was multivariate stepwise regression analysis and Granger's causality test, using monthly frequency data from January 2011 to December 2012. The variables used for the study include the average monthly closing price of BSE Sensex and S&P CNX Nifty and the explanatory variables were the Index of Industrial Production (IIP), Wholesale Price Index (WPI), Money Supply (M3), Interest Rates (IR), Trade Deficit (TD), Foreign Institutional Investment (FII), Exchange rate (ER), Crude Oil Price (CP) and Gold Price (GP). The result showed significant impact of macroeconomic variables on the Indian stock market. The gold prices have its negative impact on the stock market. Further, the study proves that the Indian Stock market improves with the increase in the inflow of foreign investment.

Also, the exchange rate shows its adverse effect on the stock market during the study period.

Hojatallah and Ramanarayana opined on the impact of Foreign Institutional Investment on the Indian Stock Market Volatility during the World Financial Crisis. The Engle-Granger, Johansen and Granger tools were used to inspect the cointegration and causality between the Foreign Institutional Investment and NSE 50. The monthly data were employed to get the results. It has been found that NSE 50 and FII were cointegrated with each other and bilateral causality exists. So the investors, institutional investors, etc. can use the available information of one variable to predict about the performance of the second variable.

Another macroeconomic variable of interest is the exchange rate since currency movements expose firms to substantial financial risks. There are a number of studies which have investigated the relationship between exchange rate movements and stock returns using data from developed markets.² In the case of developing countries, Abdalla and Murinde (1997) investigate the interactions between exchange rates and stock prices in the emerging financial markets of India, Korea, Pakistan and the Philippines. Using the cointegration and Granger tests, they report unidirectional causality from exchange rates to stock prices in all the countries, except the Philippines. They also find evidence of a long-run relationship between exchange rates and stock returns for India and Pakistan. More recently, Granger, Huang and Yang (2000) using a BVAR model, examine the relationship between stock prices and exchange rates for nine Asian countries and find mixed results. Whilst their findings suggest no relationship between the stock and the exchange rate for Japan and Indonesia, they find that exchange rates lead stock prices in Korea, whereas stock prices lead exchange rates in Hong Kong, Malaysia, Thailand and Taiwan. Grambovas (2003) too examines the interaction between exchange rate fluctuations and equity prices. Using data from three European emerging financial markets including Greece, the Czech Republic and Hungary, Grambovas finds a strong link between foreign exchange and capital markets in Greece and Hungary.

The relationship between stock prices and trading volume has also received considerable attention and numerous studies have empirically examined the sensitivity of stock returns to the changes in the trading volume. There are at least four reasons why the price/volume relationship is important. First, as Karpoff (1987) suggests, price-volume relationship provides useful insights into the market characteristics. Second, the price/volume relationship is useful for event studies because if price and volume are jointly determined, then incorporating the price/volume relationship would increase the power of the tests. Third, the price/volume relationship is critical for the debate about the empirical distribution of speculative prices.

Numerous studies provide results in support of a contemporaneous relationship between changes in share prices and variations in macroeconomic variables (Bilson et al., 2001; Fifield et al., 2002; Fifield and Power, 2006) and a relationship between current changes in share prices and past changes in macroeconomic variables (Fama, 1981; Chen et al., 1986; Rapach et al., 2005). Various econometric techniques such as cointegration (Nasseh and Strauss, 2000; Acikalin et al., 2008), VAR (Abugri, 2008) and Granger causality analysis (Wongbangpo and Sharma, 2002) have been applied. However, different sets of macroeconomic variables have been found to be significantly related to equity values in different stock markets. For example, Poon and Taylor (1991) found that the macroeconomic variables that influenced UK returns were different from those that determined US equity price changes. Humpe and Macmillan (2009) found a long-run relationship between share prices and three economic variables (i.e. industrial production, the interest rate and long term interest rates) in the US market, but a long-run relationship between share prices and two economic variables (i.e. industrial production and MS) in the Japanese market. More recently, Birzand Lott (2011) examined news about GDP growth, unemployment, retail sales and durable goods, and found that only news about GDP growth and unemployment significantly affected stock returns in the US.

Similarly, there is mixed evidence regarding the nature of the relationship between particular economic factors and share returns. For example, some studies have documented a negative relationship between share price changes and inflation (Fama, 1981; Chen et al., 1986); while others have reported a positive association between share prices and inflation in hyper-inflationary environments in countries such as Argentina, Chile, Mexico and Venezuela (Choudhry, 2001). Wongbangpo and Sharma (2002) suggested that the reason for a positive association between the two variables in hyper-inflationary economies is that share prices act as a hedge against inflation. However, Sing and Low (2000) and Zhou et al. (2005) called this reasoning into question by suggesting that equity investments are poor hedges against inflation. The evidence from existing studies on the relationship of the exchange rate and MS with share prices is also mixed.

3. Problem Statement:

The problem is to find out how does some of the selected macroeconomic variables affect the stock prices of NSE 50 from the year 2006 to 2017.

4. Objectives of the study:

- Primary Objective: To identify the macroeconomic variables
- Secondary Objective: To investigate the relationship that exist between the independent variables which are the selected macroeconomic variables and the dependent variable, the stock prices of the firms listed in NSE 50.

5. Significance of the study:

The present study is expected to add several primary contributions to the existing literature. First, it will add to the present literature by examining the relationship of the stock market with a set of macroeconomic variables in emerging markets like India, in the present context. This study is expected to offer some insights for Indian policymakers, investors, researchers and portfolio managers. Investors may be able to make informed decisions based on macroeconomic dynamics and it is possible for them to decide the ideal time to buy and sell the stocks. It also helps to identify what all economic factors should be considered before buying the stock. The study will be advantageous to know the relationship of prices and economic activity; the direction of the outcome of the relationship may enhance the predictive ability of policy makers; thus, both contractions and expansion of the Indian economy may be forecasted and predicted with some degree of certainty. Policymakers are mainly interested in exploring the determinants of the stock market, and how stock market reflects the changes in domestic and international macroeconomic variables of the economy, thus, the study will provide them a background to determine the variables, which are expected to influence the stock market. Moreover, economic theory suggests that stock prices should reflect expectations about future corporate performance, and the corporate profits generally reflect the level of economic activities. If stock prices accurately reflect the underlying fundamentals, then the stock prices should be considered as the leading indicators of future economic activities, and not the other way around. Therefore, the study of the causal relations and dynamic interactions between macroeconomic variables and stock prices will help in the formulation of the nation's macroeconomic policy. Further, the study will provide an insight to researchers for future research in the area.

6. Scope of the study:

The study suggests further scope for the research to increase the understanding about the dynamic relationship between the macroeconomic variables and stock prices in India. Further research may either eliminate some of the limitations or expand the scope of relationship already done in the present research. Future work might re-examine the issues addressed in this research using a relatively more comprehensive data set (i) including more recent share price data; and

(ii) the data of major leading stock indices of developed economics can also be included. This research would be particularly valuable as a more recent time period and inclusion of share prices of developed economies will give a better insight to predict the movement of share prices by tracking the changes in leading share markets of the world. Examining how the developed markets of the UK and the US affect the emerging markets like India could be valuable.

7. Research Methodology

Research Design:

The type of research adopted is quantitative study and it has a clear statement of the problem and the hypothesis.

Sample Design

Population: The Stock Prices of the companies listed in the NSE Sample: Closing price of Nifty Stock Prices from the year 2006 to 2017. Sampling Framework: The secondary data collected from RBI website

Tools of data analysis:

Linear regression, unit root, Johansen cointegration, vector Autoregression Estimate and Granger causality test are the analysis used for this data analysis and is done using SPSS software and Eviews.

Variables definition:

➤ Dependent Variable:

The closing price of stock prices is a very important measure to determine how macroeconomic variables have an impact on stock prices. It represents the weighted average of 50 Indian company stocks in 12 sectors and is one of the two main stock indices used in India.

➤ Independent Variables:

1. IIP

The index of Industrial Production(IIP) is the overall production in the industrial sector for a given period of time. It measures the level of economic activity in an Indian economy. On the basis of sector, it is categorized into three segments. They are manufacturing, mining & quarrying and electricity. The base year taken is 2001-02.

2. Call money rate

It is the rate at which short term funds are borrowed and lent in the money market. Some of the participants of the call money market are RBI, banks, and primary dealers.

3. FII

Foreign Institutional Investment is an investment made by an investor in the securities or markets of foreign nation. The stock prices can vary if there are huge flows of foreign investments in India. This can be done only if the companies get registered in the stock exchanges of India.

4. WPI

Wholesale Price Index(WPI) is the price of the representative basket of wholesale goods. Some studies have shown that changes in WPI have changed the stock prices in the Indian stock market.

5. Exchange rate

It is a medium of financial transactions between the countries. The entire import and export process of any country depends upon the exchange rate of his currency. If, the country currency will depreciate immediately increase its import value and decrease its exports value or vice versa.

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were framed which need to be tested.

H01: There is no significant relation between the “IIP” and “Nifty stock prices”

H02: There is no significant relation between the “call money rate” and “Nifty stock prices”

H03: There is no significant relation between the “FII” and “Nifty stock prices”.

H04: There is no significant relation between the “WPI” and “Nifty stock prices”.

H05: There is no significant relation between the “exchange rate” and “Nifty stock prices”.

8. Analysis and Interpretation

Monthly data are chosen to avoid spurious correlation problem often found in the quarterly and the annual data. However, the choice of monthly data was constrained by the fact that the variables used in this study were available only at monthly intervals. First the descriptive statistics was done. Then, the data was tested for stationarity and checked whether the variables are cointegrated or not. Finally, the Vector Autoregression Estimate was done to check the probability of cointegration.

Descriptive Statistics

Table8.1 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Nifty	134	2755.10	8901.85	5680.4627	1697.39036
IIP	134	108.8	198.7	160.305	20.9872
Call money rate	134	.05	9.00	4.9000	1.84346
FII	134	19921.000000	28630.000000	1161.62064263	4404.163941672
WPI	134	104.9	185.9	149.981	26.9123
Exchange rate	134	39.3200	68.6160	52.495905	9.0447668
Valid N (list wise)	134				

The above table shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. It includes the mean, standard deviation, range of observations and the number of observation. The mean value of nifty, IIP, call money rate, FII, WPI, and exchange rate are 5680.4627, 160.305, 4.9000, 1161.62064263, 149.981 and

52.495905 respectively. The standard deviation tells us about the variations of the value from the mean value.

Unit Root Test

The unit root test was used to check the stationarity of the data i.e. to check whether the data has trend or no trend. If the probability value of the variables is less than 0.05, it can be said that the data is stationary and there is no trend. If the probability values of the variables are more than 0.05, then the data is non-stationary and there is trend. The unit root test for all the variables are given in the table.

Nifty

Table 8.2

Null Hypothesis: NIFTY has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant				
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-1.117658	0.7077
Test critical values:	1% level		-3.480038	
	5% level		-2.883239	
	10% level		-2.578420	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.				
Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation				
Dependent Variable: D(NIFTY)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/11/18 Time: 17:58				
Sample (adjusted): 2006M01 2017M01				
Included observations: 133 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
NIFTY(-1)	-0.019171	0.017153	-1.117658	0.2658
C	151.5277	101.2454	1.496638	0.1369
R-squared	0.009445	Mean dependent var		43.04323
Adjusted R-squared	0.001884	S.D. dependent var		332.3997
S.E. of regression	332.0864	Akaike info criterion		14.46359
Sum squared resid	14446862	Schwarz criterion		14.50705
Log likelihood	-959.8288	Hannan-Quinn criter.		14.48125
F-statistic	1.249158	Durbin-Watson stat		2.001770
Prob(F-statistic)	0.265759			

The ADF test in the table 8.2 proved that the variable nifty has a unit root because the probability is greater than 0.05 which is 0.7077. This tells us that we can accept the null hypothesis that the variable nifty has a unit root. The ADF test statistic value is -1.117658 which is lesser than the critical values at 1%,5% and 10% significant level. So we can confirm that the variable nifty is non-stationary.

IIP

Table 8.3				
null Hypothesis: IIP has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant				
Lag Length: 12 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-2.788168	0.0629
Test critical values:	1% level		-3.485115	
	5% level		-2.885450	

	10% level		-2.579598	
*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.				
Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation				
Dependent Variable: D(IIP)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/09/18 Time: 10:16				
Sample (adjusted): 2007M01 2017M01				
Included observations: 121 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IIP(-1)	-0.089904	0.032245	-2.788168	0.0063
D(IIP(-1))	-0.459587	0.081760	-5.621134	0.0000
D(IIP(-2))	-0.213124	0.090436	-2.356627	0.0203
D(IIP(-3))	-0.111346	0.091886	-1.211783	0.2283
D(IIP(-4))	-0.311920	0.089564	-3.482663	0.0007
D(IIP(-5))	-0.333379	0.090583	-3.680355	0.0004
D(IIP(-6))	-0.253030	0.093143	-2.716564	0.0077
D(IIP(-7))	-0.255345	0.094107	-2.713343	0.0078
D(IIP(-8))	-0.334444	0.092433	-3.618241	0.0005
D(IIP(-9))	-0.313067	0.092681	-3.377887	0.0010
D(IIP(-10))	-0.205710	0.097254	-2.115169	0.0367
D(IIP(-11))	-0.251713	0.097008	-2.594769	0.0108
D(IIP(-12))	0.405946	0.087797	4.623687	0.0000
C	16.62599	5.484995	3.031178	0.0031
R-squared	0.769316	Mean dependent var		0.493388
Adjusted R-squared	0.741289	S.D. dependent var		9.876092
S.E. of regression	5.023337	Akaike info criterion		6.174509
Sum squared resid	2700.029	Schwarz criterion		6.497989
Log likelihood	-359.5578	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.305887
F-statistic	27.44912	Durbin-Watson stat		2.136346
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The ADF test in the table 8.3 proved that the variable IIP has a unit root because the probability is greater than 0.05 which is 0.0629. This tells us that we can accept the null hypothesis that the variable IIP has a unit root. The ADF test statistic value is -2.788168 which is lesser than the critical values at 1% and 5% significant level. So we can confirm that the variable IIP is non- stationary.

Call Money Rate

Table 8.4

Null Hypothesis: CALL_MONEY_RATE has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant				
Lag Length: 2 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-2.692343	0.0780
Test critical values:		1% level	-3.480818	
		5% level	-2.883579	
		10% level	-2.578601	
*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.				
Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation				
Dependent Variable: D(CALL_MONEY_RATE)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/11/18 Time: 18:05				
Sample (adjusted): 2006M03 2017M01				
Included observations: 131 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CALL_MONEY_RATE(-1)	-0.202216	0.075108	-2.692343	0.0081
D(CALL_MONEY_RATE(-1))	-0.411831	0.094803	-4.344079	0.0000
D(CALL_MONEY_RATE(-2))	-0.257711	0.085757	-3.005124	0.0032
C	0.985422	0.387124	2.545499	0.0121
R-squared	0.296991	Mean dependent var		-0.001908
Adjusted R-squared	0.280384	S.D. dependent var		1.612558
S.E. of regression	1.367936	Akaike info criterion		3.494541
Sum squared resid	237.6485	Schwarz criterion		3.582334
Log likelihood	-224.8925	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.530215
F-statistic	17.88398	Durbin-Watson stat		1.948874
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The ADF test in the table 4.2.3 proved that the variable call money rate has a unit root because the probability is greater than 0.05 which is 0.0780. This tells

us that we can accept the null hypothesis that the variable call money rate has a unit root. The ADF test statistic value is - 2.692343 which is lesser than the critical values at 1% and 5% significant level. So we can confirm that the variable call money rate is non-stationary.

FII

Null Hypothesis: FII has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant				
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-11.61824	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level		-3.480038	
	5% level		-2.883239	
	10% level		-2.578420	
*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.				
Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation				
Dependent Variable: D(FII)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/11/18 Time: 18:06				
Sample (adjusted): 2006M01 2017M01				
Included observations: 133 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FII(-1)	-1.014921	0.087356	-11.61824	0.0000
C	1171.821	397.9740	2.944467	0.0038
R-squared	0.507488	Mean dependent var		-13.21008
Adjusted R-squared	0.503729	S.D. dependent var		6297.491
S.E. of regression	4436.363	Akaike info criterion		19.64798
Sum squared resid	2.58E+09	Schwarz criterion		19.69144
Log likelihood	-1304.591	Hannan-Quinn criter.		19.66564
F-statistic	134.9836	Durbin-Watson stat		2.001271
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

The ADF test in the table 8.5 proved that the variable FII does not have a unit root because the probability is less than 0.05 which is 0.0000. This tells

us that we can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis that the variable FII has a unit root. The ADF test statistic value is -11.61824 which is greater than the critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% significant level. So we can confirm that the variable FII is stationary.

WPI

Table 8.6

Null Hypothesis: WPI has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant				
Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-1.036198	0.7390
Test critical values:	1% level		-3.480425	
	5% level		-2.883408	
	10% level		-2.578510	
*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.				
Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation				
Dependent Variable: D(WPI)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/11/18 Time: 18:07				
Sample (adjusted): 2006M02 2017M01				
Included observations: 132 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
WPI(-1)	-0.003361	0.003244	-1.036198	0.3020
D(WPI(-1))	0.496206	0.076512	6.485373	0.0000
C	0.813477	0.500419	1.625593	0.1065
R-squared	0.257479	Mean dependent var		0.603788
Adjusted R-squared	0.245967	S.D. dependent var		1.134901
S.E. of regression	0.985492	Akaike info criterion		2.831114
Sum squared resid	125.2841	Schwarz criterion		2.896632
Log likelihood	-183.8535	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.857737
F-statistic	22.36627	Durbin-Watson stat		1.973425

Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		
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The ADF test in the table 8.6 proved that the variable WPI has a unit root because the probability is greater than 0.05 which is 0.7390. This tells us that we can accept the null hypothesis that the variable WPI has a unit root. The ADF test statistic value is -1.036198 which is lesser than the critical values at 1%,5% and 10% significant level. So we can confirm that the variable WPI is non-stationary.

Exchange Rate

Table 8.7

Null Hypothesis:
 EXCHANGE_RATE has
 a unit root Exogenous:
 Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-0.218449	0.9320
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.480038	
5% level	-2.883239	
10% level	-2.578420	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented
 Dickey-Fuller
 Test Equation
 Dependent
 Variable:
 D(EXCHANGE_
 RATE) Method:
 Least Squares

Date: 03/11/18 Time: 18:08				
Sample (adjusted): 2006M01 2017M01				
Included observations: 133 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.

EXCHANGE_RATE(-1)	-0.002878	0.013173	-0.218449	0.8274
C	0.321732	0.700022	0.459604	0.6466
R-squared	0.000364	Mean dependent var		0.170996
Adjusted R-squared	-0.007267	S.D. dependent var		1.354186
S.E. of regression	1.359097	Akaike info criterion		3.466442
Sum squared resid	241.9761	Schwarz criterion		3.509906
Log likelihood	-228.5184	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.484104
F-statistic	0.047720	Durbin-Watson stat		1.883756
Prob(F-statistic)	0.827420			

The ADF test in the table 8.7 proved that the variable exchange rate has a unit root because the probability is greater than 0.05 which is 0.9320. This tells us that we can accept the null hypothesis that the variable exchange rate has a unit root. The ADF test statistic value is - 0.218449 which is lesser than the critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% significant level. So we can confirm that the variable exchange rate is non-stationary.

Johansen Cointegration Test

The Johansen cointegration test was conducted to check whether there is long term relationship between the variables. If the probability values of the variables are less than 0.05, it is proved that there is long term relationship. If the probability values of the variables are more than 0.05, it is proved that there is no long term relationship. The cointegration for all the variables are given below.

Table 4.3.1

Sample (adjusted): 2006M05 2017M01				
Included observations: 129 after adjustments				
Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend				
Series: NIFTY IIP CALL_MONEY_RATE FII WPI EXCHANGE_RATE				
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 4				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.281232	123.2973	95.75366	0.0002
At most 1 *	0.258244	80.69926	69.81889	0.0053
At most 2	0.130645	42.16252	47.85613	0.1542
At most 3	0.088078	24.10202	29.79707	0.1962

At most 4	0.074181	12.20812	15.49471	0.1472
At most 5	0.017407	2.265235	3.841466	0.1323
Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.281232	42.59800	40.07757	0.0255
At most 1 *	0.258244	38.53674	33.87687	0.0129
At most 2	0.130645	18.06050	27.58434	0.4901
At most 3	0.088078	11.89390	21.13162	0.5582
At most 4	0.074181	9.942881	14.26460	0.2157
At most 5	0.017407	2.265235	3.841466	0.1323
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

From Table 8.8 , trace statistic value indicates that there is cointegration among the variables as p-value (0.0002) is less than 0.05 and critical value (95.75366) is less than the trace statistic value (123.2973). Max-Eigen value also indicates there exists cointegration as p-value (0.0255) is less than 0.05 and critical value (40.07757) is less than Max-Eigen statistic (42.59800). We also reject the null hypothesis that there are at most one cointegrated equations. Therefore, both the tests indicate that there exists cointegration among the variables. Hence, there is long term relationship between these variables.

Vector Autoregression Estimates

Table 8.9

Vector Autoregression Estimates	
Date: 03/12/18 Time: 13:45	
Sample (adjusted): 2006M02 2017M01	
Included observations: 132 after	
Adjustments	
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []	
	NIFTY

NIFTY(-1)	0.791803
	(0.08972)
	[8.82480]
NIFTY(-2)	0.136111
	(0.08860)
	[1.53618]
IIP	-2.079539
	(1.91157)
	[-1.08787]
CALL_MONEY_RATE	-35.34945
	(16.0393)
	[-2.20393]
FII	0.025878
	(0.00674)
	[3.84061]
WPI	6.364478
	(3.34890)
	[1.90047]
EXCHANGE_RATE	-0.469832
	(6.29477)
	[-0.07464]
R-squared	0.967417
Adj. R-squared	0.965853
Sum sq. resids	11980709
S.E. equation	309.5895
F-statistic	618.5502
Log likelihood	-940.7563
Akaike AIC	14.35994
Schwarz SC	14.51282
Mean dependent	5722.306
S.D. dependent	1675.355

Table 8.9 tells us about the Vector Autoregression Estimates for all the variables. The VAR model shows that the R-square is 96% which means that 96% of variations can be explained using this model. The model is good and can be projected publically. But with VAR model we cannot predict the significant value. So we estimate it using probability values. The three values of each variable are regression coefficient, standard error and t-statistics.

Table 8.10

System: UNTITLED				
Estimation Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/12/18 Time: 12:33				
Sample: 2005M12 2017M01				
Included observations: 134				
Total system (balanced) observations 134				
	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(1)	-3653.286	690.8973	-5.287741	0.0000
C(2)	21.10594	7.862629	2.684336	0.0082
C(3)	29.25463	9.704183	3.014642	0.0031
C(4)	0.021799	0.017495	1.246004	0.2150
C(5)	40.50942	19.38393	2.089846	0.0386
C(6)	-120.2388	43.73456	-2.749286	0.0068
Determinant residual covariance		710333.8		
Equation: NIFTY = C(1) + C(2)*IIP + C(3)*WPI + C(4)*FII + C(5)				
*EXCHANGE_RATE + C(6)*CALL_MONEY_RATE				
Observations: 134				
R-squared	0.751600	Mean dependent var	5680.463	
Adjusted R-squared	0.741897	S.D. dependent var	1697.390	
S.E. of regression	862.3402	Sum squared resid	95184728	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.255071			

Table 8.10 shows the probability of cointegration. We can see that all the coefficients of variables except FII have probability less than 0.05 which means that we can reject the null hypothesis for all the variables except for FII. The null hypothesis tells us there is no cointegration among the variables. So we can say that all the variables except FII can have impact on nifty.

Granger Causality Test

The granger causality test was done to know which variable influences which other variables. If the probability value is more than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is accepted and if the probability value is less than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is rejected. The granger causality test for the non-stationary and cointegrated variables is shown below.

NIFTY AND IIP

Table 8.11

Sample: 2005M12 2017M01			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
IIP does not Granger Cause NIFTY	132	1.16052	0.3166
NIFTY does not Granger Cause IIP		3.75579	0.0260

From the table , we accept the null hypothesis that IIP does not granger cause nifty but we reject the null hypothesis that nifty does not granger cause IIP. So we can say that nifty can influence IIP.

NIFTY AND CALL MONEY RATE

Table 8.14			
Sample: 2005M12 2017M01			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
CALL_MONEY_RATE does not Granger Cause NIFTY	132	2.49194	0.0868
NIFTY does not Granger Cause CALL_MONEY_RATE		0.61999	0.5396

From the table , both the probability value is more than 0.05 and thus leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which means that both the variables do not influence each other.

NIFTY AND WPI

Table 8.15

Sample: 2005M12 2017M01			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
WPI does not Granger Cause NIFTY	132	1.72682	0.1820
NIFTY does not Granger Cause WPI		0.11421	0.8922

From table 8.11, both the probability value is more than 0.05 and thus leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis which means that both the variables do not influence each other.

NIFTY AND EXCHANGE RATE

Table 8.12

Sample: 2005M12 2017M01			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
EXCHANGE_RATE does not Granger Cause NIFTY	132	5.41485	0.0055
NIFTY does not Granger Cause EXCHANGE_RATE		2.65807	0.0740

From table 8.12, we can see that we can reject the null hypothesis that exchange rate does not granger cause nifty which means that exchange rate can influence nifty. We need to accept the null hypothesis that nifty does not granger cause exchange rate because the probability is greater than 0.05.

9. Findings

- All the variables except FII are non-stationary and has a unit root. So we can say that there is a trend in nifty, IIP, call money rate, WPI and exchange rate.
- The Johansen cointegration test show us that there is cointegration among the variables which indicates that there is long term relationship between these variables.
- The VAR model shows that the R-square is 96% which means that the model is good and can be projected to the population.
- All the coefficients of variables except FII have probability less than 0.05 which indicates that all the variables except FII can have impact on nifty.
- The granger causality test indicates that nifty can have impact on IIP.
- The test also shows us that nifty and call money rate does not influence each other.
- Nifty and WPI also do not influence each other.
- The granger causality test also indicates that exchange rate can have influence on nifty but nifty does not influence exchange rate.

10. Conclusions

This study investigates the short run and the long run equilibrium relationship between a set of macroeconomic variables and stock prices using data for the period 2006 to 2017 from the Indian stock market. This article has analyzed only some of the macroeconomic variables which is one of the limitations of this study. The economic variables comprise Index of Industrial Production, call money rate, Foreign Institutional Investment, Wholesale Price Index and exchange rate. Data Analysis and interpretation were done using SPSS and Eviews software. The unit root tests indicate that only FII does not have unit root. The evidence obtained from the cointegration tests suggests that the variables have long term relationship with nifty stock prices in the Indian stock exchange. But the VAR model suggests FII cannot influence nifty stock prices. The

Granger causality test indicates that exchange rate can have impact on nifty. Overall the model of this study is fit.

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AN ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN TELECOM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The telecom industry is an interesting industry to study, not only due to its volatile nature in terms of technological breakthrough and its policies, but also due to the high growth rate of this industry over the past few decades and the significant contribution of the industry to the economies of the nation. This study has been drafted to portray performance, present trends and future opportunities in the telecom sector of India. It has been seen that the Telecom Sector of India has registered a phenomenal growth during last few years, propelled largely by the unprecedented growth of the mobile telephony and infrastructure which not only is beneficial for the telecom sector but has a multiplier effects over the entire economy. The present study intends to fill the gap about understanding and analyzing the key factors that influence the growth of the telecom industry in a country by using various methods.

Key words: Tele density , ARPU, HSA, PMRTS, VSAT

Telecom is an essential infrastructure for economic development and hence for the improvement of the quality of human life. The use of telephone is in different activities like social and economic, and gathering information and knowledge. From these the highest use goes to social activities. It is used for saving time and expenditure in social and financial contexts. In India people are interested in owning mobile phones. The mobile telephone connection is costly when compared with land phone connections, as the initial capital cost of handset purchase is more. Salaried and business people who are having comparatively high economic status were the most intensive users of mobiles. In the absence of cheaper fixed line services mostly in rural areas, there are increased use of WLL phones and mobile phones. But in such cases there arise problems in the case of range also. As the desired inter locator is reached through telephony, and the telephone is likely to be the quick way for communication, telephone has a considerable advantage over other communication channel in emergencies. Simplicity in access makes telephony more particular in the case of priority requirement for all socio-economic groups.

The telecom services have been very much useful for promotion of employment. They create number of job opportunities in this new field. By the use of internet, doctors are getting consultancy from all over the world. One can interact with another and can receive important tips about a particular case from the experience of the other doctor. With the help of Telephone, producers and the middle men are able to gather information about the availability of raw material, market price and finished products. Telephone is considered as the means for obtaining and sharing information. Public Telephone facilities are useful to the poor also. It can replace the need to travel or postal

costs. High level of use of telephone for Social networking implies that most of the rural areas are in need of subsidized access. Wider access to internet service is possible through the expansion of telecommunications connectivity. Households in most contexts tend to spend, on average, between 2 per cent and 4 per cent of house hold income on telecommunications. The use of telephone for the acquisition of information and knowledge was very low till the introduction of availability of internet through phones.

Most of the developing countries are facing the growth phase of telecom sector, because of the technology changes in accordance with the local geography. At the primary stage the numbers of mobile phone connections are lower than the number of land phone connections in developing countries. After 1995 most of the developing countries are facing rapid growth in the cell phone penetration. While considering the technological development in the telecom sector, India is late starter. India is the fourth largest telecom market in Asia after China, Japan and South Korea. The Indian telecom network is the 8th largest in the world and the second largest among the developing economies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The telecom industry is an interesting industry to study, not only due to its volatile nature in terms of technological breakthrough and its policies, but also due to the high growth rate of this industry over the past few decades and the significant contribution of the industry to the economies of the nation.

This study has been drafted to portray the history & evolution, present trends and future opportunities in the telecom sector of India. It has been seen that the Telecom Sector of India has registered a phenomenal growth during last few years, propelled largely by the unprecedented growth of the mobile telephony and infrastructure which not only is beneficial for the telecom sector but has a multiplier effects over the entire economy. In this Project intends to fill the gap about understanding and analyzing the key factors that influence the growth of the telecom industry in a country by using various methods.

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the research study are:-

- To examine telecom sector's performance in India
- To identify the recent trends in pricing on telecom sector in India

METHODOLOGY

The present study is based on secondary data obtained from the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI), Department of Telecommunication (DoT) and the reports from Government of India and other sources. Different telecom magazines, newspapers and journals were consulted for gathering of information. Information was also collected by holding discussions and interviews with knowledgeable persons employed at different levels in various telecom companies of India. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, year- wise annual growth of the industry in its various segments, percentage share of different service providers per year were calculated

Average Revenue per User (ARPU) per month = 4.

1/3*x Qrtly Revenue adjusted for interconnect usage charges and roaming settlement charges

Average subscribers during the quarter

Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) per month for wireless service declined from 81.69 during the year 2017 to ` 70.55 during the year 2018, thereby showing a yearly decline rate of 13.65%.

The following table presents the ARPU per month for various categories of circles and various platforms for payment viz. post-paid and pre-paid.

1.3.2 Average Subscriber Outgo per outgoing minute for usage from Home Service Area (HSA)

The tariff plans are of bundled nature and the trade-off is generally between monthly fixed charges and variable (call) charges. Therefore, average subscriber outgo per outgoing minute for usage from Home Service Area (HSA) as defined below would be a realistic indicator of average tariff levels.

Average Subscriber Outgo per Outgoing Minute for usage from HSA22.

C. Average Subscriber Outgo per outgoing minute for usage from Home Service Area (HSA)

= Rental revenue + Revenue from outgoing calls from HSA

No. of outgoing minutes from HAS

This analysis has been prepared based on the information furnished by the Service Providers. It is also available on TRAI's website (www.traai.gov.in under the link <http://www.traai.gov.in/release-publication/reports/performanceindicators-reports>).

In this analysis, Tele-density is based on the population projections from census data published by the Office of Registrar General & Census Commissioner of India

The Report has been prepared based on the information furnished by the Service Providers. The number of telephone subscribers in India increased from 1,190.67 million at the end of Dec-17 to 1,197.87 million at the end of Dec-18, registering a yearly growth rate of 0.60%.

Table 1

Tele Subscriber

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Figure 1

Year ending	Subscriber Base (million)			Teledensity		
	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Overall
2015	435.75	600.66	1036.41	49.94	152.45	81.83
2016	468.64	683.14	1151.78	53.27	170.15	89.90
2017	502.42	688.25	1190.67	56.66	168.29	91.90
2018	531.59	666.28	1197.87	59.50	159.98	91.45

Trend of Tele-density in India Tele-Density (%)

Table2
Wireline Subscriber Base & Teledensity - Rural & Urban

Year ending	Subscriber Base (in million)			Wireline Teledensity		
	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Overall
Dec-15	4.53	20.99	25.52	0.52	5.33	2.01
Dec-16	3.86	20.55	24.40	0.44	5.12	1.90
Dec-17	3.42	19.81	23.23	0.39	4.84	1.79
Dec-18	3.11	18.76	21.87	0.35	4.50	1.67

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Total Wireline subscriber base declined from 23.23 million at the end of Dec-17 to 21.87 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly decline rate of 5.88%. Rural wireline subscriber base has shown decline of 9.06%, from 3.42 Million at the end of Dec-17 to 3.11 Million at the end of Dec-18. During the same period, Urban wireline subscription also recorded decline of 5.33%, from 19.81 million to 18.76 million. Overall Wireline Teledensity declined from 1.79 at the end of Dec-17 to 1.67 at the end of Dec-18. During the same period urban wireline teledensity declined from 4.84 to 4.50 and Rural Wireline Teledensity also declined from 0.39 to 0.35.

Figure 2

Trend of Wireline Tele-density (rural-urban)

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Trend of Wireline Tele-density (rural-urban)

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Village Public Telephones (VPTs)

There are 5, 93,731 inhabited villages in India as per census 2001. At the end of Dec-18, 22.30% of the total inhabited villages in India have been connected by VPTs. Number of VPTs declined from 2, 02,395 at the end of Dec-17 to 1, 32,403 at the end of Dec-18 with yearly decline rate of 34.58%. As per the information received in TRAI as on December, 2018, only M/s BSNL is providing VPT service in India.

The following chart depicts the trend of number of VPTs in India during last four years

Figure 3
Trend of Number of VPTs in India

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Table 3
Trend of Internet subscriber base
 Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance

Segment	Mode of Access								Total Subscribers (in million)	
	Wired Subscribers (in million)		Wireless Subscribers (in million)							
			Fixed Wireless (Wi-Fi, Wi-Max, Radio & VSAT)		Mobile Wireless (Phone + Dongle)		Total Wireless			
	Dec-17	Dec-18	Dec-17	Dec-18	Dec-17	Dec-18	Dec-17	Dec-18	Dec-17	Dec-18
Broadband	17.86	18.17	0.44	0.43	344.57	506.76	345.01	507.19	362.87	525.36
Narrowband	3.43	3.26	0.01	0.01	79.65	75.59	79.66	75.60	83.09	78.86
Total	21.28	21.42	0.45	0.44	424.22	582.35	424.67	582.79	445.96	604.21

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

This section summarizes information submitted by 326 operators for the year ending 2018. Part-I consists of information of Internet service (both narrowband and broadband), Part-II consists of broadband service and Part-III covers narrowband service.

Part-I: Internet Service (broadband + narrowband)

As per reports received from operators, total number of internet subscribers increased from 445.96 million at the end of Dec-17 to 604.21 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 35.49%. Out of total 604.21 million internet subscribers, number of broadband subscribers is 525.36 million and number of narrowband subscribers is 78.86 million at the end of Dec-18.

Wireless Internet subscribers increased from 424.67 million at the end of Dec-17 to 582.79 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 37.23%. Wired Internet subscribers increased from 21.28 million at the end of Dec-17 to 21.42 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 0.66%. Number of Broadband subscribers increased from 362.87 million at the end of Dec-17 to 525.36 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 44.78%. However, the number of Narrowband subscribers declined from 83.09 million at the end of Dec-17 to 78.86 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly decline rate of 5.09%.

The following charts present the composition of Internet Subscribers by mode of access and composition of Broadband & Narrowband subscription.

Figure 4.4
 Composition of Internet subscription as on 31 December, 2018

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

More than 96% of total internet subscribers use wireless mobile technology to access internet services. 34 Indian telecom sector (third edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators Out of total internet subscription, the share of broadband subscription is 86.95% and the share of narrowband subscription is only 13.05% as on 31 December, 2018. The following chart depicts the composition of market share of broadband and narrowband subscriptions.

Figure 5
Composition of Broadband & Narrowband subscription as on 31 December, 2018

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Number of rural internet subscribers increased from 132.03 million at the end of Dec-17 to 213.30 million at the end of Dec-18 and the number of urban internet subscribers increased from 313.92 million to 390.91 million during the same period.

Out of 525.36 million broadband subscribers, number of rural broadband subscribers is 173.30 million and number of urban broadband subscribers is 352.06 million.

Out of 78.86 million narrowband subscribers, number of rural narrowband subscribers is 40.00 million and number of urban narrowband subscribers is 38.86 million.

Public Mobile Radio Trunk Services (PMRTS)

The subscriber base of Public Mobile Radio Trunk Service (PMRTS) increased from 54,233 at the end of Dec-17 to 57,784 at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 6.55%. Detailed table on Service Area wise subscriber base of PMRTS is below.

M/s Arya Omnitalk Radio Trunking Services Pvt. Ltd. is the market leader in PMRTS with 83.28% share of total subscription as on 31 December, 2018.

Public Mobile Radio Trunk Services (PMRTS)

The subscriber base of Public Mobile Radio Trunk Service (PMRTS) increased from 54,233 at the end of Dec-17 to 57,784 at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 6.55%.

Detailed table on Service Area wise subscriber base of PMRTS is below.

Table 4

PMRTS Subscriber base - Service Provider wise

Sl. No.	Name of the Service Provider	Subscriber Base as on 31.12.2017	Subscriber Base as on 31.12.2018	Net Addition in Subscribers %	Market share as on 31.12.2018
1	Arya Omnitalk Radio Trunking Services Pvt.Ltd.	45290	48121	2831	83.28
2	Procall Ltd.	3054	3218	164	5.57
3	Inative Networks Pvt Ltd	1820	1820	0	3.15
4	Quick Call	1618	2065	447	3.57
5	Smartlink Pvt Ltd	968	968	0	1.68
6	Bhilwara Telenet Services Pvt Ltd	818	870	52	1.51
7	Wiwanet Solutions Pvt Ltd	361	361	0	0.62
8	Airtalk Solutions & Services Pvt Ltd	304	361	57	0.62
	Total	54,233	57,784	3,551	100

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

M/s Arya Omnitalk Radio Trunking Services Pvt. Ltd. is the market leader in PMRTS with 83.28% share of total subscription as on 31 December, 2018.

Figure 6

Trend of number of PMRTS subscribers

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT)

The total number of Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT) subscribers increased from 2,71,881 at the end of Dec-17 to 2,87,424 at the end of Dec-18. Net addition in VSAT subscribers during the year 2018 has been 15,543 at the yearly growth rate of 5.72%.

Hughes Communication Limited continues to be the market leader with subscriber base of 1,03,168 followed by Bharti Airtel Ltd (79,604) at the end of Dec-18

Table 5
VSAT Service Providers currently providing service & their
subscriber base

Sl.No.	Name of the Service Provider	Subscriber base at the Quarter ending		Net Addition during the year 2018	Market Share (%) Dec-18
		Dec-17	Dec-18		
1	Hughes Communications Ltd.	98995	103168	4173	35.89%
2	Bharti Airtel Limited	72933	79604	6671	27.70%
3	Tatanet Services	55973	67584	11611	23.51%
4	HCL Comnet	21961	18154	-3807	6.32%
5	BSNL	19254	16307	-2947	5.67%
6	Infotel Satcom	2691	2533	-158	0.88%
7	Cloudcast Digital (earthwhile Planetcast Media Services)	74	74	0	0.03%
Total		271881	287424	15543	100.00%

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

M/s Tatanet Service has recorded maximum net addition of 11,611 subscribers followed by M/s Bharti Airtel Ltd (6, 671 subscribers) during the year 2018.

Figure 7

Trend of Number of VSAT Subscribers

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

The chart shows depicts % break-up of outgoing minutes from Home Service Area to inter-circles and intra-circles for wireless service:

Revenue

1/3*Qly Revenue adjusted for interconnect usage charges and roaming settlement charges

Average subscribers during the quarter

Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) per month for wireless service declined from 81.69 during the year 2017 to 70.55 during the year 2018, thereby showing a yearly decline rate of 13.65%.

Figure 8
Percentage break-up of outgoing minutes from Home Service Area (HSA) during the year 2018

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

The following table presents the ARPU per month for various categories of circles and various platforms for payment viz. post-paid and pre-paid.

Table 4.6
Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) per month

Category	Postpaid		Prepaid		Blended	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
Circle A	403.30	335.54	73.82	68.90	92.02	82.54
Circle B	387.04	305.79	67.54	57.64	75.28	62.86
Circle C	308.15	233.39	66.96	61.02	72.65	65.05
Metro	365.20	316.67	41.70	28.62	84.69	68.44
All India	381.33	315.59	67.22	59.42	81.69	70.55

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) per month for postpaid service declined from 381 during the year 2017 to 316 during the year 2018. ARPU per month for prepaid service also declined from during the 67 year 2017 to 59 during the year 2018.

The following chart presents the Quarterly trend for ARPU per month during the year 2017 and 2018.

Figure 9

Quarterly Trend of ARPU per month of Wireless Service

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

From the above table that, composition of ARPU declined in all segments except rental revenue and average revenue from data usage in the year 2018 as compare to the year 2017. Per month ARPU for wireless data usage increased from 27.50 during the year 2017 to 41.05 during the year 2018. On the other hand, per month ARPU for voice call declined from 32.08 to 13.55 during the same period.

Table 7

Composition of Average Revenue Per User (ARPU) per month

Sl. No.	Item	Revenue (excl. service tax) per subscriber per month for the Year 2017 (₹)	Revenue (excl. service tax) per subscriber per month for the Year 2018 (₹)
1	Rental Revenue	19.63	22.99
2	Revenue from calls	32.08	13.55
3	Revenue from SMS	2.02	1.40
4	Revenue from data usage	27.50	41.05
5	Revenue from VAS	3.95	2.68
6	Other revenue	2.32	2.25
7	Revenue from Outroamers (outside HSA)	3.77	1.78
8	Total revenue from subscribers (1+2+3+4+5+6+7)	91.28	85.69
9	Net inter-operable settlement charges receivable	-9.89	-15.14
10	Net Revenue (ARPU) (8+9)	81.39	70.55

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

As can be seen in the above table, composition of ARPU declined in all segments except rental revenue and average revenue from data usage in the year 2018 as compare to the year 2017. Per month ARPU for wireless data usage increased from 27.50 during the year 2017 to 41.05 during the year 2018. On the other hand, per month ARPU for voice call declined from 32.08 to 13.55 during the same period.

The following chart presents the comparison of share of Revenue as a percentage of total Revenue during the year 2018

Figure10
Composition of Revenue of wireless Service during the year 2018

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

It may be seen in the above chart that revenue from data usage comprises about 48% of total revenue from wireless services during the year 2018.

Average Subscriber Outgo per outgoing minute for usage from Home Service Area (HSA)

The tariff plans are of bundled nature and the trade-off is generally between monthly fixed charges and variable (call) charges. Therefore, average subscriber outgo per outgoing minute for usage from Home Service Area (HSA) as defined below would be a realistic indicator of average tariff levels.

Average Subscriber Outgo per Outgoing Minute for usage from HSA22

$$= \frac{\text{Rental revenue} + \text{Revenue from outgoing calls from HAS}}{\text{No. of outgoing minutes from HSA}}$$

The table below provides the Average Outgo (tariff) per Outgoing Minute for usage from Home Service Area (HSA).

Table 8

Category-wise Average Subscriber Outgo (tariff) per outgoing minute from Home Service Area for wireless Service

Category	Postpaid		Prepaid		Blended	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
Circle A	0.44	0.37	0.27	0.13	0.29	0.15
Circle B	0.42	0.36	0.23	0.12	0.24	0.13
Circle C	0.36	0.19	0.20	0.10	0.20	0.10
Metros	0.46	0.37	0.19	0.09	0.24	0.13
All India	0.43	0.35	0.23	0.12	0.25	0.13

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Average subscriber outgo per outgoing minute for wireless service from home service area declined from 0.25 during the year 2017 to 0.13 during the year 2018.

As per information received from the wireless access service providers, number of wireless data subscribers has increased from 424.02 million at the year ending 2017 to 578.20 million at the year ending 2018 with yearly growth rate of 36.36%. The number of wireless data subscribers was 227.91 million at the year ending 2013.

Total number of wireless telephone subscribers was 1176.00 million at the year ending 2018. Out of total number of wireless telephone subscribers, the number of wireless data subscriber was 578.20 million at the year ending 2018. Thereby, share of wireless data subscribers was 49.17% of total wireless telephone subscribers the year ending 2018.

Figure 11:
Trend of total wireless telephone subscribers and total wireless data subscribers

Source of data Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Total volume of wireless data usage increased from 20,092 million GB during the year 2017 to 46,404 million GB during the year 2018 with yearly growth of 131%. Total volume of Wireless data usage comprises of data usage by 2G, 3G, 4G and CDMA data subscribers. Technology-wise distribution of volume of wireless data usage is mentioned in the following table.

Table 4.9
Wireless data usage (in million GB per year)

Year Ending	2G Data Usage	3G Data Usage	4G Data Usage	CDMA Data Usage	Total Value of Data Usage
2014	340	349		138	828
2015	479	700		196	1,375
2016	477	1,221	2,775	169	4,642
2017	423	3,187	16,426	56	20,092
2018	443	5,654	40,304	3	46,404

Source of data: Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

4G technology (LTE – Long Term Technology) was introduced in India during the year 2016. During a short period of time, 4G data technology became the market leader in wireless data usage with total volume of 40,304 million GB during the year 2018.

Out of total volume of wireless data usage of 46,404 million GB in the year 2018, 4G (LTE) technology has the major part of 86.85% with volume of 40,304 million GB. Shares of 2G, 3G and CDMA data usage are 0.95%, 12.18% and 0.01% respectively in total volume of wireless data usage in the year 2018.

There has been a very sharp decline in CDMA data subscribers and data usage due to verge of closure of CDMA technology by the service providers. The numbers of customers availing data services from CDMA service providers are less than 0.01% of the total mobile customers during the year 2018.

Figure 12

Share of technology-wise data usage during the year 2018

Technology:4G

% Share :81.75%

Source of data: Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Technology

The following table depicts the average cost to subscriber for per GB wireless data usage

Table 10

Average cost to subscriber for Per GB wireless data

Year	GSM data cost per GB	CDMA data cost per GB	Total Wireless data cost per GB
2014	289.15	168.48	268.97
2015	243.58	122.20	226.30
2016	74.55	102.42	75.57
2017	19.08	117.24	19.35
2018	11.77	169.67	11.78

Source of data: Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 yearly performance indicators

Average wireless data cost to subscriber has been calculated in respect of total wireless data revenue and volume of total wireless data usage reported by the access service providers.

The average cost to subscriber for wireless data in the year 2014 was 269 per GB and in the year 2015, it was 226 per GB. On introduction of 4G (LTE) technology in India, average cost to subscriber for wireless data usage sharply declined to 75.57 per GB during the year 2016. Further, average cost to subscriber for wireless data declined from 19.35 per GB in the year 2017 to 11.78 per GB in the year 2018.

following chart depicts the trend of average cost to subscriber for per GB wireless data usage during last four years

Figure 13

Trend of Average cost to subscriber for Per GB wireless data

Source of Data: Indian Telecom Sector (Third Edition) 2018 Yearly Performance Indicators

Average cost to subscriber of GSM data shows declining trend over the last four years and it declined from 289 per GB in the year 2014 to 11.78 per GB in the year 2018. CDMA data cost to subscriber shows mixed trend during the same period. However, average cost to subscriber for overall wireless data service shows declining trend over the period.

Declining trend of cost of data to subscriber shows intense market competition in data services in the telecom market. This has led to a situation where even a person living below poverty line can easily afford mobile data service and avail various kinds of Government and commercial services. This has facilitated the financial inclusion of the masses living on the fringe. Accordingly, the Authority has continued with its policy of 'forbearance' in the Telecom Tariff.

The study covers secondary data. For the purpose of collecting the data an effective analysis have been done. The following findings, suggestions and conclusion are the core and end results of the study. This provides the ultimate results for the objectives.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

- According to the 2015 to 2018 study, the teledensity and subscribers in the urban area are more than the rural area
- According to the 2015 to 2018 study, Number of VPTs declined from 2, 02,395 at the end of Dec-17 to 1, 32,403 at the end of Dec-18 with yearly decline rate of 34.58%.
- Total numbers of internet subscribers increased from 445.96 million at the end of Dec-17 to 604.21 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 35.49% and Wireless Internet subscribers increased from 424.67 million at the end of Dec-17 to 582.79 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 37.23%. However, the number of Narrowband subscribers declined from 83.09 million at the end of Dec-17 to 78.86 million at the end of Dec-18 with yearly decline rate of 5.09%.
- The subscriber base of Public Mobile Radio Trund Service (PMRTS) increased from 54,233 at the end of Dec-17 to 57,784 at the end of Dec-18 with yearly growth rate of 6.55%.
- The total number of Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT) subscribers increased from 2, 71,881 at the end of Dec-17 to 2, 87,424 at the end of Dec-18.
- ARPU per month for wireless service declined from 81.69 during the year 2017 to 70.55 during the year 2018, thereby showing a yearly decline rate of 13.65%. And ARPU per month for postpaid service declined from 381 during the year 2017 to 316 during the year 2018.
- ARPU declined in all segments except rental revenue and average revenue from data usage in the year 2018 as compare to the year 2017. And data usage comprises about 48% of total revenue from wireless services during the year 2018.
- The number of wireless data subscribers has increased from 424.02 million at the year ending 2017 to 578.20 million at the year ending 2018 with yearly growth rate of 36.36%. The number of wireless data subscribers was 227.91 million at the year ending 2013.
- Total volume of wireless data usage increased from 20,092 million GB during the year 2017 to 46,404 million GB during the year 2018 with yearly growth of 131%.
- 4G data technology became the market leader in wireless data usage with total volume of 40,304 million GB during the year 2018. And there is a very sharp decline in CDMA data subscribers and data usage due to verge of closure of CDMA technology by the service providers.
- On introduction of 4G (LTE) technology in India, average cost to subscriber for wireless data usage sharply declined to 75.57 per GB during the year 2016. Further, average cost to subscriber for wireless data declined from 19.35 per GB in the year 2017 to 11.78 per GB in the year 2018.
- Average cost to subscriber of GSM data shows declining trend over the last four years and it declined from 289 per GB in the year 2014 to 11.78 per GB in the year

2018. . However, average cost to subscriber for overall wireless data service shows declining trend over the period.

SUGGESTIONS

- The teledensity subscribers and number of village public telephones decline in the urban area are more than the rural area so they should concentrate more on rural area
- Since the Number of Narrowband subscribers are decreased more facilities to should be provided subscribers
- It showing ARPU declined in all segments except rental revenue and average revenue from data usage in the year 2018 as compare to the year 2017. Then TRAI should take better policies to promote ARPU rate of the telecom sectors.
- TRAI should control over the telecom players to fix flexible rate of price and to maintain average cost to subscriber for wireless data usage
- To promote Research and Development, Designing of telecom sector

CONCLUSION

Every functional division and service provider of Telecom Sector of the country is trying to provide world class telecom infrastructure in its area of operation to give services to its customers and so, helping the country to progress in the global scenario in the form of Government Telecom policies.

So it can be concluded that the sector's performance and recent trends in pricing on telecom sector of India has made it a key contributor in India's economic and social up gradation. But according to the 2015 to 2018 the pricing on telecom sectors is decline on the basis of ARPU and then total wireless data cost per GB decreased and increasing use of internet subscribers. The people can available low level priced on internet facility

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**A STUDY ON LOCAL SELF GOVERNMENT:
PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF AUTONOMOUS COUNCILS IN
TRIBAL AREAS OF ASSAM**

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Abstract:

The present paper deals with a unique system of Local self Governance system in the states of north east India, especially in Assam. The Sixth Schedule of the constitution of India indicates the formation of Autonomous District Councils by the Tribal Communities themselves. Several autonomous councils working in this regards to develop the tribal belt of the region. In this context an attempt has been made to point out role/challenges to autonomous councils in developing tribal areas of Assam. The central government has given varying degrees of autonomy to several autonomous administrative divisions of India within the state legislature. The sixth schedule of the Constitution of India is the base for the formation and functions of most of these autonomous councils. Hence they are faced so many challenges such as conflict of power, corruption, and disparity among autonomous bodies and local bodies etc. to autonomous councils in developing tribal areas in Assam. The most important organizational change in the administration is the grant of political autonomy and statehood in North East India. The process of structural setup of local self government goes back to the British Era when the Interim Government of India had appointed a sub-committee to the Constituent Assembly. The Legislations or law passed by the Autonomous councils come into force only after the assent of the Governor of the particular state. The paper discusses the problems of the different autonomous councils of Assam.

Keywords: Historical Background of Local Self Governance, Objectives, Autonomous Council of Tribal Areas, Problems, Suggestions.

Introduction:

Local self governance, in a very simple sense is a government formed by a group of free people to manage and regulate their own occurrence. It is a multi-dimensional organized social institution with a feeling of oneness. In political terms, it is related with the governance of a local area, constituting a political sub-division of a state or other major political organization. On the basis of

performance of its function, it acts as the agent of the state for the realization of democratic values and benefit.

In this regard Laski said that people cannot realize the full benefit of democratic government unless they begin by the admission that all problems in their incidence require decision at the place. The concept and practice of local self governance in India is as old as its history. During ancient Indian's they developed a highly efficient local self government.¹ In the same manner, albeit in varying degree, evidences of self governance are to be seen in almost all the kingdoms of Indian sub-continent. In British India, Ripon took the initiative to give its due place in his scheme of governance, though not in democratic spirit. During the time of independence and in Independent India, Mahatma Gandhi promoted the cause of Local self Governance which now crystallized in the form of Panchayati raj. Panchayati raj was introduced in the country with great usefulness. In 1959 Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh were the first states to adopt the Panchayati Raj System in India.

The tribal areas and states of North East India are inhabited by fairly homogenous group of tribes with mutually exclusive tribal social system. There is a unique system of Local self Government institution in the states of north east India, Especially in Assam. The tribal of the North East India especially Assam have a clear cultural background and they live a life of their own, having a strong tap root in their respective culture and tradition. The Autonomous District Councils (ADCs) are designed to provide for a good amount of autonomy on the tribal population through their elected representatives. Under the Para 2 (1) & Para 6 (A) of Sixth Schedule of the Constitution of India. Their laws of inheritance, marriage and customs of tribal people are much different from the plains people of mainland India. It is the reason why internal autonomy was granted so that they may take their rightful place in the country.

Objectives –

1. To study historical background of local self-government and the six schedule of the Constitution of India.
2. To study about the several autonomous councils in Assam and its powers and functions.
3. To study about the problems faced by autonomous councils in Assam in their development prospect.

Methodology –

Both primary and secondary sources of data have been used for the present study. The major portion of the present study is based mainly on secondary data available in books and journals, relevant books, published and unpublished research papers and different websites have been reviewed. And primary data

are collected through observation, to some extent through discussion with local people, social organization of tribal areas.

Main Discussion -

Historical Background: India as a country of vast cultural and ethnical diversity. It was said that a uniform pattern of local administration that Panchayati raj may not be workable. For this purpose the Cabinet Mission Plan in 1946 indicated that an Advisory Committee be formed to suggest for the formation of a local self-governance for the Minorities, Tribals and some Areas. The Constituent Assembly set up an Advisory Committee which appointed a sub-committee known as the North East Frontier (Assam) Tribal and Excluded Areas Committee under the chairmanship of Gopinath Bordoloi. Thus Bordoloi Committee was formed and it was of wide conviction that the tribals of Assam are historically and culturally different from tribes of other parts of the country. It should be allowed to promote and regulate their own way of life according to their choice. B. R. Ambedkar compared these tribes to that of the Red Indians of America. And he was in favour of adopting a policy which best suited their will and genius. He encouraged towards formation of District Council. Which operates now as Autonomous District Council in north east states of Assam, Meghalaya Tripura and in limited form in Manipur.

The Bordoloi Committee approved that the District Council should have legislative power over the occupation and land, other than land comprising the nature of cultivation of land should be left to the tribes themselves. Financial powers should be allocated to the council. It was remarkable about the Bordoloi report that the manner and the political skill through which it sought to reconcile the hill people's demand for political autonomy with Government of Assam.

The close of the Second World War and its impending departure, the British Government made a departure from its earlier policy of least interference in the personal administration of the hill areas. British govt. tried to consider the means for establishing and developing local government among the hill people. They tried to secure advancement by peaceful and progressive administration, the growth of democratic spirit among tribals. In consultation with the local officers made a number of recommendations. After the independence, the Constitution of India has been enforced on 26 January 1950. According to the specific part and articles of the Constitution of India composition and administration of Autonomous councils have been continuing.

The Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution: Articles 244(2) and 275(1) to the constitution of India contain provisions for the administration of the tribal areas in the states of Assam, Meghalaya, Tripura and Mizoram. Actually it gives permissions for the formation of **autonomous councils** to govern areas which

have been given **autonomy** within their respective states and most of these **autonomous district councils** are located in North East India but two are in the Ladakh region of top most Northern part of India.

The autonomous district can be subdivided into autonomous regions. It is based on if there are different scheduled tribes in it. The Governor had the power to include any area in the list of autonomous areas, create new autonomous districts. The Governor can also unite two or more autonomous districts or parts thereof so as to form one autonomous district and define the boundaries of any autonomous district and he could exclude any area from the list of autonomous district. The Sixth Schedule approves for the formation of Autonomous District Councils by the tribal communities themselves. The strength of the District Council was fixed at a maximum of 24 members. On the basis of adult franchise for a period of five years members are to be directly elected. The Governor was powered to nominate certain number of persons. The numbers appointed by the Governor shall hold office during the pleasure of the Governor. Each district council will have a chairman and a deputy chairman. This act extended the legislative power of the District Council to allotment, occupation or use of land for agriculture and non agriculture purposes, other than categorized as reserved forests, management of unclassified forest, and the use of canal or water courses for the purpose of agriculture, control of Jhumming or other shifting cultivation. The council has also power for appointment of chief or headmen, their successor, inheritance of marriage and all other social customs. The District Councils earn their income from land revenue, forest administration of justice etc.

Autonomous councils of Assam:

In Assam there are several autonomous councils. Which are mentioned bellow-

1. Bodoland Territorial Council.
2. Karbi Anglong Autonomous Council.
3. North Cachar Hills Autonomous Council.
4. Missing Autonomous Council.
5. Rabha Hasong Autonomous Council.
6. Tiwa Autonomous Council.
7. Deori Autonomous Council.
8. Thengal Kachari Autonomous Council.
9. Sonowal Kachari Autonomous Council.

Power and functions of Autonomous District Councils: These **Autonomous District Councils** (ADC) have given the power to enact legislations for the welfare and development of the tribal people of the North East India. The autonomous councils also be described as a 'State in mine nature' because they

have all the paraphernalia of a government like Legislature, Executive and Judiciary. The autonomous councils or ADCs have full freedom to legislate and execute on matters like Land Revenue, Primary Education, and Customary Laws etc. It is assigned to it under the Sixth Schedule of the Constitution of India.

Legislative Powers/Functions:

These Councils have empowered to make laws for allotment of land, use of land for grazing, and shifting cultivation. They also have power to establish village councils, public health, and appointment of village chiefs, laws on marriage, social customs, money-lending and trading by non-tribals within the autonomous district. (Para 3, Sixth Schedule) All the laws and rules passed by the ADCs have to be assent by the Governor of the state.

Executive Powers/Functions

The ADCs or autonomous district councils have been empowered with the executive power to construct or manage primary schools, dispensaries, markets, cattle, ponds, roads and water ways, land revenue, forest, primary education, taxes, administration of villages and towns, etc. (Para 6 & 8, Sixth Schedule)

Judicial Powers/Functions

ADCs have been given the power to establish village courts, District Council courts in the autonomous area for adjudication or trial of suits and cases or customary laws in which both the parties are tribal. (Para 4 (1), Sixth Schedule) But it cannot try cases involving offences. Autonomous District Councils courts are courts of appeal in respect of all suits and cases tried by the village court and the Subordinate District Council Court. The High Court and the Supreme Court of India have jurisdiction over suits and cases decided by the Autonomous District Council Courts. (Para 5 (1), Sixth Schedule).

Problems of Autonomous councils -

- I. **Misuse of power:** From the study it is known that, the power of nominations in the ADCs have been misused on several occasions. The purpose is to give representation to minority or unrepresented tribes in the district. The nomination power is generally vested in the hands of the Governor of the state. But it is experienced that, on some cases the nomination power is misused for narrow party gains .Often such persons are nominated who would support the party in power in the ADC.
- II. **Political Patronage and Favoritism:** The ADCs have framed service rules to manage and regulate the service of their employees. These councils Cs make appointment to teachers and other staff and increase the number of schools without providing adequate infrastructure to the schools. In several

autonomous councils, most appointments for various posts were made with a view to extending political patronage without considering for the qualification of persons. There are some teachers who are not qualified enough to teach in the primary schools. In several autonomous councils misuse of government funds for schools development was also evident since there had been no expert inspecting officers. And in the appointment of various posts, favoritism and political influence played a vital role. Such situation led to the decline in the standard of living and the quality of education.

- III. **Lake of Good Initiative:** Under the Sixth Schedule of the Constitution of India, the Autonomous District Councils are empowered to make laws to allotment or use of land. (Para 8 (1), Sixth Schedule) In Meghalaya and in the hills of Assam, no land can be mortgaged, leased, bartered, gifted or otherwise transferred by tribal to non-tribal without the permission of the ADCs. Although the ADCs have power to make laws for land development and land revenue, hardly any significant steps have been taken to initiate land reforms which hold the key to prosperity in tribal society.(Ray, 1999, p.260) In several autonomous councils areas, land revenue collection could not be made since the control over land remained with the village chief and Headmen. Revenue from the grazing lands in the karbi hills and some other hills went to the village chief instead of the ADCs. (Chaube,1999, p.109). In the hill areas, food scarcity caused by irregular collection of land revenue because of ethnic conflicts and deplorable communication made the collection of revenue small and complicated in several autonomous councils areas of Assam state. (Bhuyan, 2008, p.169)
- IV. **Loopholes and leakages in the process of collection of the taxes:** The study reveals that tax is an important source of the ADCs' internal income. The Autonomous District Councils have framed some regulations for the collection of taxes in their areas. The ADCs collect taxes on profession, trades, callings, employments, animals and boats, entry of goods into markets for sale and tolls on persons and goods carried in ferries. But, he ADCs neither enforced the regulation strictly nor realized the amount efficiently so collection of taxes was not done regularly and properly. No attempt is made by the ADCs to raise its revenue by exploiting its financial resources available to them. The receipt from the source of taxation was not adequate as there were loopholes and leakages in the process of collection of the taxes. It is alleged that taxes collected by the official hardly reached the coffer of ADCs of Assam in its entirety. Thus, there is an allegation of siphoning of tax amount by the concerned officials.
- V. **Inadequate as well as Unworkable Funds:** Funds for carrying out developmental activities as provided according to the present system are

found to be inadequate as well as unworkable. In some ADCs' adequate money was asked from the state government for the purpose of construction of communication in rural areas, implementation of forest schemes and salary for the staff but the state government released inadequately. It has been being observed that the funds given as grants-in-aids by the state governments are far from being sufficient to meet the actual requirements of the ADCs.

- VI. **Interest to the neo-middle rich class:** It is observed that the ADCs served the interest of mainly the neo-middle rich class or classes of rich traders, contractors, bureaucrats . Those educated who had emerged from within the tribal society of North East India due to enlarging money economy on developmental activities. These emerging socio-economic structures in the tribal areas did not allow the benefits of the ADCs to flow towards the weaker section of the tribes. (Prasad, 1997, p.68) Again the elected members of the ADCs and the office employees who were normally from the elite group of the tribal society they have vested interest in preserving the exploitative structure. So they were not likely to do anything that would strengthen the position of the poor in their areas.
- VII. **Lake of proper Coordination:** On the relationship between the ADCs and the state government, the Constitution of India has not provided a proper co-ordination of the ADCs administration with the administration at the state level. The state government has no legal authority to guide and advise the ADCs. The administrative guidance of the officers of the state government are not utilized by the ADCs in their everyday work. The relationship between the ADCs and the state government is cooperative when the same political party rule both in the ADCs and at the state .But when the ruling party in the ADCs is different from the state then there is contradiction from the state government in different forms.
- VIII. **Ineffective Governmental Laws:** It may further be observed that forest is another main source of the ADCs' income. Huge income received by ADCs comes from the forest resources and hence a reduction in the income from forest source results in tremendous financial hardship for the people. Most of the tribal villagers depend on forests for crops cultivation and for other livelihood. The large forests are the source of sustenance for the poor section of the tribal people of North East India. But jhum cultivation, extension of jhumming areas, cutting of timber, such factors contribute to the decline in revenue collected by the ADCs. But, in these areas, forest conservation laws are generally not so effective. Along with it there is serious problem of deforestation in these ADCs areas.

Suggestions –

- The government and other agencies need to win the confidence of ADCs and there has to be a proper coordination or adjustment between powers and functions of ADCs and state or central government. And also there has to be equilibrium between traditional practices and usages with changes that have occurred within the tribal society today.
- There must be stopped Political Patronage and Favoritism. Because this two things is the root cause of corruption in the administration of ADCs. Along with this the issue on representation needs to be reconsidered because there is still has limited participation of women in the decision making process, and also excludes the non-tribals of the State.
- There is need of Good Initiative in the ADCs administration so that adequate accountability and transparency of funds generated should be entrusted to authorities such as the Comptroller-General and Auditor-General of Accounts to prevent misuse. and to take initiatives to ensure that the Autonomous Councils have well defined legislations that clearly identify the powers and functions of the village level bodies, transparency in the allocation and utilization of funds. Improvement of literacy rate is also necessary for the development of tribal people and to eradicate the problems of Autonomous councils of NE India.
- The need of effective Governmental Laws is always required to each and every administration so that they can strengthen and closely reviewing of financial position of the ADCs, empowering the local self-governance, Empowerment of civil society bodies etc.
- Traditional forms of governance must be promoted with democratic self governance so that irrespective of all classes of society, religion, gender justice can get the opportunity to take part in governance.
- Regular and assured financial assistance from both Central and State governments and also an efficient monitoring system from them are two vital factors for the development of tribal areas in NE India.
- Finally not lastly the most important is that the awareness and active participation of tribal people, their organization in every sphere of their life.

Conclusion

In conclusion it can be said that ADCs fail to fulfill the hopes and desires of the tribal people of North East India. It has only strengthened identity politics. Social and economic development has been ignored. The birth of the ADCs was held with anticipations and aspirations as it was thought to be sign of political and constitutional advancement for granting autonomy to the ethnic minorities in areas of North East India. But the hopes was largely destroyed and frustrated,

by every aspect of development such as per capita income, health status, education, housing, poverty level. The ADCs areas remain poor and backward. If the above problems are not rectified, tribal development will always be a distant dream in spite of the existence of ADCs in North East India as well as Assam.

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वास्तुशास्त्रानुसारं गृहनिर्माणे दिक्साधनम्

डॉ. नवीनशर्मा

सहायकाचार्यः(ज्योतिषम्)

महर्षिवाल्मीकिसंस्कृतविश्वविद्यालयः

कैथलनगरम्, हरियाणा

गृहनिर्माणार्थं प्रयुक्तभूखण्डे सूक्ष्मदिशां प्रयोजनत्वात् सूक्ष्मदिग्ज्ञानम् आवश्यकम्, "पूर्वापरादिव्यवहारहेतुः दिग्मुक्तावल्यां विहिता-इति परिभाषा न्यायसिद्धान्त " । भूगोलस्य कन्दुकारकल्पनया ध्रुवानुरोधेन भूपिण्डस्य भ्रमणमथवा भूस्थिरत्ववादीनां प्राचीनानां मतेन प्रवहवायुना नक्षत्रग्रहाणां ध्रुवानुरोधेन पूर्वतः पश्चिमायां भ्रमणम्, इदमेव दिग्ज्ञानार्थं जनान् प्रेरयति।^१ दिक् व्युत्पत्तिर्यथा-

कृत्वैकमवधिं तस्मादिदं पूर्वञ्च पश्चिमम्।

इति देशो निदिश्येत् यया सा दिगिति स्मृता॥^२

वास्तुग्रन्थेषु गृहनिर्माणात् पूर्वं दिक्साधनविधेः संक्षेपेण वर्णनं कृतमस्ति यथा श्रीजीवनाथदेवज्ञेन वास्तुरत्नावल्यामुक्तं यत् -

प्रासादे सद्नेऽलिन्दे द्वारे कुण्डे विशेषतः ।

दिङ्मूढे कुलनाशः स्यात्तस्मात्संशोधयेद्दिशः ॥^३

अर्थात् देवालये, राजप्रसादे, साधारणभवने, आलिन्दे, द्वारे, कुण्डे विशेषतः एतेषां निर्माणाय दिशि ध्यातव्यम् । दिग्ज्ञानरहिते सति कुलनाशः जायते । अतः एतेषां निर्माणात्पूर्वं दिशा सम्यक् साधनीया । अपराजितपृच्छायामपि दिग्मूढनिषेधः कृतः यथा -

चतुरश्रं समं कृत्वा दिग्मूढं परिवर्जयेत् ।

पूर्वपश्चिमादिग्मूढं वास्तु स्त्रीनाशकं स्मृतम् ॥^४

तत्रोक्तं यदावासार्थं भूमेः परीक्षां कृत्वा दिक्साधनार्थं समतलभूमौ वृत्तमालिखेत्। वृत्तेऽस्मिन् दशाङ्गुलप्रमाणयुक्तशङ्क संस्थाप्य दिक्साधनविधेः प्रयोगपूर्वकं दिक्साधनं कुर्यात् । यथा -

दिग्ज्ञानार्थं यदा रविरयनद्वयगतः स्यात्तदा (धनुरन्तयोरन्यतरगतः-सायनमिथुनान्त) उत्तमरीत्या :क्रान्तिगतेः शून्यत्वाद्नेन विधिना दिग्ज्ञानं साधुभवति। सूर्यसिद्धान्तेऽस्य विधिः प्रतिपादित । सूर्यसिद्धान्ते दिङ्दोषपरिहारः यथा -

सिद्धायतनतीर्थेषु नदीनां सङ्गमेषु च ।

स्वयंभूबाणालिङ्गेषु तत्र दोषो न विद्यते ॥^५

शिलातलेऽम्बुसंशुद्धे वज्रलेपेऽपि वा समे। तत्र शङ्कगुलैरिष्टैः समं मण्डलमालिखेत्

॥

तन्मध्ये स्थापयेच्छङ्कुं कल्पनाद्वादशाङ्गुलम्। तच्छायाग्रं स्पृशेद्यत्र वृत्ते पूर्वापरार्धयोः ॥

तत्र बिन्दू विधायोभौ वृत्ते पूर्वापराभिधौ। तन्मध्ये तिमिना रेखा कर्तव्या दक्षिणोत्तरा ॥

याम्योत्तरदिशोर्मध्ये तिमिना पूर्वपश्चिमा। दिङ्मध्यमत्त्वैः संसाध्या विदिशस्तद्वदेव हि ॥^६

शङ्कुस्थापनेनैव दिक्साधनस्य विधानं प्राप्यते। वास्तुराजवल्लभे उक्तं यत् -
वक्ष्येऽहं दिक्परिच्छेदं शङ्कुनार्कोदये सति।
उत्तरायणमासे तु शुक्लपक्षे शुभोदये।
तोयासिद्धवसुधावलयान्तर्यस्तलम्बककृतार्जवशङ्कोः।
यत्र भा विशति मुञ्चति वृत्तं ते दिशौ वरुणवासवयोः स्तः॥
याति भानुरपमण्डलवृत्त्या दक्षिणोत्तरदिशोरनुवेलम्।
तेन सा दिगनृजुः प्रतिभाति स्यादृजुः पुनरपक्रममौर्व्या॥
छायानिर्गमनप्रवेशसमयार्कान्तिजीवान्तरं,
क्षुण्णं स्वश्रवणेन लम्बकहृतं स्यादङ्गुलाद्यं फलम्।
पश्चाद्विन्दुमनेन रव्ययनतः सञ्चालयेद् व्यत्यायात्,
स्पष्टा प्राच्यपराथवायनवशात् प्राग्विन्दुमुत्सारयेत्॥ ७

सायनमेषादौ तुलादौ वा सूर्यः पूर्वस्यामुदेति, तथा च श्रवणकृत्तिकानक्षत्रयोः तारकाः अपि पूर्वस्यां भवन्ति, इतोऽपि स्वाति-

प्राचीमेषतुलारवेरुदयतः स्याद्वैष्णवे वह्निभे
चित्रास्वातिभमध्यगा निगदिता प्राची बुधैः पञ्चधा॥८

अर्थात् चित्रानक्षत्रयोः मध्यभागोऽपि पूर्वदिशि भवति, अत एव पूर्वदिशायाः बोधार्थं पञ्चप्रकाराः प्राप्यन्ते यथा सायनमेषोदयः .१ -, रसायन तुलोदयः ., ३श्रवणोदयः ., ४ कृत्तिकोदयः .
.५चित्रास्वातीनक्षत्रयोः मध्यभागः इति। किन्तु अयनांशवशात् दिशाबाधो भवति इत्यस्मात् प्रकारोऽयं स्थूलवर्तते। : किन्तु वैज्ञानिक युगेऽस्मिन् सम्यक् दिग्ज्ञानं कर्तुं नूतनानुभवाधारेण दिक्सूचककम्पासयन्त्रस्य आविष्कारो जातः। येन शीघ्रमेव दिग्ज्ञानं भवितुमर्हति। सिद्धान्तज्योतिषेऽपि कम्पासयन्त्रतुल्यमेव चुम्बकयन्त्रस्योल्लेखः प्राप्यते यथा -

सचुम्बकादेव सुशिल्यविज्ञाः कुर्वन्ति दिग्ज्ञानमिहान्यथैवा
पूर्वपरा याऽत्र कृता प्रकारैर्ज्ञेया बुधैः सा सममण्डलीया॥९

वास्तुवल्लभे सन्दर्भेऽस्मिन् उक्तं यथा-

प्रासादं भवनं करोति नगरं दिङ्मूढमर्थक्षयं ।
हर्म्ये देवगृहे पुरे च नितरामायुर्धनं दिङ्मुखे॥१०

एवमभीष्टप्रविधिभिः दिक्शोधनादिपूर्वकं वास्तुवेत्ता गृहनिर्माणं कुर्यात्। यतोहि प्रासाद-भवनदेवालादीनां-नगर- दिक्शोधनाभावात् द्रव्यादीनां नाशो भवति। दिशानुगुणं निर्माणेन च नितरामायुर्धनञ्च वर्धते। सुहूर्तगणपत्यनुसारमपि यथा -

दिक्शुद्धिरहितं गेहं प्रासादो वा जलाशयः।
कुर्याद्धानिं मृत्तिं तस्मादादौ दिक्साधनं चरेत्॥११

दिक्शोधनाभावेन निर्मितप्रासाद-गृहजलाशयादिभिः हानिः मृत्युश्च सम्भवति।- तस्मिन् लग्ने शुभग्रहस्य संयोगः दृष्टिः वा भवेत्। लग्नात् केन्द्रत्रिकोणयोः शुभग्रहाः, त्रिषडायेषु च क्रूरग्रहाः चन्द्रश्च भवेत्, तदा शङ्कुस्थापनं श्रेष्ठफलदायकं भवति।

एवं प्रकारेण दैवज्ञेन निर्धारित-शुभमुहूर्त्ते ब्राह्मणादिभिः पुण्याहवाचनमये वातावरणे, वाद्ययन्त्राणां माङ्गलिकध्वनौ सुभगानां मङ्गलगीतयुक्तपरिवेशे दैवज्ञपूजनपूर्वकं वास्तुपुरुषस्य कुक्षिस्थाने शुङ्कुस्थापनं कुर्यात्।

वास्तुसौख्यग्रन्थेऽपि शङ्कुस्थापनस्योपरोक्तमुहूर्त्तः एव निर्दिष्टः। वास्तुसारसङ्ग्रहेऽपि शङ्कुस्थापनार्थं लग्नशुद्धिविषये विशेषेणोक्तमस्ति।

दिक्परत्वेन गृहविभागः

आधुनिककालेऽस्मिन् जनाः अज्ञानवशात् वास्तुसिद्धान्तविरुद्धं स्वसुविधानुरूपं सिद्धान्तानुरूपं भूखण्डे कक्षविन्यासं कुर्वन्ति। कदाचित् स्थितिरियमुपर्युक्तवास्तुविदां भ्रमवशात् गृहस्वामिनः सुविधाजन्यस्थितेः परिप्रेक्ष्यत्वादपि जायते। अत एव गृहस्वामी कुवास्तुजन्यदोषेण सपरिवारं पीड्यते। परञ्च भारतीयवास्तुशास्त्रे गृहे निवासकर्तृणां कृते सुविधासुरक्षयोः प्राप्तेः सिद्धान्तानां प्रविधीनाञ्च प्रतिपादनं कृतम्, येषामस्ति महद् वैज्ञानिकं महत्त्वम्। वस्तुतः वास्तुपुरुषावयवानुरूपं तत्रस्थदेवभागेषु कक्षादिविन्यासः कर्तव्यः।

गृहनिर्माणे दिङ्मूहत्त्वम्

दिक्परत्वेन गृहविभागं कर्तुमद्यत्वे बहुशः जनाः दिशानां सूक्ष्मत्वज्ञानाभावत्वात् दिग्भ्रमिता एव, ज्योतिषवास्तुग्रन्थेषु चोपलब्धवर्णनानुसारं दिशानामधिपतयः ग्रहादेवताश्च वर्तन्ते।

गृहनिर्माणात् पूर्वमिदमवश्यमेवावधेयं यत् भूखण्डस्य कस्मिन् भागे कमुद्देश्यमनुदिश्य स्थपतिना निर्माणं कारणीयम्। दिशानामधिपतिकारणात् प्रत्येकस्मिन् भूखण्डे देवतानुकूलप्रयोजनार्थं निर्माणं कर्तव्यमन्यथा दिशासम्बद्धदेवतायाः क्रोधावेशेन कष्टं भवति। भवननिर्माणान्तर्गतप्रयोज्यमाणकक्षेषु यदि देवतानुकूलं वस्तूनां कक्षानाञ्च समायोजनं भवेत्, तर्हि गृहपतिः देवानुग्रहं प्राप्य सुखशान्तिपूर्वकं जीवनं यापयति-समृद्धिः। दिशानुकूलभवननिर्माणेन नितरामायुर्धनं वर्धते नान्यथा, यथोक्तम् -

प्रसादं भवनं करोति नगरं दिङ्मूढमर्थक्षयम्।

हर्म्यं देवगृहे पुरे च नितरामायुर्धनं दिङ्मुखे॥१४

अत एव पूर्वोक्तप्रकारेणाभीष्टप्रविधिभिः दिक्शोधनादिपूर्वकं एकाशीतिस्तुमण्डले पदवा-अग्रलिखितप्रकारेणगृहविभागः कर्तव्यः।

नारदपुराणे गृहविभागः

पूर्वादिगेष्वलिङ्गेषु गृहभेदास्तु षोडश।
स्नानागारं दिशि प्राच्यामाग्नेय्यां पाकमंदिरम्।
याम्यां च शयनागारं नैर्ऋत्यां शस्त्रमंदिरम्।
प्रतीच्या भोजनगृहं वायव्यां धान्यमंदिरम्।
कौबेर्यां देवतागारमीशान्यां क्षीरमंदिरम्।
शय्यामूत्रासत्रतद्विद्ध भोजनं मंगलाश्रयम्।
धान्यस्त्रीभोगवित्तं च शृङ्गारायतनानि च।
ईशान्यादिक्रमस्तेषां गृहनिर्माणकं शुभम्॥१५

वास्तुभूमे: पूर्वस्यां स्नानगृहम्, आग्नेय्यां पाकगृहम्, नैऋत्यां शस्त्रागारः, प्रतीच्यां भोजनगृहम्, वायव्यां धान्यमन्दिरम्, उत्तरस्यां दैवमन्दिरम्, ईशान्याञ्च जलगृहं निर्मेयम्। आग्नेयदक्षिणयोर्मध्ये दक्षिमन्थनगृहम्, दक्षिणनैऋत्ययोर्मध्ये घृतनिवेशगृहम्, नैऋत्यपश्चिमयोर्मध्ये शौचालयः, पश्चिमवायव्ययोर्मध्ये विद्याभ्यासः, वायव्योत्तरयोर्मध्ये रतिगृहम्, उत्तरैशानयोर्मध्ये औषधनिवेशः शृङ्गारद्रव्यनिवेशश्च कर्तव्यः । किन्त्वत्र इत्युक्ते सत्यापि "गृहभेदास्तु षोडश" पञ्चदशगृहभेदाः एव प्राप्यन्ते। यथा-

	ईशानः देवगृहम्	सर्वसंग्रहगृहम्	ई.पू. स्नानगृहम्	पूर्वः दक्षिमन्थनगृहम्	पू.आ. पाकगृहम्	
ई.उ.	औषधगृहम्				धृतसंग्रहगृहम्	आ.द.
उत्तरः	कोषगृहम्				शयनगृहम्	दक्षिणः
वा.उ.	रतिगृहम्				शौचालयः	द.नै.
वायव्यः	धान्यगृहम्	शोकगृहम्	भोजगृहम्	विद्याभ्यागृहम्	शस्त्रगृहम्	
		वा.प.	पश्चिमः		प.नै.	

मत्स्यपुराणानुसारं उक्तं यथा -

ईशान्यामन्नहानिः स्याद् वास्तौ संवर्धिते सदा । ईशाने देवतागारं तथा शान्तिगृहं भवेत् ॥
महानसं तथाग्नेये तत्पार्श्वे चोत्तरे जलम् । गृहस्योपस्करं सर्वं नैऋत्ये स्थापयेद् बुधः ॥
बन्धस्थानं बहिः कुर्यात् स्नानमण्डपमेव च । धनधान्यं च वायव्ये कर्मशालां ततो बहिः ॥
एवं वास्तुविशेषः गृहभर्तुः शुभावहः ॥^{१६}

किन्त्वत्र सम्पूर्णगृहस्य विभागविषये नोक्तम् । अग्निपुराणे गृहविभागः एवं प्रकारेण निर्दिष्टः यथा -

पूर्वस्यां श्रीगृहं प्रोक्तमाग्नेय्यां वै महानसम् ।
शयनं दक्षिणस्यां तु नैऋत्यामायुधाश्रयम् ॥
भोजनं पश्चिमायां तु वायव्यां धान्यसंग्रहः ।
उत्तरे द्रव्यसंस्थानमैशान्यां देवतागृहम् ॥^{१७}

दिकपरत्वेन गृहविभागविषये वास्तुरत्नावल्यां उक्तं यथा -

स्नानाग्निपाकशयनास्त्रभुजश्च धान्यभाण्डारदैवतगृहाणि च पूर्वतः स्युः ।
तन्मध्येस्तु मधनाज्यपूरीषविद्याभ्यासाख्यरोदनरतौषसर्वधाम् ॥^{१८}

सन्दर्भः :-

१. ज्यो. दिग्देश., ले. डॉ. नागेन्द्रपाण्डेय

२. निरु., अ., - १
३. वा. रत्ना., अ. - ३, श्लो. - ०१
४. अप. पृच्छा., अ. - ५२, श्लो. - २-५
५. प्रासा. म., अ. - ०८, श्लो. - १०
६. सू.सि ., त्रिप्रश्नाधिकारः, श्लो४-१-
७. वा.वि ., अ३-., श्लो १०.....७ - .
८. वा.व .रा ., अ१-., श्लो१० - .
९. सि.वि .त ., त्रिप्रश्नाधिकारः, श्लो - .३७८
१०. वा.ब .रा ., अ१ - ., श्लो - .१०
११. मु.गण ., वास्तुप्रकरणम्, श्लो - .१८
१२. वा. सौ., नवमो भागः, श्लो. - ४५३.....४५६
१३. वा. सा. सं., त्रयोदशतमं सोपानम्, श्लो. - ८.....१३
१४. रा. व. म., अ. - १, श्लो. - १०
१५. ना.ख .पू .पु ., अ५६ - ., श्लो५८८.....५८५ - .
१६. म. पु., अ. - २५६, श्लो. - ३३ — ३५
१७. अ.पु., अ. - १०६, श्लो.- १८, १९
१८. वा. रत्ना., अ. - ९, पृ. - १२४

A STUDY ON THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN PERFECT COMPUTER SERVICES

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Abstract

Employee engagement is a workplace approach designed to ensure that employees are committed to their organization's goals and values, motivated to contribute to organizational success, and are able at the same time to enhance their own sense of well-being. Engaged workers stand apart from their not-engaged and actively disengaged counterparts because of the discretionary effort they consistently bring to their roles. These employees willingly go the extra mile, work with passion, and feel a profound connection to their company. They are the people who will drive innovation and move the business forward. Employee Engagement is the extent to which employee commitment, both emotional and intellectual exists relative to accomplishing the work, mission, and vision of the organization. Engagement can be seen as a heightened level of ownership where each employee wants to do whatever they can for the benefit of their internal and external customers, and for the success of the organization as a whole. Not-engaged employees offer perhaps the greatest untapped opportunity for businesses to improve their performance and profitability. Not-engaged workers can be difficult to spot. They are not overtly hostile or disruptive and likely do just enough to fulfill their job requirements. Measuring employee engagement is important. Measuring the right things those that matter most to performance and provide a framework for positive change is crucial. In today economic downturn situation, organization started to look into its people asset internal employee so that they can utilize the human asset to sustain the competitiveness in the industry.

Keywords: Employee, Engagement, Workplace, Motivation, Production, Profit

Introduction

Employees who are engaged in their work and committed to their organizations give companies crucial competitive advantages - including higher productivity and lower employee turnover.

Researchers studied 49,928 work units, including nearly 1.4 million employees. This latest iteration of the meta-analysis further confirmed the well-established connection between employee engagement and key performance outcomes:

- customer ratings
- profitability
- productivity
- turnover (for high-turnover and low-turnover organizations)
- safety incidents
- Shrinkage (theft)
- absenteeism
- patient safety incidents
- quality (defects)

Engaging employees requires a year-round focus on changing behaviors, processes, and systems to anticipate and respond to an organization's needs. High levels of employee engagement occur when employees are involved with, committed to, enthusiastic, and passionate about their work.

Areas of focus include defining the concept of employee work engagement, how it is measured, how often it occurs, the costs of disengagement, the business benefits linked to positive engagement, and how workplaces can be changed to encourage engagement.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the level of employee engagement in Perfect Computer Services, Chennai.
- To find out the factors contributing to employee engagement.
- To find out if there is any relationship between age and employee engagement.
- To find out if there is any relationship between gender and employee engagement.
- To give suggestions for improving the level of employee engagement in Perfect Computers Services, Chennai.

Need & Scope of the Study

The organization is still in its growth stage and thus it is important for the organization to study the mindset of the employees, what makes them satisfied and there by engage them in their work in order to improve the organizational effectiveness. Hence, the company is interested to study the employee engagement level and plans to implement strategies to improve the level of employee engagement.

Review of literature:

Roshni Haider & Shad Rahmani(2012) we can conclude that employee engagement activities are very necessary and currently most of the organizations are trying to provide good engagement measures so as to retain their employees and also develop the career of their employees. This culture is more prevalent in corporate these days and they are trying more innovative methods to engage their employee. Employee get Extra benefits and perks and employer tend to get a committed and loyal workforce.

Collins Badu Agyemang, Samuel Batchison Ofei (2013) Their study revealed a significant positive relationship between employee engagement and employee commitment. Employees of private organizations have a higher level of employee engagement and organizational commitment than employees in public organizations, and long-tenured and short-tenured employees did not differ in commitment levels.

Dr Gokula Krishnan, S(2013) The objective of this study is to know the association between employee engagement level and its drivers; and to study relationship between demographic variables and drivers of engagement along with level of employee engagement. The study supports that the employee engagement level relies mainly on the practices of support (motivational) and recognition, belief in ability to succeed and belief in job and organizational.

Gary Johnson, Jaime Roberts and Karen (2013) This paper seeks to address the role and impact of employee engagement within an organization undergoing cultural transformation, addressing the issues of monitoring and increasing levels of staff engagement over time. The paper draws an in-depth employee engagement surveys over a five year period as part of a case study to illustrate how HR drives and monitors change through employee engagement. The role of engagement and monitoring processes are highlighted as part of the transition.

Dr. Thiruchelvi. A (2013) Engagement is also being shaped by energy, efficacy and involvement in a role. People vary in their engagement as a function of their perceptions of the benefits they receive from a role. To create the willingness of employees, an organization must design jobs that motivate the employees and make them get the work done. This study brings in a conceptual model that helps to identify the various factors that will impact employee engagement.

Nidhi Sharma(2013) According to the study is not difficult to see that that an effective Employee engagement model must address the emotional needs of employees. Organizations may not be able to satisfy everyone through career progression or huge salary packets, but they can definitely strive to create experiences for employees that make them feel wanted, cared for and

respected. It will require extraordinary effort to put this machinery in place, but the results can also be expected to be extraordinary.

Swarnalatha, C Dr. & Prasanna, T.S, (2013)”The Gallup Organization, potentially the most widely recognized name associated with employee engagement due to their bestselling book, “First, Break All the Rules,” defines engaged employees as those who, “work with a passion and feel a profound connection to their company” and “drive innovation and move the organization forward”

Swathi S.(2013) Their study focuses only the factors like feedback, Rewards, Reorganization, and Leadership etc. which influence the Employee Engagement. Along with engaged technology and streamlined work processes gaining employee’s discretionary effort, so called engagement, may be one of the most effective ways to improve productivity and improve business results.

Dr. Preetinder S. Gill Dr. John Dugger III ,Mr. Frank Norton (2014) Employers have focused increasing attention on monitoring employee engagement over the past decade. It was found that these dimensions shared a strong relationship and provided preliminary evidence that compensation shares a causal relationship with alignment with the organization and opportunity for development and recognition.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in this project is Descriptive Research. A descriptive study is one in which information is collected without changing the environment.

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when/why the characteristics occurred. Rather it addresses the "what" question. The characteristics used to describe the situation or population is usually some kind of categorical scheme also known as descriptive categories.

Data Collection

Primary data was collected from the respondents by means of questionnaire. The employee engagement level was determined based on the average engagement score.

The questionnaire consisted of 31 questions in total out of which, 4 questions were for studying demographic factors, 26 questions consisting of 5 actionable engagement drivers (factors), each of which contributes to the overall level of engagement .The questionnaire also consisted of one question, for finding factors contributing to overall employee engagement.

Employees responded to the survey using a 5-point Likert scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree).

The engagement drivers studied were:

- Working Environment
- Leadership
- Team & Co-worker relations
- Compensation program
- Career development

The employees with average engagement score 1-1.9 were found to be hostile, score 2-2.9 were found to be disengaged, between 3-3.9 were contributing and employees with average engagement score 4-5 were found to be engaged.

Sampling Design

Population

A population for the study refers to a well-defined collection of individuals or objects known to have similar characteristics. All individuals or objects within a certain population usually have a common, binding characteristic or trait. In this study, the population refers to all the employees of Perfect Computer Services, Chennai. The total number of employees, that is, the population size is 60.

Sampling Technique

The data was collected using census method, since the total number of employees i.e. population size was not too large. The whole population was considered for the study in order to ensure effective analysis and results.

Sample Size

The sample size for the study was 60. A total of 60 questionnaires were circulated among the employees and all responded for the same. The response rate was 100%.

Data Analysis Tools

Statistical Tools

- Percentage Analysis
- CHI-Square test
- Weighted Average method

Weighted Average Method

Factors contributing to employee engagement

Factors	Rank (in decreasing order)					Total
	5	4	3	2	1	
Working environment	22	16	14	4	4	60
Leadership	12	8	16	14	10	60
Team & Co worker relations	10	7	18	7	18	60
Career Development	16	8	14	12	10	60
Compensation Program	18	12	15	9	6	60

Source: Primary Data

$$(X_1W_1 + X_2W_2 + X_3W_3 + \dots)$$

$$\text{WEIGHTED AVERAGE} = \frac{\quad}{N}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Working environment} &= (22*5+16*4+14*3+4*2+4*1)/60 \\ &= 228/60 \\ &= 3.80 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Leadership} &= (12*5+8*4+16*3+14*2+10*1)/60 \\ &= 178/60 \\ &= 2.97 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Team \& Co worker relation} &= (10*5+7*4+18*3+7*2+18*1)/60 \\ &= 164/60 \\ &= 2.73 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Career Development} &= (16*5+8*4+14*3+12*2+10*1)/60 \\ &= 188/60 \\ &= 3.13 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Compensation Program} = (18*5+12*4+15*3+9*2+6*1)/60$$

$$= 206/60$$

$$= 3.45$$

Ranking of factors

Factors	Weighted Average	Rank
Working environment	3.80	I
Leadership	2.97	IV
Team & Co worker relations	2.73	V
Career Development	3.13	III
Compensation Program	3.45	II

Inference

From the Tables 4.32, 4.33 it is inferred that the weighted average values of working environment and compensation program are highest among the 5 factors studied. Hence, working environment and compensation program are the most important factors contributing to the employee engagement.

Chi-SQUARE TEST

Age and Employee Engagement

Aim: To test if there is any relationship between age of respondents and Employee Engagement.

H0: There is no relationship between Age and Employee Engagement

H1: There is significant relationship between Age and Employee Engagement

Age vs. Employee Engagement cross tabulation

Age group	Employee Engagement Score				Total
	Hostile	Disengaged	Contributin	Engaged	
20-25	0	4	18	0	22
	0	3	13	0	16
Total					60

Chi-square Test between Age and Employee engagement

	Value	Df	Asym.Sig (2-sided)
Pearson chi-Square	12	9	0.213

Inference:

It is inferred from the cross tabulation that none of the employees are completely engaged regardless of age group. Table 4.35 shows that sig. value is 0.213 (>0.05) and so the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no relationship between Age and Employee Engagement.

Gender and Employee Engagement

Aim: To test if there is any relationship between Gender of respondents and Employee Engagement.

H0: There is no relationship between Gender and Employee Engagement

H1: There is significant relationship between Gender and Employee Engagement

Table 4.35 Gender vs. Employee Engagement cross tabulation

Gender	Employee Engagement Score				Total
	Hostile	Disengaged	Contributing	Engaged	
Male	0	9	41	0	50
					10
Total					60

Table 4.36 Chi-square Test between Gender and Employee engagement

	Value	Df	Asym.Sig (2-sided)
Pearson chi-Square	2	1	0.157

Inference:

It is inferred from the cross tabulation that none of the employees are completely engaged regardless of gender. Table 4.36 shows that sig. value is 0.157 (>0.05) and so the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no relationship between gender and Employee Engagement.

Findings

1. 28.33% of employees disagree that they are appreciated by their supervisor.
2. 46.67% of employees are neutral about usefulness of supervisor's feedback.
3. Most of the employees (35%) are neutral about the help they receive from team members.
4. Most of the employees (45%) are neutral that their team work is good.
5. 50% employees feel that team members treat each other with respect.
6. Almost 46.6% employees feel that enough training is given to them for job completion.
7. Promotions within the company are good, that is agreed by 38.33% employees.
8. Equal percentage of employees (36.67%) Disagree and have neutral feeling that deserving candidates are promoted.
9. 53.33% employees are neutral towards encouragement given for skills up gradation.
10. 50% of employees are neutral about the fairness of their pay.
11. 53.33% employees have neutral feelings that their company benefit plan meets their needs.
12. 38.33% of employees agree that their retirement plan is fair.
13. 81.67% of employees are contributing toward employee engagement, 18.33% are disengaged, and none of the employees are hostile or engaged.
14. Weighted average values of working environment and compensation program are highest among the 5 factors studied.
15. There is no relationship between Age and Employee Engagement as well as there is no relationship between Gender and employee engagement.

Suggestions

1. The Employee Engagement activities at the firm should be designed in such a manner that it helps in improving team & Co-worker relations .Lot of efforts should be taken to improve team relations since, it is one of the least contributing factors towards employee engagement.

The following initiatives could be taken in order to improve the Team and Co-worker relations:

- Communication club activities

- Group tasks
 - Team outings
 - Team lunch
2. The leadership was not appreciated by most of the employees ,the effectiveness of leadership could be improved by bringing in the transparency between top management and other employees .Certain initiatives such as CEO speak ,monthly town hall meetings, feedback sessions, Ice breaking sessions can be implemented to improve the interactions between top management and other employees.
- 3.Career development is the third highest contributing factor. Certain measures can be taken to improve the career development of employees such as:
- Inclusion of executive programs where employees can simultaneously study and complete skill based courses.
 - Supporting internal promotion.
 - Conducting motivational programs.
4. Compensation program is already found to be good by the employees. But it can be tweaked to convert the contributing employees to engaged employees. A special bouquet of benefits can be included in compensation program according to employee's quarterly performance.
5. Working environment is the best contributing factor, thus extra efforts should be taken for maintaining a pleasing working environment for all employees.

Conclusion

The study was undertaken to analyze the employee engagement level, as engaged employees are more productive and contributing towards the organizational effectiveness. The study also focused on finding out factors contributing employee engagement. Sample of 60 employees of the organization (Perfect computer services) were part of the survey. The Employee engagement level in the organization was found to be average. It was found that, Team and Co-worker relations as well as Leadership were to be improved. Suggestions were given to improve these factors .There was no significant relationship between the age, gender of the employees and their engagement level.

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ATTITUDE TOWARDS USING CYBER RESOURCES OF UNDER-GRADUATE STUDENTS IN RELATION TO COMPUTER PHOBIA AND E-LEARNING ORIENTATION

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Abstract

Attitude towards using cyber resources of Under-Graduate students in relation to computer phobia and e-learning orientation has been dealt with in this paper. In the present study descriptive survey method was adopted. Random sampling technique was used to select samples of 240 Under Graduate students studying different colleges in Bangalore city. A standardized Attitude Towards Using Cyber Resources Scale (ATUCRS) developed and standardized by Dr.S. Rajasekar, Computer Phobia Scale (CPS) developed and standardized by Dr. S. Rajasekar and Dr. P. VaiyapuriRaja, E Learning Orientation Scale (E-LOS) developed and standardized by Dr.SaurabhiChaturvedi, Dr.SantoshDhar and Dr.UpinderDhar was used to collect the data and Pearson's Co-efficient of Correlation technique was adopted for data analysis. There is significant and negative relationship between Attitudes towards Using Cyber Resources in relation to Computer Phobia and there is significant positive relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources in relation to E-Learning Orientation among Arts and Science Under -Graduate students.

Key words: Cyber Resources, Computer Phobia And E-Learning Orientation, Under Graduate Students.

Introduction

Today, technology is one of the most discussed subjects of our lives. Internet is the most widely used technology in the world. Internet is the source of information in the modern era. In the present decade, Cyber Resources have been used widely in education. Classroom has become virtual environment that allows learners to understand practically of what learning and teaching is all about and also helps learners to have long retention of subject content. It affects the educational styles and learning in a creative way. The use of the Cyber Resources provides great educational benefits to students. It makes learning precise and up-to date.

E-Learning is used to describe technology enhanced learning; where by appropriate and relevant use of technology is used to augment the learning process. Many educational institutes adopt web based learning systems for facilitating their students. There are numerous companies in the market commercially developing web based learning modules or courses to help students to make learning process much more efficient, simpler and competitive. Students can stay even in their home or classrooms and receive lectures without seeing the lecturer or teacher. Computers, smart-phones and tablets are the widely-used technology today by the students.

In many educational institutes tablets are distributed to students to enable E-Learning. In-fact many state Governments is promoting E-Learning by giving free tablets and laptops to students. The traditional education delivery system has been a classroom setting with a teacher giving a lecture and students listening and writing notes. The teacher's role is not just to read a book in the classroom. A student can do this by himself, or even use an online library, like Wikipedia, which will provide him a plethora of information anywhere, anytime.

In the digital era, the cyber resources play an important role in both teaching and learning. Cyber is a prefix used to describe a person, thing, or idea as part of the computer and information age. Cyber resources include mainly all the online applications of computer, like email, web based applications, search engines and so on. Attitude towards Cyber Resources is an expression of favour or disfavour toward cyber resources which play an important role in learning. It enhances learning process and makes learning accurate and up-to-date. In the digital era, the cyber resources play an important role in both teaching and learning. Cyber is a prefix used to describe a person, thing, or idea as part of the computer and information age. Cyber resources include mainly all the online applications of computer, like email, web based applications, search engines and so on. Attitude towards Cyber Resources is an expression of favour or disfavour toward cyber resources which play an important role in learning. It enhances learning process and makes learning accurate and up-to-date (Anjali Puri, 2016).

Concept of Computer Phobia

Computer Phobia is associated with the anxiety about learning to use computers or not being able to learn to successfully use computers which is often used to basically mean avoidance or fear of learning the new skills required by increasing use of computers in the school or workplace. Computer Phobia is the fear of computers or working on a computer.

Concept of E-Learning

E-Learning is electronic learning, and typically this means using a computer to deliver part, or all of a course whether it's in a school, part of your

mandatory business training or a full distance learning course. A learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of electronic resources is known as E-Learning.

Need And Importance of the Study

The Favourable Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources play a very important role in making one really interested in it. Unless the students possess a favourable Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources, they may not be interested in it, which in turn will affect their knowledge of Cyber Resources and also they will find learning with help of Cyber Resources difficult, which in turn will affect their learning. “Attitudes are important in education because they affect learning efficiency” (Wrightstone et al., 1964).

A Computer Phobic person rarely handles Cyber Resources and develops an aversion over the application of Cyber Resources. Therefore, if one has favourable Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources, then there may be a chance for them to be motivated in acquiring knowledge of Cyber Resources, as it is clear that the Cyber Resources knowledge is very much needed. Also, to acquire sound Cyber Resources knowledge, the person must be free from Cyber Phobia at least to some extent.

Several studies have been done on Attitude Towards Using Cyber Resources among B.Ed., students, students anxiety level in utilising Cyber Resources, Computer Phobia among students and students Attitude Towards E-Learning. These researches have been done on various target groups. E-Learning is a major technology that has changed education technology of the world but the teachers & some professionals are supposed to be pure users of both Cyber Resources and E-Learning technology. Therefore, the researcher was prompted to study the level of Computer Phobia and E-Learning Orientation as influenced by the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources. The researcher wanted to find the relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources, Computer Phobia and E-Learning Orientation. From the review of related literature, it was found that the above three variables have not been studied across any population especially the population of students of different professional courses. This invoked researcher to take up this study.

Variables of the Study

The following variables were selected for the study:

Dependent Variable

Attitude towards using Cyber Resources.

Independent Variable

- a) Computer Phobia.
- b) E-Learning Orientation

Objectives of the Study

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

- To find out the relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources of Under- Graduate (Arts and science)students in relation to Computer Phobia.
- To find out the relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources ofunder Graduate (Arts and science) students in relation E-Learning Orientation.

Hypotheses of the Study

The present study was undertaken with the following Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between mean scores of Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources of Under- Graduate (Arts and science) students in relation to Computer Phobia.
2. There is no significant relationship between mean scores of Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources of Under -Graduate (Arts and science) students in relation to E-Learning Orientation.

Sampling Procedure for Collection Of Data

The sample of the study constituted Under Graduate students of Arts and Science from Bangalore University. The sample data was collected from 240 students by employing random sampling technique.

Tools of the Study

For the present study the following tools were used for collecting the data.

1. Attitude Towards Using Cyber Resources Scale (ATUCRS) developed and standardized by Dr.S. Rajasekar.
2. Computer Phobia Scale (CPS) developed and standardized by Dr. S. Rajasekar and Dr. P. Vaiyapuri Raja.
3. E Learning Orientation Scale (E-LOS) developed and standardized by Dr.SaurabhiChaturvedi, Dr.SantoshDhar and Dr.UpinderDhar.

Statistical Technique used for Data Analysis

1. The following statistical technique were used for data analysis
Pearson's Co-efficient of Correlation

Analysis and Interpretation

Table-1 shows the number, degrees of freedom, “r” value and level of significance of Computer Phobia with Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources.

Variables	N	Mean	df	“r” value	Significance level
Computer Phobia with	240	63.82	238	0.644	** S
Attitude towards using cyber resources	240	75.83			

*-Significance at 0.05 Level, **-Significance at 0.01 level

From the table -1it is seen that obtained “r” value – 0.644 is higher than table value 0.139 at 0.01 levels of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is formulated that there is significant and negative relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources of under Graduate Students (Arts and Science) in relation to Computer Phobia.

The obtained mean value of Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources is 75.83 and mean score of Computer Phobia is 63.82. According to Computer Phobia scale as the score increases lesser is the Computer Phobia. It is evident here that higher the Computer Phobia score lesser is the Computer Phobia in students which increases Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources. Which implies that greater the Computer Phobia lesser the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources or lesser the Computer Phobia higher will be the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources.

Table-2 shows the number, degrees of freedom, “r” value and level of significance of E-learning orientation with Attitude Towards Using Cyber Resources.

Variables	N	Mean	df	“r” value	Significance level
e-learning orientation	240	135.2	238	0.520	**S
Attitude towards using cyber resources	240	75.83			

*-Significance at 0.05 Level, **-Significance at 0.01 level

From the table- 2, it is seen that obtained “r” value – 0.520 is higher than table value 0.139 at 0.01 levels of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is formulated that there is

significant positive relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources of under Graduate Students (Arts and Science) in relation to E-Learning Orientation

The obtained mean value of Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources is 75.83 and mean score of e-learning orientation is 135.2. Hence it is evident from the above mean scores that higher the E-Learning Orientation score higher will be the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources or lesser the E-Learning Orientation decreases the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources.

Educational Implications

The following were the implications observed and assessed during the survey.

1. The study showed that there was significant and negative relationship between mean scores of Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources of under Graduate Students (Arts and Science) in relation to their Computer Phobia. This implies that lesser the Computer Phobia higher will be the Attitude Towards Using Cyber Resources or higher the Computer Phobia lesser will be the Attitude Towards Using Cyber Resources. The findings on this study, however, indicate that learning in the computer environment requires the special challenge of developing a mix of declarative, procedural, conceptual, and logical knowledge. While successful learning is always a function of the interaction of many factors, those known to be essential for cultivating computer skills include extensive practice, a positive attitude, motivation, and the sense of satisfaction that attends accomplishment. These factors clearly interact in a circular fashion, for example, the more one has or take the opportunity for instruction and practice, the more time one will devote, this supports motivation and satisfaction which, in turn, extend one's use and thirst for more and finally the levels of computer will come down. Thus, Educational institutions should in addition to integrating computer use in their courses, make regularly available a wide range of short-format, hands-on workshops and demonstrations in which undergraduates can be given individual attention. The subjects of the workshops and demonstrations should parallel applications being integrated into course activities, in order to enhance exposure and high levels of practice. In addition to allocating fiscal resources to on-campus hardware and infrastructure, universities should also provide for upgrading of users' skills and user support, opportunities for undergraduates to purchase affordable software and hardware for use at home, and remote connectivity to the campus network for all students. This is view of the limitations in the ability of university to put in place adequate and up-to-date computer facilities on-campus so, that undergraduates generally prefer to do academic

computing at home rather than at the universities. Furthermore, students who are going to participate in courses that require the use of the Internet would benefit if offered technology literacy courses prior to enrolling in courses that require its use. One may conclude that these courses would increase computer literacy, reduce Computer Phobia which consequently improves Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources.

2. The study was further conducted to find out the relationship between Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources amongunder Graduate Students(Arts and Science)with their E-learning orientation. The results showed that there was significant positive relationship Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources ofunder Graduate Studentsin relation to E- Learning Orientation. Hence it implies higher the E-Learning Orientation higher will be the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources or lesser the E-Learning Orientation decreases the Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources. The study demonstrated that there was a statistically significant correlation between student attitudes toward technology and their levels of access to various technologies. Students who had better access to technology and the Internet generated stronger positive attitudes. The level of access to technology and its reliability influence student there is a need for the provision of appropriate training at different levels, the development of expertise in e-learning use, and research to gather data and inform future developments. These are important tasks that require substantial attention and great effort from the government to ensure the development of adequate awareness, positive attitudes, and improved motivation towards e- learning which will intern increases positive Attitude towards Using Cyber Resources in students.

Conclusion

In the digital era, the cyber resources play an important role in both teaching and learning. Cyber is a prefix used to describe a person, thing, or idea as part of the computer and information age. Cyber resources include mainly all the online applications of computer, like email, web based applications, search engines and so on. Attitude towards Cyber Resources is an expression of favour or disfavour toward cyber resources which play an important role in learning. It enhances learning process and makes learning accurate and up-to-date. In the digital era, the cyber resources play an important role in both teaching and learning.

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